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LINKING URBAN LANDSCAPES TO ECOSYSTEM SERVICES AND CARBON FLOWS A EUROPEAN ANALYSIS

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Linking urban landscapes to ecosystem services and carbon flows

A European analysis

Marlène Delphine Fabienne BOURA

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Abstract

In the context of population growth and urbanisation, associated with an increase in the concentration of GHG (greenhouse gases) in the atmosphere, the impact of human activities on climate change is ever increasing. Simultaneously, the pressure on natural ecosystems, especially in and around cities, is intensifying. Natural ecosystems associated with the urban forest (all elements of urban vegetation) can play an important role in mitigating climate change, especially in cities. In addition, they can contribute positively to the quality of life and wellbeing of urban dwellers. The dynamic of the services they provide, to Earth and mankind, vary between and within cities and need to be better understood.

This thesis focusses on the impact of the spatial integration of the urban forest on the supply and demand of ecosystem services. The main objective is to provide insights into how urban forms and their inner characteristics are related to ecosystem services (ES) and to carbon dioxide (CO₂) profiles. In particular, it analyses the level of integration of the urban forest present within the built up footprint and anthropogenic land, in order to derive the effect of their spatial distribution on 5 ES provided by the urban forest.

The research is conducted at detailed spatial resolution for hundreds of Functional Urban Areas (FUAs) in Europe. It is structured as follows.

We built an Urban Forest typology for Europe: 689 urban areas in 10 clusters and gathered in 4 groups (Forest cities, Herbaceous cities, Anthropogenic cities and Standard European cities). The typology reveals how nature is spatially integrated into urban structures. The metrics used in the typology reflect the potential supply and demand of 5 urban ES associated with the urban forest: micro climate regulation, macro climate regulation, air quality regulation, rainwater runoff regulation and physical and mental health. All cities are ranked according to an overall score. One of our main conclusions is that, given the same forest cover, a spatially integrated urban forest makes cities less sensitive to urban stressors.

We then focus on a specific regulatory ES: macro climate regulation. The Urban Carbon

Balance (UCB) model has been developed and allows the estimation of the urban carbon balance at a high spatial and temporal resolution for a large number of areas, using land used and emission data. The UCB model has been applied to 802 European urban areas. We downscaled anthropogenic CO₂ emissions to a spatial resolution of 1 ha before applying a temporal decomposition of annual, monthly and finally daily emissions, following year-, sector- and country-specific guidelines. For a typical day of each month, we simulate 3 steady-state situations for the dispersion and sequestration of CO₂ molecules. We find that the urban structure and the level of integration of the urban forest contribute positively to helping urban areas sequester their own emissions.

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Many thanks to my family and friends for their support and to Victor for your love and support during the ups and downs.

"We need a rapid and deep change in the way we do business, how we generate power, how we build cities, how we move, and how we feed the world. If we don't urgently change our way of life, we jeopardize life itself."

– António Guterres (2019)
UN Secretary General

"It is particularly ironic that the battle to save the world's remaining healthy ecosystems will be won or lost not in the tropical forests or coral reefs that are threatened but on the streets of the most unnatural landscapes on the planet."

– Christopher Flavin (2007)
Former President of Worldwatch Institute

1. General introduction

This thesis studies the link between **urban forms and patterns** and the **potential provision of ecosystem services provided by the urban forest**. More particularly, it investigates the link between urban landscape characteristics and **five ecosystem services impacting human health and well-being** before presenting and applying **a new approach for estimating urban carbon budgets**. The overall objective of this work is to improve the appraisal of pressure on and demand for ecosystem services within urban areas and the contribution of these urban areas to climate change. Better insights from the implication of different urban structures will assist urban planning decisions to support ecological transitions and cleaner economies and societies.

1.1 Background

Anthropogenic activities and consequences

Planetary boundaries are finite. It took about 10 billion years from the Big Bang, for the Earth to be created and made suitable for life and then for the first human species to appear (Harari, 2011). Life on Earth, for the animals currently existing, relies on the composition of the atmosphere, the air temperature, the quality of the soils to be able to provide with food, and the availability of drinkable water (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). Over the past few decades, all these elements have been neglected in the race for more successful economies and associated lifestyles. They are now at stake and threaten the Earth's ecological limits (O'Neill et al., 2018). This has resulted in a loss of biosphere integrity (biodiversity loss and extinctions, see Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005, Mace et al., 2014, Steffen et al., 2015), biochemical flows, land-system change and climate change (Steffen et al., 2015).

Rockström et al. (2009) first defined the planetary boundaries as: "a function of the degree of risk the global community is willing to take, e.g., how close to an uncertainty zone around a dangerous level or threshold of a Earth System process humanity is willing to place itself, and/or for how long a boundary can temporarily be transgressed

Figure 1.1: Number of social thresholds achieved versus number of biophysical boundaries transgressed for different countries, scaled by population (O'Neill et al., 2018)

before a threshold is crossed". The level of pressure on different planetary boundaries¹ is increasingly studied (Rockström et al., 2009, Steffen et al., 2015, Raworth, 2017, O'Neill et al., 2018), as is the relationship between biophysical and social indicators (Raworth, 2017, O'Neill et al., 2018). Economic prosperity and high quality of life seem to go hand in hand with transgressing global boundary thresholds (see Figure 1.1). Yet, according to O'Neill et al. (2018), a significant reduction in the use of natural resources by the world's most prosperous economies is possible without threatening their quality of life, and would therefore allow a more even sharing of natural resources with other countries.

The planetary boundary of climate change (or tipping point) is represented by the global average CO₂ concentration with a threshold of 350 ppm (Steffen et al., 2015). The concentration has increased from 280 ppm in 1750 to 415.88 ppm in Feb 2021 (Lindsay, 2020, NOAA, 2021). In addition, the land conversion planetary boundary is represented using the global coverage of forest lands, which is set to at least 75% (Steffen et al., 2015). In 2020, the global forest cover was at 31.2% in the world and 38.3% in EU28 (FAO, 2020). It should also be noted that the different planetary boundaries are interlinked in the sense that the degradation of one of them can lead to the deterioration of the others as a feedback effect, as presented by Mace et al. (2014).

Climate change is a global phenomenon resulting from a combination of processes at local, regional and global scales, including the increasing concentration of greenhouse gases (GHGs) induced by human activities (IPCC, 2015, 2019), causing an increase in extreme weather events at regional and local scales (IPCC, 2019). It is part

¹The planetary boundaries they refer to are: climate change, ocean acidification, stratospheric ozone depletion, global phosphorus and nitrogen cycles, atmospheric aerosol loading, freshwater use, land use change, biodiversity loss and chemical pollution.

of a feedback loop whose impacts are felt at different magnitudes in different places of the world (IPCC, 2019, 2021). For instance, the poles suffer at a much higher magnitude from these contemporaneous changes, and in time, they are likely to accelerate the consequences of climate change if and when the tipping point is reached (Ballinger et al., 2020, IPCC, 2021).

Why urban areas?

Anthropogenic emissions are released during the process of burning fossil fuels due to human activities (transport, heating, cooling, energy production). These activities mainly take place in cities, which are responsible for three thirds of anthropogenic emissions (IEA, 2008), even though they account for only a tiny fraction of emerged lands on Earth - 0.19 to 3% depending on how urban is defined (Liu et al., 2014). The demographic growth (United Nations, 2019), land-conversion (Seto et al., 2012) and modern societies' production and consumption modes (IPCC, 2019) have dramatic impacts on human wellbeing and natural environments and is felt at different scales (Seto et al., 2012, IPCC, 2019).

Churkina (2012) highlights the feedback relationship between urbanised land and global change. Human settlements impact global change through local urban heat island effect (UHI), GHG emissions, air and water pollution. On the other hand, global change has an impact on human settlements through regional heat waves, sea level rise or water scarcity. In the urban context, the vegetation is providing a large set of ecosystem services (Bolund and Hunhammar, 1999, Larondelle and Haase, 2013). Ecosystem services coming from vegetated land impact human health and wellbeing by providing access to natural land, improving the air and water quality, and having a positive impact on the urban heat island effect (UHI). The GHG emissions emitted in urban areas are impacting the climate at regional and global scales due to its cumulative effect (IPCC, 2015). Yet, knowledge about the relationship between urban form and ecosystem services remains limited (Alberti, 2005, Frank et al., 2012, Dobbs et al., 2014, Grass et al., 2019).

A fundamental hypothesis in this work is that the internal structure of cities, meaning the spatial integration, organisation and relative distance of different types of LU is significantly impacting urban ecosystems. In other words, we consider that the famous statement of Turner "space matters" is key in the valuation of the contribution of urban areas.

The aim of this thesis is to investigate how the urban landscape configuration impacts ecosystem services and the carbon cycle, and the role of the urban vegetation in these relationships.

Research questions

1. What types of urban structures are in Europe? How is the urban forest integrated with urban landscapes?
2. How does the urban structure impact the demand and supply of regulatory ecosystem services?
3. How does the urban structure impact the carbon profile and the carbon contribution of urban areas to the global cycle?
4. Can a high resolution and standardised method be developed to estimate urban carbon flows based on land use data for replication and comparison?

1.2 Urban forest, land use and urban landscape

Urban forest and ecosystem services

The repurposing of natural land to functional land for human activities has been part of human history since the beginning of agriculture (Foley et al., 2005). The demographic growth which followed the agricultural revolution led to the creation of the first cities and mega-cities in Mesopotamia (O'Sullivan, 2006). It came along a delocalisation of agricultural and farming activities away from core cities and the industrial revolutions led to more energy consumption and air polluting activities within and around cities (Foley et al., 2005, O'Sullivan, 2006). As shown in Figure 1.2, this process involves a high and fast decrease of natural land. Yet nature did not disappear from human settlements and its study and management led to the creation of an interdisciplinary field: urban forestry.

It is a fairly new field of research which definition and development as we know it nowadays has faced controversy and opposition across the world, even among foresters (Konijnendijk et al., 2006). It is defined as "managing trees and forest resources in and around urban community for the physiological, sociological, economic, and aesthetic benefits trees provide to society" (Helms, 1998). The *urban forest* corresponds to individual trees and associated vegetation, as well as urban woods and woodlands, within urban areas. The different vegetation units (street trees, grasslands, shrubs, parks, forests) are seen as a whole: the urban forest (Konijnendijk et al., 2006).

The presence of the urban forest and its ecosystem comes with a set of advantages (or services) which, if well understood, can help cities to become more sustainable. Multiple attempts have been made to define and classify ecosystem services (ES - de Groot, 2006, Wallace, 2007, Costanza, 2008, Danley and Widmark, 2016). Overall ES can be described as ecosystem functions that provide a benefit to human beings. Ecosystem functions are all the physical, chemical and biological interactions (fluxes and transformations) at play within a given ecosystem or between ecosystems (de Groot, 2006, White and Brown, 2007). de Groot (2006) proposed a classification of ES in four functions: regulation, habitat, production and information. Regulation functions are the ones that maintain the "essential processes and life support systems" (de Groot, 2006). They are associated to "climate, hydrological and biochemical cycles, earth surface processes, and a variety of biological processes" (Hein et al., 2006). If well understood, natural mechanisms happening in natural and anthropogenic lands, also called nature based solutions (NBS), can provide fast and affordable alternatives to accompany ecological transition.

Urban development and drawbacks

The urban form can be characterised by five elements: land use, transport infrastructure, density, building type and layout according to Dempsey et al. (2010). The process of urbanisation is nowadays characterised along various aspects/phenomenon in the world. An increase of: artificial lands, land use change, population size, share of urban dwellers in the total population (United Nations, 2014, 2019) and landscape fragmentation (EEA, 2006, EEA and FOEN, 2011, 2016). The world's population has been increasing very fast in the last decades: from 3,033.2 to 7,550.3 millions (+149%) in the period 1960-2017 (United Nations, 2019). It evolved slower in Europe, respectively from 605.9 to 742.1 millions (United Nations, 2019), so an increase of 22%. Europe is known for its high share of urban dwellers (74% in 2018 according to United Nations, 2019). The European population was predominantly living in urban settlements since the 50's, while at the world's scale, the shift happened in 2007 (United Nations, 2014). The concentration of human in limited areas suggests a higher level of pressure on natural

Figure 1.2: Land-use transitions (Foley et al., 2005)

ecosystems within urban areas, and hence, of their ecosystem services.

Urban developments result in diverse urban forms when considering human settlements (artificial land such as buildings and transport infrastructures) and natural land (vegetation and water bodies, EEA, 2017). The intensity of pressure on natural ecosystems can be influenced by the urban form (Makido et al., 2012, Churkina, 2012, Des Rosiers et al., 2017). Jabareen (2006) identified four types of supposed "sustainable" urban forms: compact cities, neotraditional development ("sustainable" transportation; diversity of housing; compactness, mixed land uses; greening), urban containment (policies of compactness) and eco-cities (urban vegetation; ecological and cultural diversity; passive solar design).

Compactness is generally characterised by a high level of density and connectivity of artificial land (Neuman, 2005). However, compact cities or urban containment policies² did not demonstrate empirical savings in energy consumption - and thus tangible environmental benefits - in the transport sector as shown by Breheny (1995). Worse, the compactness of artificial soils is responsible for the intensification of local extreme weather events such as floods, with increased water runoff and urban heat island effect due to the materials used and the albedo associated with urban constructions (Taha, 1997, Grimmond, 2007, Semadeni-Davies et al., 2008, Akbari et al., 2012, Oke, 2015). Still, the "belief" in compact cities remains persistent nowadays (Jabareen, 2006, Ewing and Hamidi, 2015).

Urban sprawl is the expansion of urban areas through the conversion of natural land into artificial or semi-natural land, which tends to increase the fragmentation or loss of natural land (EEA, 2006, EEA and FOEN, 2016). There is no consensus in the literature on

²Containment refers to "policies that impose geographical constraints on urban growth to contain sprawl and restrain urban growth" [Jabareen, 2006]

the definition of urban sprawl (Jaeger et al., 2010). According to Bruegmann (2005), it is an ancient process, already observable in Mesopotamia and later in ancient Rome: "as cities have become economically mature and prosperous, they have tended to spread outward at decreasing densities". Urban sprawl can emerge from multiple reasons and be observed via multiple factors: population growth, housing market pressure, natural barriers, policies (OECD, 2018). Therefore, multiple dimensions need to be taken into account to assess the level and characteristics of sprawl (Arribas-Bel et al., 2011, OECD, 2018): some related to the morphology (scattering/fragmentation, connectivity/dispersion - variation of urban population density -, availability of open space), and others to the internal composition (density - average urban population density, population-to-density allocation, land-to-density allocation -, decentralisation, land use mix). Spatial dispersion of activities (residence, work, school, public and private services, natural amenities) increases commuting and car dependency (as public transport provision becomes more expensive as the agglomeration expands). The resulting increase in car use is likely to increase emissions from the transport sector. In addition, the loss of natural land has a direct impact on the local climate and the potential for climate change mitigation.

Scope of the study

In this work, urban areas are defined using the Functional Urban Areas³ (FUAs) proposed by the OECD (2013). Instead of considering administrative boundaries of cities it looks for its real footprint in terms of anthropogenic activities, represented by the population density and the commuting zone around the core city in terms of residence and work place (OECD, 2013, Dijkstra and Poelman, 2012, Dijkstra et al., 2019). Urban boundaries using this definition are available in many countries across the world, but the majority are located in Europe as of today⁴. Nevertheless, the methodology is well described and could be replicated for other areas (Dijkstra and Poelman, 2012, Dijkstra et al., 2019). From these FUAs, the European Environment Agency proposes the Urban Atlas 2012 (UA2012, EEA, 2016): a vectorial land use database at the European scale (38 countries included, see Table A.2) at resolution ± 5 m. Each spatial dataset considers 29 land use or land cover categories for 808 FUAs around European cities having more than 50,000 inhabitants by 2012.

This dissertation first considers four regulating functions and include, following Daily (1997) the ecosystem functions that impact (directly or indirectly) human health and wellbeing (Chapters 2 and 3). It then focuses on the macro climate regulating ecosystem service (Chapters 4 and 5). We characterise the existing urban patterns using landscape metrics to assess the pattern of anthropogenic land, the urban forest, and their spatial configuration (Chapter 2). It also investigates the relationship of the urban type with five urban ES and the urban carbon cycle (Chapter 5).

³"A functional urban area can be defined in four steps: 1) Identify an urban centre: a set of contiguous, high density (1,500 residents per square) grid cells with a population of 50,000 in the contiguous cells; 2) Identify a city: one or more local units that have at least 50% of their residents inside an urban centre; 3) Identify a commuting zone: a set of contiguous local units that have at least 15% of their employed residents working in the city; 4) A functional urban area is the combination of the city with its commuting zone." Dijkstra et al. [2019]

⁴Europe + Australia, Canada, Chile, Colombia, Israel, Japan, Korea, Mexico, New Zealand, United States. See <https://www.oecd.org/cfe/regionaldevelopment/functionalurbanareasbycountry.htm>

1.3 Urban Forest Ecosystem Services (UFES)

Compared to natural ecosystems, urban ecosystems deal with different climate, soil, vegetation or social dynamic conditions and disturbances, all affecting ecosystem functions (Trepl, 1995, Pickett et al., 1997, 2001, Niemelä, 1999, Alberti, 2005, 2008, Livesley et al., 2016). In this study, we consider five ES that can be assessed with our data and are most relevant to the urban forest: (1) macro climate regulation; (2) micro climate regulation; (3) air quality regulation; (4) rainwater regulation; and (5) mental and physical health. The UFES 1 to 4 are well represented by Livesley et al. (2016), see Figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3: Urban forest ecosystem service and function: at the tree, street and city scale (Livesley et al., 2016)

Macro climate and air quality regulation

Anthropogenic activities associated to human settlements can be grouped by sectors: transportation, buildings, industry, agro-forestry, electricity and heat production and other sectors such as waste treatment and management (United Nations, 1998, IPCC, 2015). Each sector emits gas pollutants, dusts or particulate matters (PMs) into the atmosphere, and more intensively within and around urban areas (IEA, 2008). Some have a local impact and deteriorate urban air quality and human health, others have a wider impact and constitute greenhouse gases that disturb the climate at the global scale. Forests, trees and wetlands are the most important elements of the Urban Forests here. They mitigate air pollutants (Nowak et al., 2006, 2013, Selmi et al., 2016) at the local scale and contribute to the macro climate regulation by sequestering CO₂ to accumulate biomass (Nowak, 1993, Nowak and Crane, 2002, Turner et al., 2008, Scharenbroch, 2012, Strohbach and Haase, 2012). To a lesser extent, parks and leisure facilities (Mexia et al., 2018), as well as urban soils (Pouyat et al., 2002, Brown et al., 2012), also contribute in the mitigation of CO₂ concentration in urban areas.

Micro climate regulation

The Urban Heat Island (UHI) is a major micro climate stress. It corresponds to the night cooling difference between urban centres and the rural areas around (Oke, 1982). The temperature difference comes from multiple factors (Grimmond, 2007): thermal characteristics of surfaces (built-up areas have higher heat capacity, storage and conductivity), sky view factor (impacting solar and terrestrial radiation, heat transport and wind speed), change in moisture (increasing water runoff and decreased evapotranspiration due to a smaller share of natural lands), air pollution and anthropogenic heat fluxes (coming from heating and cooling systems, machineries and vehicles).

Rainwater drainage

Urban areas have, almost by definition, large amounts of impervious land (roads, transport infrastructures, buildings and associated activity land). When the water does not infiltrate, it risks to accumulate in some areas and to provoke runoffs. The increase of impervious surfaces thus impacts the soils' filtering and runoff regulating function (OECD, 2018). In addition to increasing flood risk (Semadeni-Davies et al., 2008), water runoff on impervious surface decreases the potential of groundwater recharge, which in turn has negative consequences on the evapotranspiration efficiency (Haase and Nuisl, 2007, Haase, 2009, Poelmans et al., 2010). Runoffs also reduce the quality of drinking water as surface contaminants are carried into water ways and groundwater (EPA, 1994).

Mental and physical health

Exposure and access to vegetation provide significant health benefits as shown in the meta-analyses provided by Bowler et al. (2010), van den Berg et al. (2015), Twohig-Bennett and Jones (2018) and Wolf et al. (2020). Health benefits are evaluated regarding specific clinic measurements incidences, physiological testing and self-reported mood states. Viewing of vegetation and forest bathing (also known as *shinrin-yoku*) have a direct and significant impact on stress levels in humans (Yamaguchi et al., 2006, Park et al., 2007, Wolf et al., 2020). It also decreases the prevalence of mental illness (van den Bosch and Ode Sang, 2017, Wolf et al., 2020). Access to vegetation - semi-natural (parks, sports infrastructures, etc.) or natural environments (forests, woodlands, wetlands, meadows) - is hence a key parameter (Tzoulas et al., 2007, Wolch et al., 2014, Donovan, 2017, van den Bosch and Ode Sang, 2017, Wolf et al., 2020).

These elements are supporting our willingness to understand the urban structure in the

context of the demand for and supply of urban ES. Which landscape configuration(s) best support a positive budget of UES with the urban forest? Which actions should be prioritised in order to optimize cities as carbon sinks? More insights on the urban structure type is fundamental to understand which urban areas are more sensitive to, or contributing to ecological challenges. Past research already tried to highlight the link between the urban form and ecosystem services or disservices (Dobbs et al., 2014, Grass et al., 2019). Yet, urban areas are complex and evolving systems also associated to socio-ecological challenges as there is no homogeneity across space.

1.4 Organisation of the thesis and summary

Figure 1.4: Chapters organisation, main outputs and research questions (RQ)

Chapter 2: Urban Forest Typology in Europe and Chapter 3: Urban Forests as Regulating Ecosystems: Ranking of European Cities

Urban areas exhibit a large variety of internal land use patterns which can affect ecosystems services (ES). The valuation of ES provided by urban forests can help us to assess urban pressures on the environment and the wellbeing of citizens. Our aim is to understand how ES relate to the spatial integration of urban forests within urbanised land across European cities.

We cluster and rank 689 large urban areas of Europe. Our *Urban Forest Ecosystem Services* (UFES) typology and the scoring of potential ES both account not only for land cover and vegetation around anthropogenic land, but also for their relative spatial distribution and configuration within each urban region via landscape metrics. We focus on five services - macro climate, micro climate, air quality, water runoff and health regulation - and provide a score per UFES in addition to an overall score for each city. Our results show that cities can be mapped into 4 main groups - Forest, Herbaceous, Anthropogenic and Standard European Cities - and further divided into 10 clusters. Forest Cities have high to very high UFES scores. Most anthropogenic clusters represent the cities with a lower capacity to supply services relative to their demand. For equal

levels of vegetation cover, cities that best integrate natural land are less sensitive to urban stressors.

Chapter 4: UCB Model - High resolution spatio-temporal model of CO₂ emissions and sequestration in cities

The ongoing climate change is caused by the increasing and cumulating amount of anthropogenic emissions. CO₂ is the most important one in terms of proportion, and most of the anthropogenic activities associated to the combustion of fossil fuels take place in cities. Yet very little is known about the contribution of urban carbon cycles to regional and global carbon cycles. The main reason is the lack of high resolution data for large urban areas and the lack of comparability between case studies. In this article, we propose a new methodology to assess the carbon balance of urban areas in a comparable and systematic manner. The High Resolution Urban Carbon Balance (UCB) Model relies on open source data for replicability. It allows to spatially downscale sectoral annual CO₂ emissions, and to estimate annual CO₂ sequestration from the urban forest at a spatial resolution of 1 ha. Both annual CO₂ emissions and sequestration can then be downscaled over time to month and average day of each month. The carbon balance is expressed in two ways: the absolute balance as the total amount of emissions sequestered over a given period. The relative balance as the percentage of emissions removed from the atmosphere by the urban forest over a given period. The model has been applied on 802 European urban areas.

Chapter 5: Urban carbon balance and urban patterns in Europe

The contribution of cities to climate change is significant and more and more urban areas and countries are now trying to take action in order to reduce their urban footprint. The reduction of anthropogenic emissions is fundamental but can be reinforced via the use of nature-based solutions. The urban forest has the capacity to absorb part of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions but the spatial dynamics at play remain unclear. What type of urban organisation could lead a city to become a carbon sink? Under which limitations? In this article, we assess the carbon profile of 802 European urban areas. These are defined after the CO₂ emissions, sequestration and carbon balance. We also investigate how different types of urban patterns can impact the urban carbon balance.

Our results show that some specific urban types can present a smaller carbon footprint. A large urban forest cover does not always guarantee that an urban area will have the capacity to uptake a large share of its own emissions. In addition, under some conditions, urban areas qualified as "Anthropogenic Cities" can also mitigate its contribution to the regional and global carbon cycles. The good performances in terms of relative carbon balance is explained by a spatial integration of the urban forest within the urban core. Yet, the presence of intense industrial emissions can be a limiting factor.

Outputs of the PhD thesis

By September 2021:

- "Land cover, landscape metrics and typology of European cities for Urban Forest Ecosystem Services (UFES) evaluation" (dataset) Zenodo, 2020. [Chapter 2](#)
- "Urban Forests Ecosystems in Europe: Types and Ranking of Cities" Ecosystem Services (*in revision*). [Chapters 2 and 3](#)
- "UCB Model - High resolution spatio-temporal model of CO₂ emissions and sequestration in cities" (*in progress*) [Chapter 4](#)
- "High Resolution Urban Carbon Balance (UCB) Model" (dataset) Zenodo, 2021. [Chapter 4 & 5](#)

-
- “Urban carbon balance and urban patterns in Europe” (*in progress*) Chapter 5

Urban Forest Ecosystem Services (UFES)

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2. Urban Forest Typology in Europe

Accessibility

This chapter is under review as a journal article. The UFES database from this article is available on the platform Zenodo (Boura and Caruso, 2020) and on GitHub (<https://github.com/mboura/UFES>).

2.1 Introduction

Urbanisation, increasing population and modern societies' production and consumption modes have dramatic impacts on human wellbeing and natural environments. Cities are *de facto* places where many of these impacts are generated because they concentrate activities and people. Concentrating population is also more likely to preserve natural ecosystems beyond the urban fringes than weaker forms of urbanisation such as urban sprawl, which fragments land at the fringe and further into the countryside (EEA and FOEN, 2011). In order to counteract some of the negative effects of concentration, afforesting cities has appeared as one of the key policy levers with positive impacts at the local scale. Some have been intended to preserve ecological corridors within cities (Vejre et al., 2007, City of Helsinki, 2009), whilst others have been intended to limit urban expansion by enforcing green belts around cities (Office of the Deputy Prime Minister, 1995, Konijnendijk, 2003). If applied across many cities, afforestation could have a potential impact at the global scale. Tweaking dense urban areas to accommodate more vegetation, however, is a challenge, because of the competition for land (Caruso et al., 2015, Haaland and Konijnendijk, 2015). Yet theoretical research shows that greenness is key to increasing residential density, to the benefit of both citizens and nature (Caruso et al., 2015), and there is plenty of empirical evidence on the benefits of vegetation for urbanites.

Following a definition by Konijnendijk et al. (2006), the *urban forest* (UF) includes all individual trees (in backyards, parks and streets), all associated vegetation (grassland,

shrubs), as well as all urban woods and woodland available within an urban area. Where the urban area itself starts and ends is obviously important in this definition, since vegetation generally increases as one moves towards the periphery of cities. Yet the driving idea of the *urban forest* concept is to stress the benefits of the proximity between natural and man-made land, and the need for "*managing trees and forest resources in and around urban community for the physiological, sociological, economic, and aesthetic benefits trees provide to society*" (Helms, 1998).

Urban forests provide a large set of ecosystem services (ES), including global climate regulation, local climate regulation, air quality regulation, noise reduction, erosion regulation, surface water runoff regulation, water purification, sewage treatment, habitat provision, biomass provision, provision of recreational, natural and cultural heritage, and health benefits (Dobbs et al., 2011, Burkhard et al., 2012, Lachowycz and Jones, 2013, Dobbs et al., 2014, Burkhard et al., 2014, Twohig-Bennett and Jones, 2018). These services occur at the tree, street and urban scales (Livesley et al., 2016). Links have been carefully drawn between UF components and ES, typically with detailed structural elements of the UF (e.g. trees heights, diameter, mix of species, etc.) used in the assessment (see Dobbs et al., 2011). However, this is a huge surveying effort that is not easy to replicate consistently across many cities.

Land cover-based approaches have been directly associated with the evaluation of ES (Burkhard et al., 2014). Yet they miss the spatial interaction between supply and demand that is very necessary in urban contexts, since many of the services happen through access and proximity between concentrated human activities and vegetated land. This is an interaction that we assume can be proxied from landscape metrics, at least for the ES that are most specific to the UF, which we call UFES for "**Urban Forest Ecosystem Services**". We know from landscape ecology that the relative position of land cover patches or their shape also significantly impact ecosystems. Alberti (2005) for example suggests landscape metrics that reveal the impact of urbanisation on ecosystems (among others: road density and crossings, mean urban and vegetation patch size, or measures of the level of adjacency between urban and forest patches). Frank et al. (2012) propose a set of spatial metrics to explicitly assess ES provision, including landscape fragmentation, naturalness, land use intensity and connectivity. However, to the best of our knowledge, the relationship between urban patterns (or landscape structures) and ecosystem services is still mostly limited today to an accounting approach and is applied to few delimited urban areas (e.g. Steinhardt et al., 1999, Escobedo et al., 2006, Burkhard et al., 2012, Walz and Stein, 2014, Graça et al., 2018).

We contend in the present paper that not only the quantity of vegetation per unit of surface or per capita is important, but also the proximity between and the relative spatial arrangement of vegetation and built-up land. We want to create a typology taking into account landscape metrics in addition to land use cover.

On the European continent, urban forest patterns have been influenced by topography, planning history and scale, urban forest cultures or climate zones. We expect geographical variations in UFES across Europe due to these. More preserved natural land is expected in northern Europe and most elevated zones, often associated with colder climates (Peel et al., 2007), lower population densities (Kaplan et al., 2009, Eurostat, 2016) and lower deforestation rates (Kaplan et al., 2009). By contrast, western and central Europe has faced a big drop in forest cover (from almost 80% to less than 10%; see Kaplan et al., 2009). Whether these trends can be extrapolated within cities is, however,

unclear. Bell et al. (2005) defined four European Urban Forest Cultures (UFC), based on the relationship urban dwellers have with vegetation and the historical management of forests. Whether these zones appear in forest ecosystem benefits is questioned here.

Our main aim is to explicitly account for land cover and landscape structures whilst undertaking this evaluation, so that we can better understand the ecosystem services potential of various urban structures, and not just from aggregate land quantities. Results from previous studies are difficult to generalise because of important heterogeneities across case studies, a melange of urban and non-urban cases, and because the extent of urban areas and the input data are not necessarily consistent across cases. Therefore, we scale up this research by providing an assessment of UFES across a large set of cities in Europe - i.e. 689 towns and cities that have over 50,000 inhabitants - each comprising an urban core and its functional periphery (defined similarly across the entire continent, using population densities and commuting thresholds; see OECD, 2013, for details).

We clarify the current situation in Europe by offering first a typology that situates each urban area against all the others in terms of their internal structure (as suggested by Wentz et al., 2018), and second, a ranking of cities along a potential UFES index that accounts for urban structures (see Chapter 3). We believe this is an important move towards a generic and statistically robust understanding of how ES relate to the integration of urban forests within urban fabrics. This is also a move towards designing policies that are adapted to key elements of the urban context rather than a one-size-fits-all recipe.

2.2 Data and methods

The method is summarised in Figure 2.1 and the entire process is handled using the R software (R Core Team, 2019, version 3.6.1).

2.2.1 Data and Functional Urban Areas

The definition of urban areas is always tricky (Parr, 2007) and can lead to substantial differences in environmental assessment results and a lack of comparability (McIntyre, 2010, Raciti et al., 2012, Liu et al., 2014). This is particularly the case when the object under study directly depends on different land uses, because artificial and natural land follow reverse distance gradients (Lemoy and Caruso, 2018) and because the more extended the area studied, the greater the risk of it interfering with another (Thomas et al., 2018). We opt for a functional definition of cities because UFES are about the locations and patterns of human activities, and location decisions themselves depend heavily on transportation (specifically commuting from residential locations). If we were to focus solely on the morphological envelope of cities, we would artificially shrink the natural part of cities and many of the human-nature interactions happening in the suburbs. We would also then take out most of the policy levers that policymakers could activate (urban development planning or afforestation strategies). By contrast, a wider regional perspective would incorporate much natural land that is seldom related to urban activities, and may gather several cities under the same unit.

We use the OECD (2013)'s Functional Urban Areas (FUAs), defined on the basis of population density and daily commuting thresholds (see OECD, 2013, Dijkstra and Poelman, 2012, Dijkstra et al., 2019, for details) and the Urban Atlas 2012 (UA2012, EEA, 2016) for land cover defined for these FUAs in Europe. The original database contains about 800 urban areas, i.e. the European cities with more than 50,000 inhabitants in 2012.

Figure 2.1: Steps of the methodology

Our study considers 689 of them, after subsetting based on the presence of each type of land cover used in our computed metrics. All urban areas considered are mapped onto Figure 2.2 and a complete list is available in Table A.3 (in Appendix).

2.2.2 Geoprocessing

The Urban Atlas classifies land into 29 categories. We reclassify the categories to merge those associated with anthropogenic pressure and demand for UFES (anthropogenic land with intensive human activities) and to merge natural and semi-natural land associated with potential UFES provision. We end up with the following 8 land use categories: forests, wetlands, herbaceous, artificial green, roads, (other) transport infrastructure, residential and non-residential built up. In addition to these 8 classes, we further define two thematically aggregated versions: *vegetation* (aggregation of artificial green, forest, herbaceous and wetlands), and *impervious* land (aggregation of all the anthropogenic land use (LU): residential, non-residential, roads, and transport infrastructure). From these reclassified vector data, we look at three types of metrics to characterise each urban region. The metrics were selected based on data constraints and our qualitative understanding of the literature, stressing a need to capture interactions between land uses and the form of urbanised or vegetated patches (see Chapter 3).

(i) The first set of metrics, i.e. land use proportions, are obtained in a straightforward

Figure 2.2: 689 Functional Urban Areas (> 50 k inhabitants) after EEA (2016)

manner from the polygon vectors, by dividing the area occupied by a land use category by the total FUA area. We do so for the 4 original vegetated land uses individually, i.e. ‘artificial green’, ‘forest’, ‘herbaceous’ and ‘wetlands’ and as a group for the urbanised land, i.e. ‘impervious’, thus resulting in 5 metrics.

(ii) Secondly, we assess the accessibility and the spatial arrangement of anthropogenic land uses and (semi-) natural ones relative to each other through buffers applied to the vector data. We compute the share of (semi-) natural land uses within 3 buffer sizes (500, 1000 and 1500 m) around each anthropogenic land use. We do so for the 3 buffer distances, thus ending with 12 metrics.

(iii) For ‘forests’, we compute 7 indices, i.e. mean and variation of both the surface and contiguity of patches (mean area, area coefficient of variation, mean contiguity, contiguity coefficient of variation), cohesion, division, and edge density. For ‘artificial green’, ‘roads’, ‘residential’ and ‘non-residential’ lands, we compute 4 indices: mean contiguity, cohesion, division, and edge density. This amounts to 23 landscape-related metrics.

Cohesion (in percent) measures the level of connectivity between the patches. Contiguity (*contig*, in $[0, 1]$) measures the level of connectivity within the patches. Division (proportion) gives the level of disaggregation of the patches. Edge density (*edgeD*) is expressed in m/ha, and the coefficient of variation (*cv*) is given by the ratio between the standard deviation and the mean.

From (i), (ii) and (iii) we obtain 40 metrics. In order to avoid duplication of information when building the typology, we subset the metrics using a Pearson’s correlation coefficient threshold. We use a 0.75 absolute value of the correlation coefficient to identify highly correlated groups of variables and keep only one of them per group (Schwarz, 2010, used 0.8 when selecting urban form indicators). We ultimately retain the 23 metrics displayed in Tables 2.1.

Statistic	Min	25 %	Median	Mean	75 %	Max	CV
ForestsPct	0.002	7.010	17.724	20.214	31.000	71.576	0.766
Forests_area_cv	27.407	394.786	699.395	845.020	1,123.076	4,135.068	0.706
Forests_area_mean	1.083	18.532	39.841	63.687	77.689	1,839.658	1.586
Forests_cohesion	58.293	95.715	98.027	96.285	99.195	99.973	0.052
Forests_contig_mean	0.181	0.466	0.504	0.506	0.547	0.735	0.138
Forests_division	0.795	0.993	0.999	0.991	1.000	1.000	0.023
Forests_edgeD	0.004	5.711	9.503	10.107	13.964	34.290	0.605
WetlandsPct	0.000	0.000	0.025	0.354	0.220	11.474	3.090
HerbaceousPct	0.0003	0.153	1.012	5.331	6.654	40.872	1.587
ArtificialPct	0.008	0.320	0.679	1.095	1.393	8.114	1.101
Artificial_cohesion	57.910	77.461	82.655	81.593	86.749	96.615	0.083
Artificial_contig_mean	0.151	0.315	0.356	0.357	0.400	0.593	0.186
Forests_UrbanFabric1500	0.0001	0.187	0.513	1.035	1.048	47.380	2.764
Artificial_UrbanFabric1000	0.002	0.025	0.043	0.067	0.074	2.816	1.933
Vegetation_Roads1500	0.015	0.143	0.240	0.266	0.364	0.804	0.586
Roads_cohesion	10.168	63.472	71.203	68.543	77.949	93.523	0.210
Roads_contig_mean	0.014	0.105	0.120	0.118	0.135	0.191	0.227
Roads_edgeD	0.006	0.387	0.830	1.146	1.524	8.300	0.982
Indus_cohesion	59.362	81.601	84.645	84.320	87.622	95.783	0.057
Indus_contig_mean	0.165	0.280	0.322	0.323	0.361	0.555	0.183
UrbanFabric_cohesion	82.579	91.752	94.067	93.606	95.851	99.508	0.032
UrbanFabric_contig_mean	0.185	0.330	0.385	0.390	0.443	0.723	0.213
ImperviousPct	0.539	6.058	8.969	10.427	13.680	41.978	0.600

Table 2.1: Descriptive statistics of the metrics (*Pct* stands for percentage of the total surface).

2.2.3 Clustering

All metrics are standardised and used in an unsupervised learning algorithm to cluster together cities that have similar characteristics. We use an agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering Analysis (HCA) algorithm and the Ward (1963)'s criteria to minimise the within-cluster variance. We run the algorithm for three different dissimilarity distances (Euclidean, squared Euclidean and inverse Euclidean) and maximise the Dunn (1974)'s index to decide on the optimum number of clusters and type of distance (dissimilarity) to be used.

2.3 Results

2.3.1 Urban Forest integration patterns across Europe

Descriptive statistics for the 23 metrics are shown in Table 2.1 and maps for some standardised metrics are provided in the Appendix (see Figure A.2), in order to provide a visual representation of the variations in their spatial distribution across the continent.

It is important, first of all, to stress that impervious land within European functional urban regions represent on average only about 10% of the total cover, which is half of the forest cover (20%) and almost double the amount of herbaceous land. Artificial green space and wetlands account for a very small relative amount of cover (respectively

1.1% and 0.35% on average).

Secondly, in terms of spatial distribution of the proportions of each type of land use, the highest urbanisation (impervious) values are mostly concentrated along the Manchester-Milan axis, via Benelux and western Germany (long known since Brunet, 1989). In terms of vegetated land, FUAs with large proportions of forest are mainly in the Nordic and Balkan countries, as well as in the north of Turkey. The proportion of herbaceous land has a very skewed distribution (75% of FUAs with less than 6.65%), and the spatial distribution reveals a striking differentiation between southern Europe, Iceland, Ireland and the northern part of the United Kingdom compared to the rest of the continent. Wetlands are rare in urban areas in general: only 66 urban regions, i.e. 10%, have a wetlands cover larger than 1%. Most FUAs have low proportions of artificial green (about 1%), with maxima found in the most populated urban areas (London, Paris, Madrid, Barcelona or Rome for instance), suggesting that this type of amenity (parks, sports facilities, etc.), which is hungry in terms of surface required, can be taken up only when economic agglomeration benefits are high.

Thirdly, and most importantly given our objectives, the coefficients of variation show that there is a strong 'signal' with little 'noise' around the contiguity, cohesion, and division landscape coefficients, whatever the land use. This suggests a clear European model of the local forms of built-up land, vegetation or even roads. This also means that those landscape metrics that relate to the within-integration of patches or particular land uses are not going to discriminate between the potential UFES differences across cities, suggesting that generic policies can be applied. In that respect, it is important to stress that fragmentation, even if not varying greatly, is rather high. The mean and median division indices for Forest are close to 1, indicating that patches of forest at 50 m resolution are mostly single cells in urban areas.

Conversely, there is very great variation for those landscape variables that contrast impervious land categories and vegetation. In particular, there is great variation depending on how close forests and artificial green space are to residential land (Forests_UrbanFabric1500's coefficient of variation is 2.77, Artificial_UrbanFabric1000 is 1.92). The edge density and variation of the areas of forest patches also vary substantially, although to a lesser extent. We can therefore expect large variations in how forests and planned green space benefit citizens in terms of health and wellbeing, or in terms of their capacity to capture local emissions. More positively, the variation also suggests that for those cities that rank low in these aspects, there is room for improvement, as exemplified by the best performing cities along these contrasting criteria.

2.3.2 Urban Forest typology

Dunn's index is maximised with the Euclidean distance metric and 10 clusters. The hierarchy between clusters is available in the dendrogram shown in Figure A.1. In Table A.1, we provide the mean and standard deviation per group and cluster of the metrics used, and the result from the ANOVA tests per cluster, which are all significant at level $\alpha = 0.01$. In addition to these 10 *clusters*, the dendrogram supports the definition of 4 distinct higher-level *groups* that we use to describe urban structures in a simpler way. We name each group after interpreting Figure 2.3's boxplots: *Forest Cities*, *Herbaceous Cities*, *Anthropogenic Cities* and *Standard European Cities*, and number the clusters within each group (F1, F2, F3, F4, H1, H2, A1, A2, A3, E1). Figure 2.4 shows the general distribution across Europe of the groups and clusters. The allocation to a cluster is reported for each FUA in Table A.3.

The E group contains a single cluster (E1) that serves as a benchmark for the other three groups, since most of its characteristics are around the European average.s Urban

Figure 2.3: Focus on distribution of standardised metrics per group

Notes: red dots indicate groups' mean; dashed lines are located at ± 2 times the standard deviation.

areas are located from western to eastern Europe, in central latitudes. The barplot on Figure 2.5 shows that this undifferentiated group is important in size (183 cities), but more cities (255) are actually 'more' Anthropogenic (higher values on the variables at the right side of each plot, reflecting a stronger effect of urbanisation). Forest Cities account for 152 FUAs and Herbaceous Cities for 99.

In Figure 2.5 we map representative urban areas for each cluster to provide a sense of their pattern. The representative cities have been chosen from the absolute value of the sum of the differences between their value and the cluster mean value (after standardisation). One can see that in the Forest group, cities are clearly integrating more natural land within and around the urban cores. The Anthropogenic group shows more compact urban cores, with only sparse patches of vegetation within the urban area. In both Herbaceous and Anthropogenic Cities, agricultural is generally favoured

Figure 2.4: Typology of the 689 FUAs (10 clusters from the HCA)

over forested land.

We describe each group further below, as well as each of their clusters, based on boxplots per clusters, which we provide in the appendix, to avoid further cluttering the text here (see Figure A.3).

Figure 2.5: Representative FUAs per cluster and their distribution per group

Forest Cities are characterised by the largest forest coverage, large forest patch size and edge density, high connectivity between those patches (cohesion) and low levels of disaggregation (division). In addition, they present large shares of vegetation around roads, and average to high values of forest and artificial green around residential land. All indices associated with semi-natural and anthropogenic land are lower than average, both in percentage and structure. Cities within this group are mainly located in the Nordic countries (Finland, Sweden and part of Norway); an arc joining the Balkans, Austria and parts of Italy; the northern and southern coasts of Turkey; and the Atlantic coast from northern Portugal to south-western France.

Urban areas that belong to this group integrate vegetated land in a way that supports both regulatory ES services and residential access to vegetated space. In addition, the urban footprint being rather small in relative size, the demand for UFES is also probably small. Yet there is important variability across cases that are reflected by the four associated clusters (F1 to F4):

- Cluster F1 (*Forest Cities - in the strict sense*) contains 20 FUAs that have the least forest fragmentation levels and among the lowest impervious cover. They also have the highest forest cover with very large and numerous patches. Residential land is surrounded to a great extent by vegetation in a 1500 m buffer. We can expect the air quality, micro and macro climate regulations potentials to be very important in this cluster.
- Cluster F2 (*Forest Cities with Land Sharing*) is similar to cluster F1 but contains only 8 urban areas which have extensive cover in terms of both forests and herbaceous land. They have the lowest proportions of impervious cover in the group. Compared to all European cities, they also have the highest proportion of natural and semi-natural land around impervious land. The specificities of this spatial configuration support high levels of provision of UFES with a demand that remains small.
- Cluster F3 (*Sparse Forest Cities*), includes 42 FUAs. Forests patches have a lower level of connectivity (mean contiguity). In addition, the level of aggregation for artificial green, roads, as well as the level of connectivity of roads and residential land, have higher values than the European average. Hence, we can expect a higher demand for micro-climate, air-quality and water-runoff regulation in this cluster of urban areas, compared to the rest of the group.
- Cluster F4 (*Fragmented Forest Cities*) is made of 82 FUAs. Forests tend to be more fragmented, with less forest cover. They show a lower proportion of vegetation around roads compared to the other Forest clusters. Half of these urban areas have a higher level of connectivity of roads than the average. All these elements negatively impact UFES potentials. Yet the demand for UFES is expected to be higher, due to the transport activities, impacting mostly the demand for regulation of macro climate, air quality and rainwater runoff.

Anthropogenic Cities include 255 FUAs mainly located in north-western, Eastern and parts of southern Europe. These cities are characterised by extensive impervious and artificial green cover, and are associated with small amounts of forest, herbaceous and wetland cover. Forests patches are mostly small, disaggregated and fragmented. Artificial green patches are more aggregated and connected and tend to be more present around residential areas than in other groups. Residential areas have rather high levels of aggregation and connectedness. On the other hand, these cities have among the smallest levels of vegetation cover around road networks.

This set of characteristics reveals compact and man-made dominant areas with very low potential for regulatory ES and accessibility to non-artificial vegetated land.

Meanwhile, the demand for UFES is expected to be the highest in this group, due to the anthropogenic urban pattern. The large size of the group calls for caution, and for analysis of specificities across its three clusters (A1 to A3):

- Clusters A1 (*Artificial Cities*) and A2 (*Built-Up Cities*) are rather similar and in line with the general trend of the group, since they account for 85% of the FUAs (respectively 109 and 110). The main differences lie in the fact that cluster A1 shows the highest proportions of impervious and artificial green land (respectively 20.3% and 2.9% on average) and geographically they are mainly located along the Manchester-Milan economic axis, including Benelux and western Germany, plus isolated cities in the south. The very high values of edge density for roads suggest a dense road network in cluster A1. The pressure on UFES is expected to be the highest for cluster A1, followed by cluster A2, compared to the rest of Europe. In addition, the potential supply is expected to be the lowest for A1 (followed by A2), so the gap between the demand and the potential provision should lead to a high deficit for all UFES under consideration in this study.
- Cluster A3 corresponds to *Built-Up Green Cities* and includes the 36 remaining urban areas, mainly located in eastern Europe (parts of Poland, Romania and Bulgaria). They present similar impervious cover as the other groups, with less artificial green cover and slightly more forest cover than urban areas from the same group. Road networks are much less dominant in the landscape. Forest patches are more aggregated and connected than in the A group average. Hence, we can expect less pressure on all regulatory UFES and a higher potential for their provision.

Herbaceous Cities are 99 FUAs predominantly located in southern Europe and Turkey. They also include cities from the north-west Atlantic coast. Both are characterised by a high level of herbaceous cover and low levels of impervious, forest and artificial green surfaces. Forests are present in small patches, with a higher level of division than the average. The indicators associated with anthropogenic land show some variability around the European mean, and a tendency towards low levels of connectivity for artificial green, residential and non-residential built-up land. The proportion of vegetation around roads tend to be more important than the average, but once again, with a notable level of variability. Residential areas have low forest and artificial green covers in their vicinity.

Cities in this group are likely to suffer from a low potential for air quality regulation due to the predominant type of vegetation (herbaceous, sometimes combined with wetlands). The lack of spatial integration between built-up land and vegetation implies a low potential for macro and micro climate regulation, rainwater runoff regulation and health services provision. For those that do not benefit from significant wetlands, the potential is likely to be even more limited. Within this group, the presence of wetlands differentiates two clusters (H1 and H2):

- Cluster H1 (*Wetland Cities*) is composed of 13 FUAs having the largest wetland cover (values from 3.8% to 11.47%), indicating a high potential for micro and macro climate regulation, as well as water runoff regulation. In addition, the forest cover tends to be slightly more important and forest patches have a higher level of connectivity (mean contiguity). These cities would benefit from a slightly higher potential of UFES. However, the demand for regulatory ES from residential and non-residential land is expected to be more important too, given a larger proportion of impervious land.
- Cluster H2 (*Herbaceous Cities in the strict sense*) comprises 86 FUAs mainly concentrated in southern Europe with few or no wetlands. The demand for regulatory ES

from the road network is more important in this cluster, but they also benefit from a higher vegetation cover around roads. The herbaceous land cover is among the highest (an average of 20.52%).

2.4 Discussion and conclusions

Two similar studies exist in Europe, but we differ from them significantly. Firstly, EEA (2017) provides a typology of 300 Functional Urban Areas (FUAs) that includes the proportion of urban green infrastructure (all land with substantial vegetated cover together, from low dense residential area to forests), protected forests (Natura 2000), water and sealed land. By comparison, we consider far more cities, including smaller ones (less than 100 k inhabitants), and a greater diversity of vegetated land cover. Moreover, the EEA (2017) typology does not account for spatial relationships between types of land cover, but only their proportions in terms of surface area. Secondly, ESPON (2018) investigates the fragmentation of forests and vegetation across Europe. However, they focus not on cities, but wider regions, and thus do not directly help us to address the benefits of nature to a growing urban population. Particularly because forests and agricultural areas far from cities and in lower-density contexts account for much of these regional surface areas. Furthermore, both EEA (2017) and ESPON (2018) do not appraise ecosystem services potentials as such.

Urban forest characteristics

As expected, the proportions of forest and herbaceous land vary across Europe and the trend seems to corroborate the UFC presented by Bell et al. (2005), the population densities (Eurostat, 2016) and the deforestation history (Kaplan et al., 2009). The largest areas of forest cover are observed in northern European UFC and Turkey, while FUAs with the lowest forest cover are observed where the herbaceous vegetation cover is the highest: in southern European UFC and part of the north-western European UFC. The level of fragmentation of forest land seems to correlate with the "population density, gross domestic product per capita, volume passenger density, and the quantity of goods loaded and unloaded per capita" as suggested by EEA and FOEN (2011). This statement is verified in the UK, the Netherlands, Belgium, north-eastern Germany, which are part of the economic axis described by Brunet (1989), and Spain, where natural and anthropogenic land are not spatially integrated within urban areas. The most populated urban areas tend to privilege artificial vegetation (such as parks) over natural vegetation.

The future of European FUAs

The IPCC set up potential global warming scenarios using Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) categories based on different ranges of radiative forcing levels by 2100. We use the work of Guerreiro et al. (2018) to put our results in the perspective of the scenarios RCP8.5 and RCP4.5. RCP8.5 is defined as: "One high pathway for which radiative forcing reaches greater than 8.5 W m^{-2} by 2100 and continues to rise for some amount of time (the corresponding ECP assuming constant emissions after 2100 and constant concentrations after 2250)", IPCC (2015). RCP4.5 is defined as: "intermediate stabilization (pathway) in which radiative forcing is stabilized at approximately 4.5 W m^{-2} (...) after 2100 (the corresponding ECPs assuming constant concentrations after 2150)", IPCC (2015).

Southern and north-eastern Europe may have difficulties facing the increase in the number of days of heat waves (up to more 69% of days with the high-impact scenario),

under the RCP8.5 concentration scenario (Guerreiro et al., 2018). Our study shows that Spain, parts of Italy (mainly in the north-east and south) including Sicily and Eastern Turkey, may be more at risk since their urban structure does not support the provision of micro climate regulation ES. Similarly, the regions including the UK, the Netherlands, Belgium, north-eastern Germany and Denmark, as well as parts of Romania and Hungary might be more sensitive to heat stresses.

Droughts are expected to be significantly more frequent in southern Europe: southern Portugal, Spain, southern France, Italy, Albania, Kosovo, Greece and Turkey (Guerreiro et al., 2018, EEA, 2020). The river water deficit is expected to go up to 75% in these regions under the RCP4.5 scenario for the period 2071-2100 compared with 1981-2010 (EEA, 2020). According to the water runoff and micro climate regulation indices, for Portugal, Kosovo, Albania and parts of Italy and Turkey, the increase in intensity is expected to be less important, thanks to their urban forest structure.

Historically, flood events occurred in south-eastern France, England, the basin around the Alps and beyond, as well as Romania and all the surrounding countries (EEA, 2007, 2010). The water discharge is expected to increase mainly in the northern part of Europe (Guerreiro et al., 2018), and more particularly in the UK, Belgium, the Netherlands and the Nordic and Baltic countries, for the period 2051–2100, compared to 1951–2000.

3. Urban Forests as Regulating Ecosystems: Ranking of European Cities

This chapter is a complement to Chapter 2.

3.1 Introduction

Links have been carefully drawn between UF (Urban Forest) components and ES (Ecosystem Services), typically with detailed structural elements of the UF (e.g. trees heights, diameter, mix of species, etc.) used in the assessment (e.g. Dobbs et al., 2011). However, this is a huge surveying effort that is not easy to replicate consistently across many cities.

The multi-functional aspect of ecosystems probably needs to be emphasized more in urban contexts than for ecosystems that are far away from human concentration centres. Landscapes provide service bundles, i.e. "services that repeatedly appear together across space or time" Raudsepp-Hearne et al. (2010). Yet, as pointed out by Haase et al. (2014), most urban ES research does not cover more than one ES, and more often, the focus is on supply rather than demand. One sees here a need to further the interlocking of urbanisation patterns and urban forest patterns, the former being mostly on the demand side, the latter on the supply side.

Through their functioning and the proximity to built environments, urban forests provide many ES (Bolund and Hunhammar, 1999). Among what we call "*Urban Forests Ecosystem Services*" (UFES), one can particularly emphasise their regulatory services such as the reduction of air pollutants by sequestration, deposition and dispersion of particulate matters, gases and dust (Gromke and Ruck, 2009, Wania et al., 2012, Nowak et al., 2013, Janhäll, 2015, Selmi et al., 2016); micro climate regulation via both evapotranspiration and the provision of shadow (Heusinkveld et al., 2014, Gunawardena et al., 2017); macro climate regulation via the absorption of greenhouse gases (mainly CO₂, Nowak et al., 2006, Davies et al., 2011, Strohbach and Haase, 2012); drainage of rainwater due to soils being less sealed (Urgeghe et al., 2010); and the mental and physical health effects of viewing and accessing green spaces (Tzoulas et al., 2007, Markevych et al., 2014). Note

that the regulatory aspects for human health, i.e. access to vegetation from urbanised space, certainly contribute to the cultural services (or leisure amenities) provided by the urban forest. Nevertheless, describing cultural services would require information on the socioeconomic characteristics, preferences and behaviour of urban dwellers (Dickinson and Hobbs, 2017, Rall et al., 2017), which we cannot obtain for all cities. In addition, we would risk double counting between the cultural and the regulatory human health services (Fu et al., 2011).

Likewise, several authors have for example shown the important role of urban patterns – not just urbanisation levels – in relation to (i) pollutant flows (e.g. Des Rosiers et al. (2017) for emissions, Kuittinen et al. (2016), Privitera et al. (2018) for sequestration, Marchi et al. (2017) for uptake, Janhäll (2015) for deposition-dispersion, or Schindler and Caruso (2014) for exposure), (ii) urban heat stress (Debbage and Shepherd, 2015, Oke, 2015, Gunawardena et al., 2017), or (iii) the health impacts of environmental quality (Panagopoulos et al., 2016). Overall, given these proximity interactions, there could even be benefits from spatial fragmentation, contrary to the view often expressed in the landscape ecology literature (Fahrig, 2017, being one recent exception) where low habitat fragmentation is important. The emphasis on air pollution and human wellbeing may push this more general evaluation in a different direction.

In this chapter we propose to apply the Burkhard et al. (2014)'s matrix to the 5 UFES considered and compare the results to an enhanced approach, considering the the spatial configuration of LU in addition to their quantity within each urban area. The final objective is to assess the mismatch that may exist between the demand for and the supply of ES associated to the UF within urban areas, and the impact of the landscape characteristics.

3.2 Methods

Figure 3.1: Steps of the methodology

Land cover	UFES					
	Global climate reg.	Local climate reg.	Air quality reg.	Natural hazard reg.	Water flow reg.	Recreation and Tourism
Forests	4.00	5.00	5.00	3.00	3.00	4.00
Wetlands	4.00	4.00	0.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Water	0.50	1.50	0.00	3.00	3.00	4.50
Herbaceous	1.33	2.00	0.67	1.00	1.00	2.33
Artificial green	1.50	-1.50	-1.00	-2.00	0.00	3.50
Other transport infrastructures	-4.00	-2.00	-3.00	-5.00	-3.00	-1.50
Roads and rail network	-4.00	-2.00	-4.00	-4.00	-4.00	-2.00
Industrial or commercial units	-5.00	-2.00	-5.00	-5.00	-4.00	-1.00
Urban fabric	-3.50	-5.00	-5.00	-4.50	-4.50	-4.00

Correspondence to the LU used in this study (values are averaged per LU): Forests = Broad-leaved + Coniferous + Mixed forests; Wetlands = Moors and heathlands; Water = Water course + Water bodies; Herbaceous = Natural grasslands + Sclerophyllous vegetation + Transitional woodland shrub; Artificial green = Green urban areas + Sport and leisure facilities; Other transport infrastructures = Port areas + Airports; Urban fabric = Continuous + Discontinuous urban fabric

Table 3.1: ES flow - demand budget matrix based on Burkhard et al. (2014)

The method is summarised in Figure 3.1 and the entire process is handled using the R software (R Core Team, 2019, version 3.6.1).

3.2.1 Linking land cover, 5 UFES and landscape metrics

From land cover to UFES

Burkhard et al. (2014) proposed a matrix that relates a list of land cover types to a set of ES in order to assess the ES potential of regions. Qualitative coefficients are used to weight each land cover type quantity in a linear combination, as in an accounting system. Each coefficient in this "budget" matrix results from a flow index minus a demand index per land cover type. Values are then standardised along a -5 to +5 range. Table 3.1 shows an adapted extract from Burkhard et al. (2014)'s matrix that relates the five ES we consider (columns) to land cover types (rows). There is a one-to-one relation between Burkhard et al. (2014)'s categories and our first three ES. Our fourth ES, i.e. rainwater regulation, will be assessed in terms of both the "natural hazard regulation" and the "water flow regulation" categories. Our fifth ES, i.e. mental and physical health, will be proxied by the "recreation and tourism" category. Rows are also adapted to fit the land-use categories of our dataset (i.e. EEA, 2016, Urban Atlas - see caption of Table 3.1 for details). In addition to natural element pertaining to the Urban Forest itself, the table rows include all land uses, since the matrix represents flow budgets (not solely supply), i.e. the resulting sum of both supply (positive values) and demand (negative values).

Towards an UFES matrix with land cover and landscape metrics

In addition to the land cover, we propose to include landscape structure and configuration metrics for UFES appraisal. Table 3.1 is thus to be complemented by a similar matrix where weights are associated with landscape metrics. Identifying such weights and landscape metrics is difficult and must follow from state-of-the-art research where links between ES and land use structures have been identified. As a proof of concept

and from the below review as a guideline, Table 3.2 shows the weight values for the 23 metrics selected in Chapter 2.

Macro climate and air quality regulation - Urban sprawl, defined as a fragmented and over-expanded form of urban expansion, increases both commuting distances and travel dependency on cars (OECD, 2018), implying an increase of emissions from the transport sector (e.g. Schindler and Caruso, 2014). More compact cities reduce total emissions, but bear denser emissions from each transport network segment (Martilli, 2014) and lead to higher rates of exposure to air pollutants for the population (Schindler and Caruso, 2014). Even though road transportation significantly has reduced its emissions through technology over the last three decades in Europe (EEA, 2019a), it still emits large amounts of air pollutants (EEA, 2019a) and greenhouse gases (EEA, 2019b).

Micro climate regulation - UHI (urban heat island) effects increase with the contiguity of impervious land (Debbage and Shepherd, 2015) and its compactness (Martilli, 2014). Among others, Heusinkveld et al. (2014) show that built-up cover types (mainly buildings) contribute to increasing UHI, but that the surrounding vegetation can mitigate it. In that sense, the fragmentation of vegetation by buildings allows for a significant decrease in the UHI effect (Kong et al., 2016). Increasing the density of the tree canopy itself has a significant and positive impact on air surface temperature cooling (Greene and Millward, 2017). The presence of waterbodies also reduces UHI intensity, through evapotranspiration processes during the day (Gunawardena et al., 2017) but can enhance it at night (Heusinkveld et al., 2014). Artificial green spaces, such as parks, tend to increase the UHI effect and the magnitude of heat waves (Ward et al., 2016), unless they have a large area of coverage of trees, shrubs and herbaceous vegetation (Vieira et al., 2018).

Rainwater drainage - From a landscape perspective, such hydrological disturbances can be caused by both urban sprawl and urban compactness policies (Whitford et al., Haase, 2009). Linear patches of vegetation can increase the potential for water runoff regulation and allow flooding control via short-term and long-term detention and storage of water (Mitchell et al., 2015). The integration of natural land within and around impervious land can improve the infiltration rate of rainwater and have a significant impact on the intensity of local extreme events.

Mental and physical health - The level of connectivity within patches may increase the use of green spaces (Mitchell et al., 2015). Wetlands also possess a recreational potential (Turner et al., 2008, Maltby and Acreman, 2011) and so should be considered. A way of capturing the potential impact of urban vegetation on health is its relative proximity and accessibility to human settlements. Yet the mental and physical health benefits resulting from the exposure can be impacted by a large set of drivers related to the socio-demographics of individuals, climate, characteristics of the vegetation, opportunity and ease of use, as well as personal drivers (Lachowycz and Jones, 2013).

3.2.2 UFES score and ranking of cities

A UFES budget coefficient is attributed to each of the metrics, for each of the 5 UFES. Coefficients are listed in Tables 3.1 and 3.2. The coefficients associated with land cover proportions (i) are taken directly from Burkhard et al. (2014). All the others, associated with land cover proportions within buffers (ii) and other landscape metrics (iii), are our own qualitative assessment based on the literature.

The budget index (or score) of a UFES j for an FUA s is denoted by I_{js} . It is computed as the weighted mean of the standardised values z_{is} , using the coefficients β_{ij} that relate a metric $i \in \llbracket 1, I \rrbracket$ to the UFES $j \in \llbracket 1, 5 \rrbracket$.

Metrics	Macro climate regulation	Micro climate regulation	Air quality regulation	Rainwater regulation	Mental and physical health
ForestsPct	4.00	5.00	5.00	3.00	4.00
Forests_area_cv	4.00	5.00	5.00	3.00	4.00
Forests_area_mean	4.00	5.00	5.00	3.00	4.00
Forests_cohesion	4.00	5.00	5.00	3.00	4.00
Forests_contig_mean	4.00	5.00	5.00	3.00	4.00
Forests_division	0.00	0.00	0.00	-3.00	3.00
Forests_edgeD	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.00
WetlandsPct	4.00	4.00	0.00	3.00	4.50
HerbaceousPct	1.33	2.00	0.67	1.00	2.33
ArtificialPct	1.50	-1.50	-1.00	-1.00	3.50
Artificial_cohesion	2.00	-2.00	-2.00	-1.00	3.50
Artificial_contig_mean	2.00	-2.50	-2.00	-1.00	4.00
Forests_UrbanFabric1500	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.00
Artificial_UrbanFabric1000	3.00	-2.00	-1.00	-1.00	5.00
Vegetation_Roads1500	4.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	4.00
Roads_cohesion	-4.00	-2.00	-4.00	-4.00	-2.00
Roads_contig_mean	-4.00	-2.00	-4.00	-4.00	-2.00
Roads_edgeD	-4.00	-2.00	-4.00	-4.00	-2.00
Indus_cohesion	-5.00	-2.00	-5.00	-4.50	-1.00
Indus_contig_mean	-5.00	-2.00	-5.00	-4.50	-1.00
UrbanFabric_cohesion	-3.50	-5.00	-5.00	-4.50	-4.00
UrbanFabric_contig_mnea	-3.50	-5.00	-5.00	-4.50	-4.00
ImperviousPct	-3.50	-5.00	-5.00	-4.50	-4.00

Table 3.2: Coefficients (β_{ij}) of UFES budget for each metric (i) and UFES (j)

$$I_{js} = \frac{1}{I} \sum_{i=1}^I \beta_{ij} \times z_{is} \quad (3.1)$$

where: $I = \text{card}(B_{i\bullet})$

The global budget index is then given by the mean of the five UFES for each FUA, reduced by the standard deviation associated with the UFES index:

$$\begin{aligned} I_s &= \frac{1}{5} \sum_{j=1}^5 I_{js} \\ &= \frac{1}{5} \sum_{j=1}^5 \left[\frac{1}{I} \sum_{i=1}^I \beta_{ij} \times z_{is} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{5 \times I} \sum_{j=1}^5 \sum_{i=1}^I \frac{\beta_{ij} \times z_{is}}{\sigma_{I_j}} \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

We rank all FUAs using this global index I_s . Cities with a higher value have a better UFES potential.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Ranking cities along potential UFES scores - Burkhard's approach

Figure 3.2: Boxplots of index values per cluster (Burkhard's approach)

Note: dashed grey lines correspond to \pm the standard deviation for each UFES index series.

We now consider the UFES budget indices presented in Table 3.1, and such that the UFES Rainwater regulations weights come from the mean between the columns Natural hazard and Water flow regulation. Firstly, we show boxplots (see Figure 3.2) of the five I_{sj} indices for each UFES (micro, macro, air quality, rainwater and health regulation - Equation 3.1) and of the global index I_s being a reduced mean of the previous five (Equation 3.2), along the typology of clusters presented in the previous chapter. Secondly, we rank all urban areas in the dataset along the global index I_s . We explore the sorting of each cluster within this ranking via colour strips (see Figure 3.3).

Regarding the groups, Forest and Anthropogenic Cities exhibit the most distinct behaviours: the first tend to have the highest values for the global index (from 1.270 to 39.469), while the latter tend to have the lowest ones (from -34.598 to 18.041; the same trend is observed for all indices). Herbaceous and Standard European groups cannot be easily contrasted: values are centred above zero with standard deviation respectively equal to 5.306 and 5.192 (again, for the global index). The distribution of index values within the 10 clusters follows a clear trend which allows us to order them from the highest performers to the least, as shown in Figure 3.2. Clusters can be ordered as follows: $F1 > F2 > F3 > F4 > E1 > H1 > H2 > A3 > A2 > A1$.

Among the six indices, health is the one with the smallest standard deviation, while air quality has the highest one. The indices have to be seen as proxies for the budget between the supply and the demand of UFES based on the land use composition. The

higher the index, the better the urban area will be able to cope with urban stresses, extreme events, as well as supporting human wellbeing.

The findings suggest that urban areas part of the most anthropogenic clusters (A1 and A2) should be considered to be the most at risk regarding the UFES studied. This means that the demand for ES is expected to be much higher than what the existing urban forest can provide. It makes these urban areas less capable of resisting most urban stressors such as peaks of air pollution concentration, heat waves, or intense local rain. Their landscapes are also less likely to have the potential to offset greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and to provide accessible natural land to enhance the mental and physical health of the population. The situation seems to be more exacerbated for cluster A1 with the micro climate, air quality and water runoff indices. Concerning urban areas part of clusters F4, E1, H1, H2 and A3, the situation is not as critical, but the UFES indices could be greatly improved. They tend to have less impervious land cover than the average, with predominant vegetation being, in order herbaceous, forest and artificial green. Forest Cities (F1-3) are all likely to perform better, since they combine a smaller demand with a higher potential supply of UFES. Their spatial configuration supports natural ES in an urban context. Yet we note that clusters F2 and F3 are very comparable, and this is due to the fact that their land use covers are rather comparable.

As expected, the above result can be seen when looking at the ranking of FUAs in Figure 3.3. Urban areas are ranked from the one with the highest global index (top left) to the one with the lowest one (bottom right), although urban areas with central values form a large palette of clusters. Clusters F4, E1 and H1 are predominantly in the upper middle, but also clusters H2, A3, with cluster A2 being in the lower middle. Clusters with rather different features may hence end up having comparable UFES potentials, as the overlapping of cluster values suggests in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.4 presents a map with global index values categorised per decile of each FUA. It illustrates the spatial trend associated with the cluster distribution, but not only that. FUAs belonging to eastern Spain, the area including the United Kingdom, Belgium, the Netherlands and north-eastern Germany, northern and eastern Italy and parts of Romania show an index among the 20% lowest values (below -1.43). These areas can be regarded as gathering the most at-risk urban areas with regard to the mismatch between the potential demand and the supply. On the other hand, Norway, Sweden, Finland, eastern Poland, parts of north-western Turkey, the Balkans, parts of Italy, parts of central Europe and the western Iberian peninsula include the FUAs with a global index greater than 12.13 (top 30%).

Figure 3.3: List of FUAs ranked by the global index value

Figure 3.4: Map of global index distribution per decile

3.3.2 Land cover and landscape metrics - proof of concept

We now consider the UFES budget indices presented in Table 3.2. Firstly, we show boxplots (see Figure 3.5) of the 23 $I_{s,j}$ indices for each UFES (micro, macro, air quality, rainwater and health regulation - Equation 3.1) and of the global index I_s being a reduced mean of the previous five (Equation 3.2), along the typology clusters. Secondly, we rank all urban areas in the dataset along the global index I_s . We explore the sorting of each cluster within this ranking via colour strips (see Figure 3.6).

Regarding the groups, once again, Forest and Anthropogenic Cities exhibit the most distinct behaviours: the first tend to have the highest values for the global index (from -0.547 to 5.701), while the latter tend to have the lowest ones (from -2.733 to 1.027); the same trend is observed for all indices. Herbaceous and Standard European groups cannot be easily contrasted: values are centred near zero with standard deviation respectively equal to 0.633 and 0.447 (again, for the global index). The distribution of index values within the 10 clusters follows a clear trend which allows us to order them from the highest performers to the least, as shown in Figure 3.5. Clusters can be ordered as follows: F2 > F1 > F3 > F4 > H1 > H2 > E1 > A3 > A2 > A1.

Among the six indices, we can see that health is the one with the smallest standard deviation (0.641), while air quality has the highest one by far (17.051). The indices have to be seen as proxies for the budget between the supply and the demand of UFES. The

Figure 3.5: Boxplots of index values per cluster (with landscape metrics)

Note: dashed grey lines correspond to \pm the standard deviation for each UFES index series.

higher the index, the better the urban area will be able to cope with urban stresses, extreme events, as well as supporting human wellbeing.

The findings suggest that urban areas part of the most anthropogenic clusters (A1 and A2) should be considered to be the most at risk regarding the UFES studied. This means that the demand for ES is expected to be much higher than what the existing urban forest can provide. It makes these urban areas less capable of resisting most urban stressors such as peaks of air pollution concentration, heat waves, or intense local rain. Their landscapes are also less likely to have the potential to offset greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and to provide accessible natural land to enhance the mental and physical health of the population. The situation seems to be more exacerbated for cluster A1 with the micro climate, air quality and water runoff indices.

Concerning urban areas part of clusters H2, E1 and A3, the situation is not as critical, but the UFES indices could be greatly improved. They tend to have less impervious land cover than the average, with predominant vegetation being, in order herbaceous, forest and artificial green. Yet the spatial configuration may lead to an insufficient supply in the event of intense anthropogenic activities.

Forest Cities (F1-4) and Wetland Cities (H1) are all likely to perform better, since they combine a smaller demand with a higher potential supply of UFES. Their spatial configuration supports natural ES in an urban context. Cluster F2 tends to perform better than cluster F1, despite less forest cover. This might be explained by the lower level of impervious cover along with much better integration of natural and semi-natural land around these impervious lands. It shows that large forest cover alone does not have the capacity to provide the full potential of UFES, while land-sharing urban patterns do. Considering the cluster F4, with the smallest mean forest patch size and forest cover in the group, FUAs do not perform as well. Cluster H1 seems to perform rather well for

indices macro and micro climate regulation and health, but less well for the air quality index.

As expected, the above result can be seen when looking at the ranking of FUAs in Figure 3.6. Urban areas are ranked from the one with the highest global index (top left) to the one with the lowest one (bottom right), although urban areas with central values form a large palette of clusters. Clusters H2, E1 and A3 are predominantly in the upper middle, but also clusters F3 and F4, with cluster A2 being in the lower middle. Clusters with rather different features may hence end up having comparable UFES potentials, as the overlapping of cluster values suggests in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.7 presents a map with global index values categorised per decile of each FUA, with isolines approximating the quintiles. It illustrates the spatial trend associated with the cluster distribution, but not only that. FUAs belonging to central and eastern Spain, the area including the United Kingdom, Belgium, the Netherlands and north-eastern Germany, northern and eastern Italy, parts of Hungary, southern Romania and eastern Turkey show an index among the 30% lowest values (below -0.471). These areas can be regarded as gathering the most at-risk urban areas with regard to the mismatch between the potential demand and the supply. On the other hand, Norway, Sweden, Finland, eastern Poland, parts of north-western Turkey, the Balkans, parts of Italy and the western Iberian peninsula include the FUAs with a global index greater than 0.778 (top 20%).

Figure 3.6: List of FUAs ranked by the global index value

Figure 3.7: Map of global index distribution per decile (with contour lines)

3.4 Discussion

Linking the typology to landscape UFES scores

Taken together, the results from 2 and 3 provide compelling insights into the main urban landscapes existing in the most populated European urban areas and the urban forest ecosystem services budget index which relates to them. From this wide range of European FUAs (689), the HCA uncovered 10 clusters which we gathered into 4 groups according to their spatial characteristics. Their urban form features, computed from both land use and landscape metrics, are related to pressure on and provision of ES associated with the urban forest (UFES). Each cluster presents specific characteristics. The creation of indices associated with the UFES budget potentials of each FUA enhances the understanding of the relationship between the urban form and the UFES profiles.

As expected, Forest Cities best support a positive score of UFES. Yet the urban pattern and spatial integration of natural and anthropogenic land within these Forest Cities lead to different levels of UFES scores among the clusters. Similarly, Anthropogenic Cities reveal substantial differences, due to differences in their urban patterns. Land sharing between the natural and anthropogenic land seems to be a key element, as well as low compactness of anthropogenic land in both groups. Hence, FUAs in clusters F2 and A3 tend to have better scores than in other clusters from their respective groups, when accounting for landscape metrics. The semi-artificial character of parks and leisure facilities is not always properly taken into account in urban forest studies. Our results suggest that they tend to be overrated in academic studies and urban planning - often integrated into the definition of urban green infrastructures (UGI), along with

forests, wetlands and herbaceous vegetation, due to their aesthetic and touristic values -, compared to what they can actually provide (EEA, 2017).

At the European scale, urban areas from clusters A1 and A2 should represent a priority in terms of planning and policies to set up paths towards more nature-integrated areas. Significant efforts therefore have to be made within these clusters to reduce the demand for both regulatory and health-related services. The outcome will be more significant when coupled with measures that increase the supply for UFES, such as afforestation within impervious lands. Indeed, they are more subject to heat, water and air pollution stresses, while their frequencies and intensities are projected to continue increasing significantly in future decades (EEA, 2007, 2010, IPCC, 2015, Guerreiro et al., 2018, EEA, 2020). Anthropogenic Cities from cluster A3 tend to have more compact built-up land but with low-density transport networks, better preservation of forest land and less artificial green cover. It contributes positively to the score for regulatory UFES, as well as to the health potential. It appears that land sharing leads to better outcomes than land sparing. To preserve the high levels of performance in Forest Cities and Wetland Cities, it is important to preserve and maintain the natural land as well as its proximity to more anthropogenic land. The small amount of artificial green (mainly parks) should not be considered as a problem as long as forest land and wetlands both remain accessible to the population.

The most populated urban areas tend to privilege artificial vegetation (such as parks) over natural vegetation, despite their lower ecosystemic values (Burkhard et al., 2014). This leads to rather strong consequences for their regulatory UFES scores, while their low proximity of vegetated land to impervious land leads to only average health index scores. Central Europe is projected to endure heat waves with higher maximum temperatures, up to more 14 °C more with the high-impact scenario (Guerreiro et al., 2018). Northern Italy, the UK, the Netherlands, Belgium, Denmark and parts of Germany are subject to more difficulties due to the mismatch between the predictions and the budget index (Guerreiro et al., 2018). Regarding water discharge in the UK, Belgium, the Netherlands and the Nordic and Baltic countries, FUAs from the Forest Cities group present a positive score (Nordic and some Baltic urban areas), while we expect the remaining ones, being mainly Anthropogenic Cities, to be more at risk (Guerreiro et al., 2018).

3.5 Conclusions

This article investigates the impact of the spatial integration and characteristics of natural, semi-natural and anthropogenic land on five ecosystem services associated with the urban forest in Europe. Again, the association of landscape metrics in addition to the usual land cover metrics strengthens our understanding of threats and potentials, as it appears that aggregation, fragmentation and the relative position of land cover impact both the creation of the clusters and the resulting indices.

The second major finding was that in the context of regulatory services, a higher level of spatial integration (in the sense of fragmentation) of the urban forest has a positive impact on human health, wellbeing and the environment. Hence, not only accounting for the quantity of the different LU, but also for their spatial configuration allow to better assess the UFES considered in this study.

An important limitation comes from the fact that we only use landscape and land cover metrics as proxies for the demand for and supply of UFES. This work could be improved with spatially explicit information on: (1) the intensity of emissions from anthropogenic land, and uptake from natural and semi-natural land with regard to the

micro climate, macro climate and air quality regulation services; (2) risks of flooding and water retention potentials regarding rainwater regulation; (3) effective accessibility and characteristics of natural and semi-natural land for physical and mental health aspects. Another important limitation comes from the coefficients used in the creation of the indices. The ones associated with the landscape metrics have been created based on a review of the literature review by the authors, and values were assigned in order to be in line with the coefficients proposed by Burkhard et al. (2014).

Regarding the valuation of UFES, the analysis could be continued in two ways. A sensitivity analysis would allow a reweighting of coefficients used in the creation of the indices in respect of the level of uncertainty. The creation of a local index would allow identification of the areas within the FUAs with the highest deficits of UFES. Despite the above limitations, this article provides valuable insights into the existing landscapes of urban areas across the European continent (38 countries included).

Urban Carbon Balance (UCB)

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4. UCB Model - High resolution spatio-temporal model of CO₂ emissions and sequestration in cities

Accessibility

The script of the UCB model and the UCB database from this article are available on the platform Zenodo (Boura and Caruso, 2021) and on GitHub (<https://github.com/mboura/UCB>).

4.1 Background and summary

The ongoing climate change is a global phenomenon induced by human activities (IPCC, 2021). It results from the accumulation of greenhouse gases (GHG) in the atmosphere, mainly since the industrial revolution (IPCC, 2014, 2019, 2021). The major GHG, highlighted by the Kyoto Protocol (United Nations, 1998), are methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), fluorinated gases (F-gases) and carbon dioxide (CO₂). The latter is the most important GHG in the atmosphere in terms of proportion (IPCC, 2014). Over the period 1850-2019, global emissions increased by $2,381 \pm 238$ Gt CO₂, according to Friedlingstein et al. (2020). Before the pre-industrial era, the global average concentration of CO₂ was about 280 ppm (Lindsay, 2020). Since then, it has continued to increase, reaching a global average of 340 ppm in 1980 and 415.88 ppm in February 2021 (NOAA, 2021), despite the previous 25 Conferences of the Parties (COP). Thus, the concentration of CO₂ has increased by 48% between 1750 and February 2021.

Yet global averages do not accurately capture notable local spatial and temporal variations as shown by NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center (2014). The levels of CO₂ concentration vary in different locations and across the seasons according to the main meteorological drivers, the different emitting anthropogenic activities and the repartition of vegetated lands (Friedlingstein et al., 2020). Global aggregates are averaging ignoring both space and time variations. More details are provided in Box 4.1. Previous large-scale studies focussed on regional to global scales (Hutyra et al., 2014) such that spatial and temporal resolutions were rarely meaningful to local or urban areas (Super, 2018). According to Seto et al. (2012), the ongoing urbanisation has a significant direct impact on the carbon pools. Therefore, the urban carbon cycle must

be properly assessed as it impacts regional and global carbon cycles (Hutyra et al., 2014).

Box 4.1 Global flows of CO₂ across time and space

NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center (2014) provides a video showing the reconstructed CO₂ fluxes around the globe for the year 2006. It shows a strong temporal variation day by day and season by season. Late autumn to spring for the northern hemisphere is the period when the concentration is highest and this hemisphere gathers the most emitting countries. It also shows strong spatial variations. There is a strong differentiation between the two hemispheres as the main winds only allow for little exchange. Moreover, the main emission zones seem to correspond to the most densely populated areas. Finally, the dispersion of CO₂ molecules over time is not homogeneous across the globe but is determined by the main wind fields and other meteorological features. For example, the North Pole and its surroundings end up with a very high level of concentration due to the Northern Hemisphere emissions. Figure 4.1 shows the concentration for 1 January, April, July and October 2006.

Figure 4.1: CO₂ concentration (ppm) in 2006 (after NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center, 2014)

Anthropogenic CO₂ emissions are mainly released into the atmosphere through the combustion of fossil fuels to produce energy (IPCC, 2014). Since the 1990s, the global demand for energy and energy-related CO₂ emissions have increased steadily, whereas the decrease observed in 2020, due to the pandemic, was only temporary (IEA, 2021). With the process of urbanisation, human settlements are agglomerating but still represent a tiny proportion of the emerged land (Liu et al., 2014). Yet the IEA (2008) projects that cities will be responsible for about three quarters of global CO₂ emissions by 2030. It has therefore become clear that cities must drastically reduce their emissions. More and more cities and metropolitan areas are now taking action around the world (see C40 Cities, Covenant of Mayors or Under2 Coalition).

In addition to reducing emissions, urban planning policies to optimize CO₂ sequestra-

tion arising from emitting land could have significant benefits. Via the natural process of photosynthesis, vegetated land can sequester part of the anthropogenic CO₂ emissions and have a direct impact on the carbon balance of urban areas. It is imperative to better understand and assess the role and the dynamic of the urban carbon cycle within the regional and global cycles (Hutyra et al., 2014). Improved insights will help to understand and calibrate future scenarios and mitigation plans. Furthermore, reducing the urban carbon balance could ripple and impact the regional and global carbon balances. To test these hypotheses, it is first necessary to take into account: urban natural flows, urban anthropogenic flows and their interaction (Churkina, 2008).

We propose a method to obtain disaggregated estimates for CO₂ emissions, sequestration and balance. The method is built on three types of data: land use, sectoral emissions and sequestration parameters. In addition, temporal decomposition factors are applied. Thus far, the current main alternatives are not appropriate for applications on multiple large urban areas for various reasons.

Global and regional transport models (both chemistry and tracer models) seem to be a very suitable solution, but they usually fail to properly account for the urban carbon cycle due to their spatial resolution (Super, 2018, Li et al., 2020). Furthermore, these models are computationally very expensive (Super, 2018) and fail in "an urban-like boundary layer with strong and heterogeneously distributed surface emissions" (Li et al., 2020). *Eddy-covariance* (EC) measurements allow the collection of very high resolution and continuous flow data (often coupled with meteorological data), but are used for a rather limited area, up to a few hundred meters around the EC tower (Balducchi et al., 2001, Kotthaus and Grimmond, 2012, Pastorello et al., 2020). Moreover, such infrastructures are not available everywhere, the global network FLUXNET accounts for 212 EC towers, mainly located in northern America, western Europe and Australia (Pastorello et al., 2020). The small footprint of EC towers make them unsuitable for analysing the flows of entire cities, large urban areas and beyond. *Urban carbon metabolism* approaches take into account both carbon stocks and flows, and they allow comparison of different scenarios of urban planning and their impact on the aggregated urban carbon balance. However, they require a large variety of data which are not always available (Kellest et al., 2013).

The High Resolution Urban Carbon Balance (UCB) Model presented in this article allows to downscale CO₂ emissions and sequestration. From these outputs, the aggregated and disaggregated urban carbon balance are then assessed using different metrics. We developed estimates of anthropogenic carbon emissions and natural carbon sequestration at a spatial resolution of 1 ha and with annual, monthly and daily temporal resolutions. The carbon balance is then expressed in two ways: in absolute terms (*i.e.* total amount sequestered over a given period) and in relative terms (*i.e.* percentage of emissions sequestered over a given period). Therefore, the uniqueness of this work comes from multiple aspects: (1) the sectoral CO₂ emissions are downscaled spatially using a high resolution urban land use database for hundreds of urban areas, (2) the seasonality of CO₂ emissions is accounted across country-, sector-, and year-specific time profiles, (3) the urban carbon sequestration capacity is estimated at a high spatial resolution for hundreds of urban areas, (4) the seasonality of the sequestration process is accounted with location-specific monthly factors, (5) the carbon balance estimates allow for comparison among a non-spatial model and spatially explicit model.

The method can be easily replicated to different locations or time periods, and it can be launched on multiple cities. The European UCB dataset is currently available

for 802 European urban areas (Boura and Caruso, 2021) along with the script to run the model using the software R (R Core Team, 2019). The empirical analysis of the database is available in Chapter 5. Here, we present the UCB model on four cities which represent different degrees of integration of land use (LU).

In the next section, we introduce the input data used to produce our database. Afterwards, we describe the model and present some results focusing on four urban areas with different urban structures and carbon profiles. We conclude with a discussion of the model and the approaches developed.

4.2 Data

Different input data are needed to apply the methodology presented here. The minimum requirements are: (1) a LU database to differentiate between anthropogenic and natural land of interest within the study area; (2) a CO₂ emissions database for a given time period, on a spatial grid and preferably disaggregated per sector of emission; (3) vegetation characteristics (canopy cover, tree type/species, aboveground biomass) should be used to obtain more accurate estimates. (4) Ecological zones (EZ) and their associated climatic domains are provided by the Global Ecological Zones database (FAO, 2012) and are used to calibrate the model. Furthermore, (5) temporal decomposition factors are used for the emissions and sequestration estimates. This subsection and Table 4.1 present the datasets used.

4.2.1 Urban limits and land use

The Urban Atlas 2012 (UA2012 - EEA, 2016) is a vectorial land use database. It uses the urban definition of the OECD (2013), called: Functional Urban Area (FUA) to delineate urban boundaries. The definition is based on population density and daily commuting thresholds (see Dijkstra and Poelman, 2012, OECD, 2013, Dijkstra et al., 2019). This functional definition is suitable for the study of anthropogenic flows as they are associated with human settlements and activities. The UA2012 provides 29 LU categories for hundreds of European FUAs with more than 50,000 inhabitants in 2012.

The anthropogenic LU categories are here aggregated into five new LU categories to match the emission activity sectors presented in Table 4.2. The residential LU corresponds to the urban fabric from continuous, dense to very sparse. The non-residential LU corresponds to industrial, commercial, public, military, private and transport units. The roads LU refers to fast transit roads and other roads. The non-roads LU refers to railways, ports, airports and associated lands. The agricultural LU includes arable land, permanent crops, pasture, complex and mixed cultivation, and orchards.

802 European FUAs from 38 countries are here considered within the spatial extent 23°W to 44°E and 34°N to 71°N. They are presented in Figure B.1 (see Appendix). CO₂ emissions, sequestration and budgets are calculated for each of these FUA at a spatial resolution of 1 ha for the year 2012 at annual, monthly and daily temporal resolutions. Figure 4.2 shows the LU data for 4 specific urban areas which will be used to illustrate the model in this article.

4.2.2 CO₂ emissions and matching with land use

Data on anthropogenic CO₂ emissions are from the database *TNO-CAMS European CO₂ emissions 2000-2014 v1* provided by Kuenen et al. (2017). The NetCDF data provide

Name	Description	Time period	Spatial res.	Spatial coverage	Source
UA2012	Urban Atlas: vector data with land use data and functional urban areas boundaries (polygons).	2012		Europe: 22.75°W - 43.85°E; 27.91° - 70.31°N	EEA (2016)
DLT2012	Dominant Leaf Type: raster data with broadleaves or coniferous as main leaf type within a cell.	2012	20 × 20 m	Europe: 31.26°W - 44.82°E; 27.63° - 71.18°N	EEA (2018a)
TCD2012	Tree Cover Density: raster data with tree coverage in percentage. Values are ranging between 0 and 100.	2012	20 × 20 m	Europe: 31.26°W - 44.82°E; 27.63° - 71.18°N	EEA (2018b)
Biomass	Aboveground biomass storage raster data. Values are in t per cell.	2010	1 × 1 km	Europe: 31.26°W - 44.82°E; 27.63° - 71.18°N	Barredo et al. (2012)
GEZ	Global Ecological Zones shapefiles (polygons).	2010		Global	FAO (2012)
GPP	Monthly Gross Primary Productivity (GPP) of terrestrial ecosystems. Monthly raster data with values in g C per m ² .	2000-2015	1/20° × 1/20°	Global	Zhao et al. (2005)
IPCC	Parameters and equations from the IPCC guidelines expressed for annual estimations.		1 ha	Global	IPCC (2006a,b,c,d, 2015)
TNO CAMS	Anthropogenic CO ₂ emissions data in NetCDF format (areal and point data). Values are in kg CO ₂ per cell per year.	2000-2014	1/8° × 1/16°	Europe: 30°W - 60°E; 30° - 72°N	Kuenen et al. (2017)
Emissions profiles	GHG sectoral temporal profiles to convert annual emissions to monthly, daily and hourly time resolutions (xlsx and csv files).	2000-2017	country	Global	Crippa et al. (2019)

Table 4.1: Overview of the input data

Figure 4.2: LU distribution

FUA codes: Sarajevo (BA001L1), Newcastle (UK013L2), Faro (PT009L1) and Tilburg (NL006L2). "Other UGI" stands for other urban green infrastructures. This category gathers parks, sport and leisure facilities.

a European grid of CO₂ emission at a spatial resolution of $1/8^\circ \times 1/16^\circ$ ($\approx 7 \times 7$ km) for each year based on available data and estimates. This chapter only considers data from the year 2012 to illustrate the model. The data can be in the form of area sources or point sources. Emissions are given by activity sector according to the SNAP (Selected Nomenclature for Air Pollution) presented in Table 4.2. SNAP3 and SNAP4 (industrial combustion and processes) are aggregated into SNAP34. SNAP7 (road transport) is divided into 3 categories (71, 72 and 73) for gasoline, diesel and LPG¹. SNAP9 (waste) is excluded due to too much uncertainty in the available data.

The uncertainty associated with this database arises from various aspects. For several sectors, the population density was used as a proxy, which is known to lead to overestimations in some sectors for very dense areas (Denier van der Gon et al., 2017, Karvosenoja et al., 2018). Regarding point source data, the actual location of major facilities may be inaccurate by a few hundred meter.

¹LPG: Liquefied petroleum gas

SNAP	Description	LU category
1	Energy industries	Non Residential
2	Small combustion	Residential
34	Industry (combustion + processes)	Non Residential
5	Exploration and production of fossil fuels	NonResidential
6	Product use	Non Residential
7(1-3)	Road transport (gasoline, diesel, LPG)	Road
8	Non-road transport	Non Road
10	Agriculture	Agriculture

Note: The UA2012 codes associated with the LU categories: agricultural (21000, 22000, 23000, 24000, 25000), residential (11100, 11210, 11220, 11230, 11240, 11300), non residential (12100), roads (12210, 12220), non roads (12230, 12300, 12400)

Table 4.2: Emission sector considered and relative LU category from the UA2012

4.2.3 Sequestration, land use and parameters

Vegetation attributes are used to allocate parametric values to the different natural lands considered in the CO₂ sequestration process. The Global Ecological Zone (EZ) and climatic domains are key proxies in terms of terrestrial carbon cycle (IPCC, 2006a,b,c,d, 2015). FAO (2012) provides the EZ used as a discriminant for the parametric values provided by the IPCC. The climatic domains are considered as the first term of the EZ: boreal, temperate and subtropical (for the study area presented in Figure B.1).

The Dominant Leaf Type database (DLT2012 - EEA, 2018a) is used to differentiate between the different vegetation types where a tree cover is present: broadleaved or coniferous (see Figure B.11 in Appendix). The Tree Cover Density database (TCD2012 - EEA, 2018b) is used to convert the maximum potential aboveground biomass growth for the EZ, if the land had 100% tree cover, into the actual tree cover in each cell (see Figure B.12 in Appendix). Both are part of the High Resolution Layer (HRL) Forests 2012 database provided by GMES/Copernicus (<http://land.copernicus.eu/>). Yet it is important to note that the vegetation considered in this database is *trees*, regardless of the LU to which it belongs. Therefore, it also accounts for the vegetation outside of forests (for instance, the presence of trees in a residential garden, a public park or a commercial area). For simplicity, we consider that all land with tree cover will be associated with forest land vegetation, with the forest sequestration potential derived from the guidelines provided by the IPCC (2006a,b,c,d, 2015). Wetlands cover is calculated directly from the vector data as the share of LU in each cell during a process of rasterisation. Herbaceous land carbon balance is highly impacted by the type of land use management (Townsend-Small and Czimczik, 2010), which can lead to a negative, neutral or positive C budget. According to Chang et al. (2015), European herbaceous land were estimated to sequester net sink of 15 ± 7 g C per m² per year on average over the period 1961-2010. Nevertheless, due to the lack of consensus in the literature and the lack of data on management practices for the studied areas, we decided to consider all herbaceous land (or grassland) as neutral.

Barredo et al. (2012) estimated the aboveground and belowground biomass of European forests at a spatial resolution of 1 km² for the year 2010. After following the IPCC guidelines for their estimations, the values were adjusted to match the country-level Global Forest Resource Assessment (FAO, 2010). According to Avitabile and Camia (2018), their approach is the least biased compared to the harmonized European Forest Data Centre (EFDAC) biomass dataset (used as reference data in their comparative

study). The biomass dataset of Barredo et al. (2012) has the smallest relative root-mean-square errors of the four databases compared to the harmonized EFDAC biomass dataset. In this model, we use the aboveground biomass (AGB) raster data. However, we note that it tends to underestimate the actual biomass (Avitabile and Camia, 2018), which may lead to an underestimation of sequestration potentials.

4.2.4 Temporal decomposition

Crippa et al. (2019, 2020) propose a set of temporal shares to decompose annual GHG inventories towards smaller temporal resolutions: month, week day and hour. Available globally, the factors are location, time and sector specific. They consider 27 EDGAR sectors of activity which are then divided into subsectors. We used EMEP and CORINAIR (1999), and EMEP and EEA (2019) publications to relate the EDGAR sectors to the SNAP categories, using the IPCC 1996 source categories provided in Crippa et al. (2019). The authors provide a quality score for the temporal profile of the different EDGAR sectors (Crippa et al., 2020). Among the sectors considered in our model, here are those for which the level of uncertainty is likely to be the highest according to Crippa et al. (2020). Agricultural burning waste, enteric fermentation and manure management have the lowest score and all belong to the agricultural sector (SNAP10). Fuel production/transmission (SNAP5), and production and use of other products (SNAP6) have the second lowest score (out of four).

The monthly Gross Primary Productivity (GPP) of terrestrial ecosystems for the year 2012 is used (MODIS GPP product or MOD17 - Zhao et al., 2005). The GPP corresponds to the amount of carbon sequestered from the photosynthesis process and can hence reflect the evolution of the growing season. The data is currently available globally for the period 2000-2015 at a spatial resolution of $1/20^\circ \times 1/20^\circ$ as a total over each month in g C per m^2 . It uses meteorological data, land cover and a combination of Leaf Area Index (LAI) and Fraction of Photosynthetically Active Radiation (FPAR) as input data to estimate the total monthly GPP (Zhao et al., 2005).

4.3 Model

4.3.1 Downscaling CO₂ emissions

The TNO CAMS dataset allows to consider emissions from road transportation (SNAP71, 72, 73), non-road transportation (SNAP8), residential built-up (SNAP2), non-residential built-up (or commercial and industrial units - SNAP1, 34, 5, 6) and agricultural activities (SNAP10). Most of the data are at the cell level (areal source data), but a non negligible part are point source data (100% of SNAP1 and part of SNAP34, 5 and 8). For the year 2012, the TNO CAMS database is cropped to intersect the FUA boundaries for which emissions data are available. Firstly, the areal data are transformed into rasters, summed per LU category, while the point data are allocated to the corresponding LU category and corresponding raster cell. The amount of CO₂ emitted within a cell is denoted $E_c^{y,LU}$ for cell c , year y and land use LU . Secondly, for the temporal decomposition, emission rasters are created at the SNAP level to match the EDGAR sectors. The CO₂ emitted is then denoted $E_c^{y,s}$ for SNAP s . The rasterisation is performed at a spatial resolution of 1 ha (100×100 m) in both cases and the ETRS89 Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area is used as the coordinate reference system.

$$E_c^{y,LU} = [(Cover_c^{y,LU} \times E_c^{y,LU,areal}) + E_c^{y,LU,point}] \times conv \quad (4.1)$$

$$E_c^{y,s} = [(Cover_c^{y,s} \times E_c^{y,s,areal}) + E_c^{y,s,point}] \times conv \quad (4.2)$$

$$E_c^y = \sum_{LU} E_c^{y,LU} = \sum_s E_c^{y,s} \quad (4.3)$$

$$E^y = \sum_c \sum_{LU} E_c^{y,LU} = \sum_c \sum_s E_c^{y,s} \quad (4.4)$$

From Equations 4.1 and 4.2: $E_c^{y,LU,areal}$ (respectively $E_c^{y,s,areal}$) corresponds to the emissions from areal data and the land use category LU (SNAP category s), which intersects the cell c , and $E_c^{y,LU,point}$ (respectively $E_c^{y,s,point}$) corresponds to the emissions from point data and the land use category LU (SNAP category s), which intersects the cell c . $Cover_c^{y,LU}$ (respectively $Cover_c^{y,s}$) corresponds to the LU cover within cell c . The last part, $conv$, is used to convert the amount of CO₂ emitted from kg per cell of $1/8^\circ \times 1/16^\circ$ per year, to ton per ha per year with $conv = 10000 \div (1000 \times area) = 10 \div area$. The Equation 4.3 provides the total emissions within a cell per year and the Equation 4.4 provides the total emissions for a FUA within a year.

4.3.2 Estimating CO₂ sequestration

CO₂ sequestration is defined as the difference between the amount of CO₂ uptaken by vegetation during the photosynthesis process and the amount released during the respiration process, over a given time period. It is assumed here that anthropogenic CO₂ emissions are uptaken and sequestered in the urban forest, as long as they remain within the urban system, considering forests, parks, private gardens, street trees and wetlands. The estimation of the amount of CO₂ sequestered is carried out following the *Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories* from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2006a,b,c,d, 2015). It proposes several ways to estimate the carbon storage and sequestration in natural lands, depending on the data available. The UCB model uses the *Tier 1* estimates for annual sequestration per hectare.

In order to estimate the CO₂ sequestration per cell, we propose the Equation 4.5 below, based on Equations 2.9 and 2.10 (Tier 1) from IPCC (2006a). It gives the yearly sequestration of CO₂ due to biomass growth in a specific land use category in ton CO₂ per ha per year. It corresponds to the gain part of the gain-loss method (IPCC, 2006a). The loss part is a consequence of land management and natural hazards, and it is here not accounted as it may introduce some bias. In terms of land management, the quantity of wood harvested and fuelwood removals are not known at the urban scale. National estimates may not reflect the urban reality. Similarly, natural disturbances impacting the carbon biomass such as fire, storms, and insect and diseases are also hardly quantifiable at the urban scale without local data.

$$S_c^{y,LU} = \frac{44.009}{12.011} \times [Cover_c^{y,LU} \times AGB_Growth_c \times (1 + R_c^{LU}) \times CF_c^{y,LU}] \quad (4.5)$$

LU is the land use category with sequestration potential, we consider (1) forest land and vegetation with tree cover, (2) wetlands. The total biomass growth is defined as $AGB_Growth_c \times (1 + R_c) = AGB_Growth_c + BGB_Growth_c$. AGB_Growth_c is the mean annual aboveground biomass growth (t dry matter / ha / year). R_c^{LU} is the root:shoot ratio to obtain the belowground biomass growth (BGB_Growth_c). $Cover_c^{y,LU}$ is the LU cover within cell c . CF_c is the carbon fraction (t C / t dry matter). c is the cell of spatial resolution 1 ha.

Climatic domain	Ecological zone	AGB growth	
Trees, Wet.	Subtropical	Subtropical humid forest	5.0
		Subtropical dry forest	2.4
		Subtropical steppe	1.0
		Subtropical mountain systems	1.0
	Temperate	Temperate oceanic forest	4.4
		Temperate continental forest	4.0
		Temperate mountain systems	3.0
		Temperate steppe	4.0 ¹
	Boreal	Boreal coniferous forest	1.0
		Boreal tundra woodland	0.4
Boreal mountain systems		1.0	
Herb.	All		0

¹ No data for temperate steppe EZ, we use the value for temperate continental forest.

Source: IPCC (2006b)

Table 4.3: Tier 1 estimated aboveground biomass growth (AGBg), in t per ha per year

Finally, the ratio of weights 44.009 / 12.011 allows the amount of C to be converted into CO₂.

$$S_c^y = \sum_{LU} S_c^{y,LU} \quad (4.6)$$

$$S^y = \sum_c \sum_{LU} S_c^{y,LU} \quad (4.7)$$

Equation 4.6 provides the estimated CO₂ sequestration within a cell per year and Equation 4.7 provides the estimated total sequestration of CO₂ for a FUA within a year.

Estimates of the parameters (AGB_Growth_c , R_c^{LU} and $CF_c^{y,LU}$) depend on the ecological zone from which the LU belongs to. The following paragraphs provide more detailed information on how they are determined.

Biomass growth

The total biomass growth is given by the sum of aboveground biomass growth (AGB growth) and of the belowground biomass growth (BGB growth). As shown in Table 4.3, AGB growth is function of the Ecological Zone (FAO, 2012). It is then multiplied by the land use cover of the corresponding LU (trees, wetlands). The tree cover density is taken directly from the TCD2012 (EEA, 2018b) while the wetlands cover is calculated from the UA2012 (EEA, 2016) as a proportion of the LU within each cell. The BGB growth is here expressed as a ratio, R , of the AGB growth. R (or the root:shoot ratio) is given by the ratio between BGB growth and AGB growth. R is function of the climate domain (which we derive from the EZ) or the EZ itself, the vegetation type, provided by DLT2012 (EEA, 2018a) - for temperate climate only - and the AGB range (see Table 4.4). The AGB value is taken from Barredo et al. (2012): AGB stocks in 2010 in Europe at a spatial resolution of 1 km.

LU	Climatic domain	Ecological zone	Vegetation type	AGB (t/ha)	R
Trees	Subtropical	Subtropical humid forest		< 125	0.20
		Subtropical humid forest		> 125	0.24
		Subtropical dry forest		< 20	0.56
		Subtropical dry forest		> 20	0.28
		Subtropical steppe			0.32
		Subtropical mountain systems			0.28 ¹
	Temperate	Coniferous		< 50	0.40
		Coniferous		50-150	0.29
		Coniferous		> 150	0.20
		Broadleaf		< 75	0.46
		Broadleaf		75-150	0.23
		Broadleaf		> 150	0.24
	Boreal	(mainly coniferous)		< 75	0.39
(mainly coniferous)			> 75	0.24	
Wet. ³	Subtropical				3.65
	Temperate				2.11
	Boreal				2.11 ²

¹ No value were available, so we used the median value for subtropical climatic domain.

² No value were available, so we apply the temperate value.

³ Since the study focuses on the terrestrial urban carbon cycle, only tidal marsh wetlands values are considered, not seagrass meadows.

Sources: IPCC (2006b), FAO (2012), IPCC (2015)

Table 4.4: Tier 1 estimated root:shoot ratios (R)

Carbon fraction

The carbon fraction (CF) within a cell c is a function of the climate domain and the vegetation type of the cell. For each cell with trees of resolution 20×20 m, we have the dominant leaf type (DLT) and the climatic domain to which it belongs. The values associated with European climate domains are reported in Table 4.5.

4.3.3 Applying temporal profiles

Emission data

In order to apply temporal profiles to the annual CO_2 emissions data, the procedure presented by Crippa et al. (2020) has been applied, using their data published in Crippa et al. (2019). After linking the EDGAR sectors and subsectors of activities to the SNAP as

LU	Climatic domain	Vegetation type	CF
Trees	Temperate and Boreal	Broadleaf	0.48
	Temperate and Boreal	Coniferous	0.51
	Subtropical	All	0.47
Wetlands	Temperate and Boreal	Nutrient-rich	0.40
	Temperate and Boreal	Nutrient-poor	0.45
	Subtropical	Tropical hummus	0.34 ¹

¹ Value for the Tropical climate domain.

Sources: IPCC (2006b,d, 2015)

Table 4.5: Tier 1 estimated carbon fraction (CF)

presented in Table 4.6, the average temporal decomposition factors were calculated for each SNAP sector as a simple mean (considering that all sectors or subsectors have the same weight).

Code	EDGAR sector	SNAP	SNAP description
AGS	Agricultural soils	10	Agriculture
AWB	Agricultural waste burning	10	Agriculture
CHE	Production of chemicals	34	Industry
ENE	Energy industry	1	Energy industries
ENF	Enteric fermentation	10	Agriculture
FFF	Fossil fuel fires	5	Fossil fuel production and distribution
FOO	Production of foods	34	Industry
IND	Combustion in manufacturing industry	34	Industry
IRO	Production of iron and steel	34	Industry
MNM	Manure management	10	Agriculture
NEU	Non energy use of fuels	6	Solvent and other product use
NFE	Production of non-ferrous metals	34	Industry
NMM	Production of non-metallic minerals	34	Industry
PAP	Production of pulp and paper	34	Industry
PRO	Fuel production/transmission	5	Fossil fuel production and distribution
PRU	Production and use of other products	6	Solvent and other product use
RCO	Residential	2	Non-industrial combustriion
REF	Oil refineries	1	Energy industries
SOL	Application of solvents	6	Solvent and other product use
TNR	Non-road transport	8	Non-road transport
TRO	Road transport	7	Road transport

Table 4.6: EDGAR sectors to SNAP categories

Using the raster files at a spatial resolution of 1 ha for each FUA and each SNAP category (obtained from $E_c^{y,s}$, Equation 4.2), the monthly decomposition of annual emissions is obtained following the Equation 4.8. $E_c^{y,m,s}$ is the amount of CO₂ emitted in cell c , for year y , month m (January to December) and SNAP category s . The equation uses: $E_c^{y,s}$, the annual emissions from SNAP category s , in cell c , and the monthly factor $mFactor$ which is specific to the year, month, SNAP category and country (iso). Similarly, the weekday decomposition is obtained from the monthly decomposition as presented in Equation 4.9. $E_c^{y,m,d,s}$ is the amount of CO₂ emitted in cell c , for year y , month m , weekday d (Monday to Sunday) and SNAP category s . The equation uses the monthly emissions $E_c^{y,m,s}$, n the number of days in the month (year specific) and the weekday factor $wFactor$ which is year, month, weekday, SNAP category and country specific.

The emissions data from all SNAP are then summed in order to obtain the total monthly ($E_c^{y,m} = \sum_s E_c^{y,m,s}$) and daily ($E_c^{y,m,d} = \sum_s E_c^{y,m,d,s}$) emissions within a 1 ha cell, and taking into account the temporal variations of the different sectors of activity, in space (country-specific factors) and in time.

$$E_c^{y,m,s} = E_c^{y,s} \times mFactor^{y,m,s,iso} \quad (4.8)$$

$$E_c^{y,m,d,s} = E_c^{y,m,s} \times \frac{7}{n^{y,m}} \times wFactor^{y,m,d,s,iso} \quad (4.9)$$

Sequestration data

In order to apply temporal profiles to the annual CO₂ sequestration data, a monthly decomposition is performed using the monthly GPP published by Zhao et al. (2005).

The Equation 4.10 is used to extract the monthly factors of sequestration to apply to the annual sequestration estimates for each cell. These are then multiplied with the annual data to obtain the monthly sequestration estimates, and converted to CO₂ (see Equation 4.11). The daily values are obtained as a simple mean, relative to the number of days in each month (see Equation 4.12).

$$gppFactor_c^{y,m} = \frac{GPP_c^{y,m}}{\sum_m GPP_c^{y,m}} \quad (4.10)$$

$$S_c^{y,m} = S_c^y \times gppFactor_c^{y,m} \quad (4.11)$$

$$S_c^{y,m,d} = \frac{S_c^{y,m,s}}{n^{y,m}} \quad (4.12)$$

4.3.4 Absolute and relative CO₂ balance

Key metrics

A **CO₂ absolute balance**: $E - S$, is the difference between CO₂ emissions and CO₂ sequestration within a delimited area, over a given time period. Here, it is expressed in t of CO₂ per day, for each urban area. A negative balance means that the urban area sequesters more than it emits, and can hence be considered as a carbon sink. A positive value means that the urban area is a carbon source.

A **CO₂ relative balance**: $E / S \times 100$, corresponds to the share of CO₂ emissions which can be sequestered by the vegetation, within a delimited area, over a given time period. Here, it is expressed in percentages per day, for each urban area. A capture smaller than 100% means that the sequestration capacity of the area is smaller than its anthropogenic emissions.

A carbon metabolism approach

This approach aggregates the values across the spatial area. Thus, the CO₂ balance corresponds to the difference between the total emissions and sequestration capacity: $B^{period} = E^{period} - S^{period}$, with *period* being the year, month or weekday. Similarly, the CO₂ relative balance (or relative sequestration capacity) corresponds to the percentage of anthropogenic CO₂ the urban forest can sequester within the same spatial area: $B_R^{period} = (E^{period} / S^{period}) \times 100$. The term *sequestration capacity* reflects a key hypothesis of this approach. By aggregating all the values, without accounting for spatial dispersion, we assume that all what has been emitted within the study area can be captured by the vegetation belonging to the same system, up to its maximum capacity. In addition, it allows accounting for the sequestration of CO₂ molecules emitted outside the spatial area which could be sequestered within the system. Yet it does not consider that CO₂ molecules emitted within the study area could be sequestered outside of it. A relative CO₂ sequestration capacity over 100% means that the existing urban forest has the capacity to sequester more than what the urban area actually emits.

4.4 Examples

In this section, results are displayed focusing on four urban areas with different urban structures as clustered in (Boura and Caruso, 2020, see also Chapter 3). They reflect a typology associated to ecosystem services (ES) that is associated with the urban vegetation for hundreds European urban areas which concluded in the creation of four urban area types. Sarajevo (Bosnia and Herzegovina) belongs to the group "Forest Cities", Faro (Portugal) belongs to "Herbaceous Cities", Newcastle (United Kingdom)

belongs to "Standard European Cities" and Tilburg (The Netherlands) belongs to "Anthropogenic Cities". They present different landscape patterns in terms of LU cover, and spatial configuration. Nevertheless, the urban areas have been selected such that their levels of CO₂ emissions remain relatively comparable.

Presentation of the four FUAs

Following on Figure 4.2, Table 4.7 provides their LU covers in percentages. Sarajevo is a large urban area with about 65% of forest lands and more than 71% of natural land (vegetation and water), for a total area of 2,637 km². It has very few agricultural land compared to the other FUAs (less than 5%). Newcastle is a large urban area of 5,445 km², with a predominance of agricultural land (54.14%). Its natural lands (except other UGI) are not spatially integrated to the urban core - they are mainly located in the east of the FUA. It presents among the smallest shares of built up lands (residential, non residential, road and non road). Faro is a small coastal urban area (486 km²) with a large cover of wetlands and herbaceous land (representing respectively 10.12 and 23% of the total area) located around the urban core and a large agricultural land cover (42.55%). Tilburg is a small urban area (323 km²) with industrial activities, which translates into the highest covers of non residential. Residential, non residential, road and other UGI are more predominant for this city (covering respectively 12.79, 7.12, 5.03 and 4.92%). We note that for an urban area from the group Anthropogenic Cities, it has a high share of forest land with 19.51%.

	Resid. (%)	NResid. (%)	Road (%)	NRoad (%)	Agri. (%)	Forest (%)	Wet. (%)	Herba. (%)	Green (%)	Water (%)	Total (km ²)
Sarajevo	5.56	0.94	0.93	0.10	19.87	64.98	-	5.85	0.28	0.15	2,637
Newcastle	3.55	1.42	1.42	0.29	54.14	14.27	0.03	21.80	1.43	0.78	5,445
Faro	6.12	2.48	2.33	0.52	42.55	4.44	10.12	23.00	0.31	5.60	486
Tilburg	12.79	7.12	5.03	0.20	46.43	19.51	0.79	0.32	4.92	1.70	323

Note: Resid. = Residential, NResid. = Non Residential, NRoad = Non Road, Agri. = Agricultural, Wet. = Wetlands, Herba. = Herbaceous, Green = Other UGI.

Table 4.7: Land use covers in percentages

Annual emissions and sequestration

When looking at the annual emissions for the 802 European urban areas, it appears that two specific SNAP are dominant: SNAP1 (energy industries) with 77.14% and SNAP34 (industry combustion and processes) with 20.66% of the total annual emissions. We notice a very large variability of the total annual emissions: values range from 0.621 to 101,715,228 t CO₂, with a median of 440,489 t CO₂ and a coefficient of variation² of 259.16.

Concerning the four FUAs presented, SNAP1 represents close to 81.89% of the annual emissions in Sarajevo, while SNAP34 represents respectively about 73.40%, 75.77% and 98.24% of the annual emissions in Newcastle, Faro and Tilburg. Hence, without these two SNAP, the total annual emissions are significantly different as shown in lower part of Table 4.8 (see Sub-total B and Total). SNAP8 (non road transportation) seems to be the third most important one in terms of emissions with 23.91% (87,497.01 t CO₂) in Faro and 8.14% (35,857.78 t CO₂) in Tilburg. Table 4.8 shows the shares of SNAP for residential, road

²Ratio of the standard deviation to the mean times 100: $cv = \frac{sd}{mean} \times 100$

transportation and agricultural sectors. The total emissions of the five SNAP considered represent a very small proportion of the annual emissions of each FUA (see Sub-total A). The absolute values for all SNAP are available in the appendix in Table B.1. It is important to note that anthropogenic emissions arising from these SNAP and the industrial sector in general are very important in terms of magnitude for many European cities. More information on this matter is available in Chapter 5.

Regarding the annual sequestration of the 802 European urban areas, there is a lesser degree of variability. Values range from 0.654 to 4,957,378 t CO₂, with a median of 108,508 t CO₂ and a coefficient of variation of 156.38.

Sarajevo has the greatest sequestration capacity among the four FUAs with 1,249,207.86 t CO₂ as shown in Figure 4.3. It is followed by Newcastle with 415,327.06 t CO₂. Faro and Tilburg have substantially lesser sequestration capacities with respectively 74,243.59 and 52,427.57 t CO₂. When comparing with the annual emissions, we can expect to have a negative carbon balance and Faro and Tilburg to have positive carbon balance.

Sector	SNAP	Sarajevo	Newcastle	Faro	Tilburg
Residential	SNAP2	15.25	14.74	0.05	1.54
Road transport	SNAP71	0.09	0.35	0.00	0.07
	SNAP72	0.17	0.54	0.01	0.11
	SNAP73	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
Agriculture	SNAP10	1.26	1.83	0.25	0.02
	Sub-total A ¹	3,352	76,929	1,155	10,262
	Sub-total B ²	3,352	112,919	88,653	10,321
	Total ³	19,986	440,652	365,900	585,450

Note: emissions per SNAP are expressed in percentage; total and sub-totals are expressed in t CO₂

¹ Total for SNAP 2, 71-3, and 10.

² Total excluding SNAP 1 and 34.

³ Total of all SNAP.

Table 4.8: Annual emissions per SNAP

Figure 4.3: Total annual sequestration capacity in t CO₂

The spatially downscaled annual emissions are displayed in Figure 4.4, such that the

value of each cell has been computed following the Equation 4.3 (E_c^y). The estimation of the annual sequestration capacity is displayed in Figure 4.5 following the Equation 4.6 (S_c^y). When comparing the two figures, we can see that the cells with the highest potential of sequestration tend to be located away from impervious lands due to the competition for land or as a result of different planning strategies. Also, there is a very large gap between the values of the most emitting cells and the rest (the top interval of values represent the maximum and 99-th percentile). This phenomenon is due to the presence of industrial activities.

Figure 4.4: Downscaled annual emissions in t CO₂ per ha

Daily sequestration and relative emissions

Figure 4.6 displays (1) in green the aggregated sequestration capacity in t per day, and (2) in red the aggregated daily emissions as a percentage of the total sequestration capacity: $E/S \times 100$, with E and S being the sum of all cells c from Equations 4.9 and 4.12. The graphs allow to observe expected seasonal variations: an increase of the sequestration capacity following the growing season as well as more important relative emissions in winter time. The growing season starts earlier in Faro which is located in lower latitudes (subtropical climate zone, see Figure B.1 in the Appendix). Indeed, its peak

Figure 4.5: Annual sequestration capacity in t CO₂ per ha

of sequestration is reached in April. Sarajevo and Newcastle have higher potentials of sequestration thanks to their larger tree covers and vegetation type (see Table 4.7 and Figures B.11 and B.12 in Appendix). Sarajevo can sequester up to 7,861.41 t of CO₂ in May and Newcastle up to 2,406.86 t CO₂ in June, while the maxima for Faro and Tilburg are respectively of 285.75 and 313.50 t CO₂.

The total daily emissions do not always vary significantly along seasons in the presence of industrial activities which tend to be dominant in terms of proportion. Instead, we look at the relative emissions compared to the sequestration capacity, which presents a seasonal behavior. Relative emissions have to be interpreted with 100% as a reference. Underneath 100% the urban area can, *in theory*, sequester as much as it emits and could be considered to be a carbon sink. Above 100% the urban area emits more than its urban forest can sequester and is more likely to be a carbon source. All year long, Sarajevo has the potential to sequester more than what it emits, when looking at aggregated values (or with a urban carbon metabolism perspective). Hence, we expect the static aggregated budget to be negative as the urban area is a carbon sink with this definition. In January and February the relative emissions are the highest with 55.54 and 56.24% and from April to October, relative emissions are smaller than 2%. It results from rather low emissions and a large vegetated cover (see Table 4.7 and Figure 4.6.b). For Newcastle, the maximum is reached in December with 1066.67% but from April to September, values remain underneath 100%. Despite having high annual emissions (with 440,652 t CO₂ in 2012), its urban forest has a rather high potential of sequestration (see Tables 4.8, 4.7 and Figure 4.6.b). Additionally, Faro and Tilburg emit

more than the sequestration capacity of their urban forest on the average Monday of each month. Hence, we expect their static aggregated budget to be positive as the urban areas are carbon sources with this definition. For Faro, relative estimations are above 400% all year round, with a peak of 876.57% in November. For Tilburg, the situation is even more critical with a minimum of 525.95% in July and a maximum of 15,503.23% in January. It results from both a high level of anthropogenic emissions and a low capacity of sequestration (see Table 4.8 and Figure 4.6.b). Such trend indicates that effort have to be made both on emissions reduction and on wise afforestation planning.

Figure 4.6: Variations of daily sequestration (S) and relative emissions (E) as a percentage of the sequestration capacity ($E / S \times 100$). Daily emissions correspond to average Monday of the month while daily sequestration correspond to the proportion of a day in each month

4.5 Discussion and conclusions

UCB is a high spatial and temporal resolution urban carbon balance model for which a database is publicly available for 802 functional urban areas in Europe (Boura and Caruso, 2021). It can be used to assess and compare the carbon profiles of urban areas in terms of anthropogenic emissions, sequestration capacity, absolute and relative carbon balance. Emissions data are sector specific and the methodology can be replicated over space and time. The database currently considers the year 2012 and will be extended for the year 2018 in the future.

The datasets created provide a unique insight that can be used in urban planning, climate models or ecosystem service analyses. In combination with landscape metrics, the UCB can help to understand the link between urban form and carbon profile,

and thus support urban planning policies to influence the urban carbon footprint as a complement to emissions reduction. Current methods (transport models, urban carbon metabolism, EC measurements or remote sensing) do not allow for both a high resolution of the estimates and a standardised approach to assess the carbon profile of several areas and enable comparisons. The contribution of the urban forest to carbon sequestration, within and beyond urban areas could be estimated with more accuracy for a large number of areas using the model or data presented in this article.

Yet, it is important to note the uncertainties and limitations of the methodology and of the database. As mentioned previously, the emission data may overestimate residential emissions in highly populated areas because of the use of a population density proxy. Due to lack of data, we do not account for the waste sector which is estimated to have released 2,791.55 kt of CO₂ in Europe (EU28) in 2019 (EEA, 2021). In addition, the sequestration estimates are based on average values per vegetation type and different ecological zones. The parameters used for the estimations are hence coarse and likely to present more variability in reality due to the distribution of different species, soil quality or soil depth. Applying a spatial interpolation could represent an improvement. Moreover, emission time decompositions factors are at the country level and hence may not account for the variability of climates for countries with more than one ecological zone or climatic domain which is likely to influence the energy demand (residential, commercial, as well as energy sector). A possible further improvement of the UCB model concerns the simulation of spatial dispersion. Thereafter, we could consider monthly and then yearly carbon balances for the studied areas via a cumulating approach.

Despite these limitations, our approach represents an appropriate and viable alternative to heavy model, very local data collection or repeated local field measurements. It allows to produce high resolution and comparable estimates for a large number of areas.

5. Urban carbon balance and urban patterns in Europe

Accessibility

The UCB database is available on the platform Zenodo (Boura and Caruso, 2021) and on GitHub (<https://github.com/mboura/UCB>).

5.1 Introduction

In 2016, the Paris Agreement was adopted with as main objective the limitation of global warming below 2°C compared to pre-industrial levels by 2100. The CO₂ concentration into the atmosphere is the predominant GHG (greenhouse gas) currently impacting climate change (IPCC, 2015, 2019). Climate change is now one of the planetary boundaries at stake (Rockström et al., 2009, Steffen et al., 2015, Raworth, 2017) and the CO₂ concentration is used as a proxy. The threshold is set to 350 ppm corresponding to the limit to remain below 2°C by 2100 (Steffen et al., 2015). Yet, in February 2021 we reached a global average concentration of 415.88 ppm (NOAA, 2021), and the recent projections from the IPCC are rather pessimistic for the coming decades (IPCC, 2021). Only under the most optimistic scenario (SSP1-9), global warming is considered as extremely unlikely to go beyond the threshold of 2°C.

Urban carbon cycles are impacting regional and global carbon cycles but insights on these exchanges remain scarce (Hutyra et al., 2014). In order to assess the positive or negative contribution, and most importantly, the magnitude of the contribution of urban areas to wider carbon systems, we first need to appraise the carbon profiles of a large number of urban areas at a meaningful spatio-temporal resolution. It is also important to understand the intra-urban dynamics impacting the resulting carbon balance. We expect the urban carbon balance to be driven by the spatial integration of the urban forest within an urban area. Our attempt focuses on the European case to assess the contribution and carbon profile of 802 urban areas to their surroundings.

In this context, it is important to mention the European Green Deal. In order to achieve a net-zero GHG neutrality by 2050, as a step forward from the Paris Agreement, countries from the EU are encouraged to pursue economic growth which does not rely on

resource use. A first milestone is set in 2030: a reduction by 55% of the GHG emissions compared to 1990. In order to take action in the most efficient way, better insight on the current situation is needed. This empirical study aims at understanding to which extent, the urban spatial organisation can impact the carbon balance and how. Finding the main drivers will help designing spatial planning policies to head towards the 2050 European Green Deal Agenda.

This article investigates the link between carbon profiles and the urban landscape typology. Carbon profiles are defined after the CO₂ emissions, sequestration and carbon balance. The absolute and relative carbon balance are computed after the simulation of a steady-state like spatial dispersion of CO₂ molecules. We aim at answering the following research questions: which carbon profiles are present in European cities? and how does the urban landscape impact the carbon profile? It will allow the identification of urban landscape characteristics leading to smaller or higher carbon balances under steady-state conditions.

Boura and Caruso (2021) propose a European urban database on CO₂ emissions, sequestration and balance at a 1 ha spatial resolution for a typical day per month along the year 2012. The method and data used allow for comparison among the 802 urban areas for which the urban boundaries have been defined in the same way (FUAs defined by the OECD, 2013) and estimates have been computed using the same input data. Boura and Caruso (2021) propose a typology for 689 European urban areas. The typology is based on landscape metrics associated to their urban forest, anthropogenic lands, and their relative spatial organisation. A detailed description of the clusters and groups characteristics is available in Table 5.1. Note that all figures summarizing variables per cluster do not account for the 802 urban areas of the study area, but for a subset of 689 of them, for which the UFES typology was created by Boura and Caruso (under review) (see Chapter 3).

Group	Cluster	n	Description
Forest Cities	F1	20	Forest Cities in the strict sense
	F2	8	Forest Cities with Land Sharing
	F3	42	Sparse Forest Cities
	F4	82	Fragmented Forest Cities
Herbaceous Cities	H1	13	Wetlands Cities
	H2	86	Herbaceous Cities in the strict sense
Standard European Cities	E1	183	
Anthropogenic Cities	A1	109	Artificial Cities
	A2	110	Built-up Cities
	A3	36	Built-up Green Cities

Table 5.1: Presentation of the clusters from the UFES typology

5.2 Results

5.2.1 CO₂ emissions

Distribution

Figure 5.1 shows the total annual CO₂ emissions per urban area in t. A large number of urban areas emitted small to very small amounts of CO₂ in 2012, while a smaller number emitted millions t CO₂. 416 urban areas (51.87%) emitted less than 500,000 t

CO₂, of which 201 (25.06 %) emitted less than 10,000 t CO₂. On the other hand, 66 (8.22%) emitted more than 10,000,000 t CO₂. As expected, these tend to be large populated area or industrial hubs. The trend seems to be associated with the typology of cities according to Figure 5.2. We can distinguish two groups of cities in terms of annual emission profile: clusters A1, E1 and F3 gathering the main emitting urban areas. 75% of the cities within these clusters emitted more than 100,000 t CO₂ from anthropogenic activities. The lowest emitting urban areas are in clusters F2, A3 and F4. It is slightly surprising to see how "well" cities from cluster A3 perform, given their landscape characteristics (see Chapter 3). More details are available in Box 5.1 for the high emitters and Box 5.2 for the low emitters.

Figure 5.1: Map of annual CO₂ emissions per urban area.

Energy industries and industry combustion and processes

The presence and intensity of emissions coming from SNAP1 (energy industries) and SNAP34 (industry combustion and processes) represent a clear driver in the total annual emissions of an urban area. Indeed, the total annual emissions are significantly (at significance level $\alpha = 0.01\%$) and positively correlated to the annual SNAP1 and SNAP34 emissions per urban area with Pearson's linear correlation coefficients of respectively 0.97 (p-value < 2.2e-16) and 0.66 (p-value < 2.2e-16). See Figure C.3 in Appendix. Figures 5.3 and 5.4 display the shares of SNAP 1 and 34 in the total annual emissions for

Figure 5.2: Distribution of the log of annual CO₂ emissions for each cluster from the UFES typology.

each urban area. The median share of emissions arising from SNAP1 is 29.39% (with an average of 42.60%). Yet, 332 out of 802 urban areas (41%) do not emit from SNAP1 and 362 (45.13%) of the urban areas, have more than half of their total emissions coming from SNAP1 only. Similarly, the median share of emissions arising from SNAP34 is 4.84% (with an average of 25.21%). 61 out of 802 urban areas (7.60%) do not emit from SNAP34 and 182 (22.69%) of the urban areas, have more than half of their total emissions coming from SNAP34 only.

Figure 5.3: Share of CO₂ emissions from SNAP1

Figure 5.4: Share of CO₂ emissions from SNAP34

Population

It is known that the intensity of anthropogenic emissions is impacted by the population size. This is partially verified here. Figure 5.5 shows the log-log relationship between the total annual emissions and the population size. It reveals the presence of two groups: cities with emissions up to $\log(E) \leq 10$ (or up to $E = 22026.47 \text{ t CO}_2$) and those with higher emissions. We performed a log-log linear regression for all the cities for which we have the population size within the FUA (368 FUAs) and for both groups (see Table C.1 in Appendix). For the overall regression, not all conditions are fulfilled to validate the regression, the relationship between population change and annual emissions seems more complex. For low emitters, the population size is able to explain 38% of the variability in annual emissions and we are confident in the trend as the residuals are normally distributed¹ and that no heteroskedasticity was detected² at significance level 0.01%. For this group, an increase in population size of 1% increases annual emissions on average by 1.357%, which translates an increasing return to scale (at significance level 0.01%). The demand for anthropogenic emissions is hence elastic to the population size. For higher emitters, the population size is able to explain only 22% of the variability in annual emissions, yet the residuals are normally distributed and that no heteroskedasticity was detected at significance level 0.01%. For this group, an increase in population size of 1% increases annual emissions on average by 0.884%, which translates a decreasing return to scale (at significance level 0.01%). The demand for anthropogenic emissions is hence inelastic to the population size.

5.2.2 Daily capacity of CO₂ sequestration

Figure 5.6 presents the total sequestration capacity for each urban area on a typical day of each month. The temporal and spatial patterns of the growing season are visible:

¹p-value from the Shapiro-Wilk test of normality equals 0.073.

²p-value from the Breusch-Pagan test of heteroskedasticity equals 0.3004.

Figure 5.5: Linear regressions - Log emissions VS Log population size

(1) the sequestration potential increases from spring onwards, peaks during summer and decreases before winter; (2) warmer areas in southern Europe benefit from a longer growing season. Figure 5.7 shows that Anthropogenic Cities (A1-3) and Herbaceous Cities (H2) have the lowest absolute sequestration capacity, while Forest Cities (F1-4) and Standard European Cities (E1) have among the highest sequestration capacity. Nevertheless, cluster F2 (from the group of Forest Cities), presents significantly lower values of absolute sequestration capacity, which can originate from the fact that it is mainly composed of rather small urban areas. However, the sequestration capacity must be differentiated from the actual amount of sequestration. The latter is constrained by: the actual amount of emissions within a given period, the relative distance between emitting and vegetated land, the sequestration capacity of the different vegetated land and the meteorological conditions.

5.2.3 Carbon balance

The different daily metrics used to assess the carbon profiles all seem to be influenced by the UFES typology, and therefore by the urban structure and configuration. Figure 5.8.a. presents the daily CO₂ emissions in t (E) for a typical Monday of each month. The lowest emitting urban areas tend to belong to clusters F2, A3 and H1. The most emitting urban areas tend to belong to clusters A1, E1, F3 and A2. Emissions tend to be higher from December to February, yet no strong seasonality is observed.

Figure 5.8.b. provides the daily CO₂ budget in t ($B = E - S$). About half of urban areas from clusters A3, F1, F2, F4 and H1 have the potential to be close to neutral or carbon sinks. They can contribute positively to wider carbon cycles by sequestering more than their own emissions. The main sinks are more likely to belong to clusters F1 and F3. On the other hand, most urban areas from clusters A1, A2, E1 and F3 are important sources of CO₂. These cities are contributing in a negative way to the regional and global carbon cycles.

Figure 5.8.c. displays daily sequestration as a percentage of the daily emissions ($S_R = S / E \times 100$). Relatively to their very low amount of emissions, cities from the cluster F2 are unsurprisingly able to sequester a much greater amount of CO₂: up to $2.84e^{12}\%$ of

Figure 5.6: Map of daily absolute CO₂ sequestration capacity per urban area for each month.

their own emissions, with median values ranging from $8.10e^9$ to $1.96e^{11}\%$. Continuing in median terms, cluster A1 and A2 present the smallest relative sequestration capacity: values are ranging respectively from 0.336 to 8.77% and from 0.574 to 20.6%. Clusters A3, E1, F3, F4 and H1 present rather comparable median patterns, with cluster A3 performing slightly better (median values ranging from 6.72 to 972%).

Figure 5.9 displays both the absolute and relative annual emissions of anthropogenic CO₂ across our study area. Cities with a large net contribution to regional and global carbon cycles (relatively to their sequestration capacity) are mainly located in the UK, Netherlands and western Germany. Yet the main absolute contributors are also located further east, in Germany or Poland. Relative sinks tend to be small net emitters. Figure 5.10 allows to assess the magnitude of the potential of cities as net sinks or sources. The dominant sources are located along the Manchester-Milan axis, but they are also present in most countries. The main sinks tend to be rather median or small cities in terms of population size, and are predominantly in central Europe and in the Balkans.

Figure 5.7: Distribution of the daily absolute CO₂ sequestration potential per cluster for each month.

Figure 5.8: Distributions. **a.** Absolute daily emissions per cluster (t CO₂ per day). **b.** Absolute daily budget per cluster (t CO₂ per day). **c.** Relative daily CO₂ sequestration per cluster (% of daily emissions).

Figure 5.9: Absolute and relative anthropogenic CO₂ emissions per FUA

5.3 Discussion

This article explores the carbon profiles of 802 European functional urban areas using the High Resolution UCB database and investigates the link between the carbon profiles and the spatial integration of the urban forest. This work is part of a first step towards a better understanding of the contribution of the urban carbon cycle within the regional and global carbon cycles. Carbon profiles are here defined with: CO₂ emissions, capacity of sequestration, absolute and relative carbon balance. The previous section showed that they are impacted by the UFES typology. We discuss here more in details how urban patterns are impacting the European urban carbon profiles and their potential contribution to wider carbon balance systems.

A large green cover? Yes but...

The comparison between clusters F1 and F2 shows that a larger forest cover is not a solution on its own. Urban areas from cluster F1 have a much larger forest and wetlands covers. Their forest patches are larger, numerous and among the least fragmented. On the other hand, urban areas from cluster F2 present much larger proportions of vegetation within small buffers around anthropogenic land such as road network and

Figure 5.10: Annual CO₂ budget per FUA

residential land. In addition, non-residential built up land is less aggregated. Both clusters present comparable covers of impervious land (including roads, other transport infrastructures, residential and non-residential built up). They have rather comparable levels of emissions but cluster F2 have much lower levels of emission. They both present a high to rather high capacity of sequestration but due to a higher emission profile, urban areas from cluster F1 are also sequestering more in absolute terms. Yet, the small number of cities from cluster F2 are able to sequester a larger amount of their own emissions despite their smaller forest cover.

The low performances of cluster F3 can be explained by its very low level of connectivity between the forest patches associated to a high level of connectivity of residential lands and road network. Despite having a larger forest cover than clusters F2 and F4, and more vegetation around its road network, cluster F3 is comparable in many ways to cluster A1, the most anthropogenic cluster. These spatial configurations characteristics are weakening the high capacity of sequestration presented in Figure 5.7 due to a lack of spatial integration between anthropogenic land and the urban forest. In addition, cities from this cluster have among the highest levels of emissions.

Anthropogenic Cities are not doomed

The good performances of the cluster A3 compared to the other Anthropogenic Cities originates from multiple aspects. The impervious land and artificial green covers - characteristic of the group - are much less predominant than for clusters A1 and A2. In addition, the road network is less dense and impervious lands such as residential built up and are less spatially aggregated and connected. Regarding the urban forest, they present a smaller cover of artificial green, a slightly bigger forest covers which is spatially more aggregated and connected, and present bigger forest patches. These aspects coupled to smaller levels of emissions despite a low capacity of sequestration leads to a better relative carbon balance than clusters A1 and A2. It suggests that a reduction of anthropogenic emissions accompanying an increase of the quantity and integration of the urban forest could have a significant impact on the carbon balance, even for Anthropogenic Cities.

Now less anticipated, the difference between the clusters F3 and A3. Albeit cluster F3 belongs to the group Forest Cities and possesses a larger forest cover and vegetation near anthropogenic lands, it performs less well than cluster A3 from the group Anthropogenic Cities. They both present comparable share of impervious lands, but for cluster A3, the road network is less dense and connected. In addition, despite having smaller patches of forest, cluster A3 has a higher connectivity among the forest patches and they are less fragmented. Hence, despite the fact that cluster F3 has a much larger capacity of sequestration along the year, urban areas from cluster A3 tend to have a better relative carbon balance than those of cluster F3.

What to prioritise?

The energy production and industrial combustion and processes are the main sectors of emissions for the highly emitting urban areas. Hence the presence of these two sectors influences the regional carbon balance more than any other sector of emission in terms of intensity. For these urban areas, heading towards a more neutral carbon balance starts with questioning their industrial sector as a whole. Indeed, only increasing the spatial integration between anthropogenic and vegetated lands cannot represent a solution on its own due to the to high level of emissions regarding the sequestration capacity. Instead, the urban forest cover and integration should be developed along with a strong strategy to reduce the carbon footprint of their industrial sector.

The least emitting cities are more driven by residential, transport and agricultural emissions. Hence, policies towards more carbon neutral balance can take two directions. (1) increasing the spatial integration between anthropogenic and natural land cover and (2) implementing policies to reduce emissions from these sectors. It is trivial to pinpoint the most emitting sectors to better understand how to proceed and to identify which action will have a higher impact on a specific urban carbon balance.

5.4 Conclusion

This contribution uses the first European urban high resolution CO₂ emissions, sequestration and balance database. Sectoral anthropogenic CO₂ emissions have been downscaled spatially and temporally such that data are available in t per ha per average Monday of each month for hundreds urban areas. A 2D spatial dispersion has been simulated for each average day. Natural carbon sequestration by the urban forests has been estimated for the corresponding urban areas at the same spatio-temporal resolution. From these data, aggregated and disaggregated carbon balance estimates and metrics are available. We used this database in association with the UFES typology

and population size associated to these FUAs when available, in order to understand the dynamics at stake and how the urban structure can impact the urban carbon balance, itself impacting the regional carbon balance.

One key finding is that the quantity of urban forest is not enough to guarantee a low carbon balance. Emphasis should be put on urban plans aiming at increasing the spatial integration of the urban forest near anthropogenic land, regardless of the amount of forest cover. In addition, it is noteworthy that say that too intense industrial activities could cripple an urban area on its path towards a more carbon neutral balance. Indeed, the magnitude of some industrial activities may considerably outperform the total *theoretical* capacity of sequestration of their urban forest and make these urban areas very unlikely to become regional carbon sinks. Afforestation possibilities within urban cores or their peripheries are limited, hence, too high industrial emissions may not be compensated by increasing the urban forest cover, even with a good spatial integration. However, a large number of urban areas, even with industrial activities, already present a good carbon balance. And a non negligible proportion of European urban areas have room for improvement. The association of both emission reduction policies with urban forest integration could have a significant impact on the carbon balance of a large number of urban areas.

Further investigation on the impact of specific landscape metrics would allow to better target the key leverages for more impactfull local actions. In addition, a zoom out from the studied urban areas would allow to better understand their contribution to the regional systems. This work focused on steady-state daily conditions along the year. In this context, we found that a higher degree of dispersion is favorable to the carbon balance for most urban areas. But some exeptions are visible and require further analysis.

Box 5.1 Top 20 of annual CO₂ emissions

The four SNAP displayed in Table 5.2 sum up to about 100% of the annual emissions of the 20 most emitting urban areas. The energy and industrial sectors (SNAP 1 and 34) are definitely predominant. Note that all values are rounded: other sectors are also emitting but represent an insignificant part of the total emissions.

FUA	ISO	Total (t/year)	SNAP1 (%)	SNAP34 (%)	SNAP5 (%)	SNAP8 (%)
Ruhrgebiet	DE	101,715,228	68.06	31.26	0	0.25
Koln	DE	86,321,332	97.31	2.45	0	0.14
Dusseldorf	DE	61,722,367	78.42	21.03	0	0.39
Berlin	DE	58,996,196	91.37	7.37	0.03	0.37
Katowice	PL	50,600,570	83.30	16.58	0.01	0.01
Kingston upon Hull	UK	45,987,659	89.33	10.57	0	0.01
Cottbus	DE	43,586,148	99.98	0	0	0
Istanbul	TR	39,764,076	79.60	16.74	0	2.76
Leeds	UK	37,444,191	99.69	0.03	0	0.04
Dresden	DE	30,801,126	99.56	0.18	0.00	0.08
Rotterdam	NL	29,193,546	79.38	19.79	0.46	0.04
Gorlitz	DE	28,500,938	99.98	0	0	0
Most	CZ	26,425,171	99.40	0	0.59	0
Edinburgh	UK	26,041,004	93.32	6.26	0	0.27
Ostrava	CZ	25,763,777	58.65	40.88	0.35	0.01
Aachen	DE	23,566,375	99.96	0	0	0
Monchengladbach	DE	21,663,395	99.68	0.22	0	0
Adana-Mersin	TR	19,600,690	80.99	18.33	0	0.26
Taranto	IT	19,298,568	31.85	68.12	0	0
Marseille	FR	18,535,551	39.68	58.60	0	1.22

Table 5.2: Top 20 of annual CO₂ emissions

Box 5.2 Bottom 20 of annual CO₂ emissions

Considering the least emitting urban areas, none of them have energy industries (SNAP1) within their boundaries and the industrial sector (SNAP34) is generally much less predominant. The four SNAP displayed in Table 5.3 - residential, road transport, agriculture, industrial combustion and processes - sum up to more than 99% for these urban areas' annual emissions (SNAP71-3 have been aggregated).

FUA	ISO	Total (t/year)	SNAP2 (%)	SNAP7 (%)	SNAP10 (%)	SNAP34 (%)
Eastbourne	UK	0.621	98.59	1.30	0	0
Benidorm	ES	2.939	34.99	7.31	25.22	31.38
Linea de la C.	ES	20.550	93.42	6.52	0	0
Ponferrada	ES	73.120	51.55	7.66	27.62	12.79
Fethiye	TR	81.096	40.48	5.59	53.92	0
Bingol	TR	108.554	20.71	1.84	77.43	0.01
Elda	ES	121.180	68.84	9.27	7.95	13.76
Gandia	ES	139.105	38.79	11.35	46.26	3.46
Sanremo	IT	194.264	93.71	4.91	0.90	0.01
Manresa	ES	196.789	48.68	16.62	18.77	15.33
Torre Vieja	ES	206.643	86.53	11.60	1.35	0.36
Slatina	RO	209.71	16.11	0.26	72.21	11.23
Povoa de Varzim	PT	282.57	58.27	6.85	32.51	2.09
Caceres	ES	315.009	8.54	6.26	80.36	4.77
Rize	TR	337.150	46.79	2.32	50.88	0.00
Kalamata	EL	432.983	10.12	1.31	88.00	0.29
Mostar	BA	463.719	53.49	2.61	23.71	20.18
Zamora	ES	479.986	3.11	1.13	95.48	0.24
Elk	PL	499.877	42.01	1.20	54.11	1.87
Acireale	IT	555.706	97.17	1.58	1.19	0.01

Table 5.3: Bottom 20 of annual CO₂ emissions

6. General discussion and conclusion

This PhD thesis aimed at understanding the link between the spatial integration of different types of vegetation within urban settlements and its implication on the supply of ecosystem services from the urban forest. The main methodological is the development of the UCB model: a high resolution, standardised and replicable method to estimate carbon flows. We also characterised different types of urban patterns in European urban areas and their relationship to the supply and demand with 5 ecosystem services associated to the urban forest. Last, we identified a link between the level of integration of the urban forest and the carbon footprint of urban areas.

In this chapter we discuss the methodological thematic contributions of the thesis. Finally, we reflect on the limitations and discuss potential future work to carry out from this research.

6.1 Methodological contributions

UFES typology

Previous knowledge on the link between urban form and urban ES flows is limited for several reasons. Firstly, they do not differentiate the different between types of urban vegetation, nor account for metrics providing information on the spatial integration of the urban forest. Yet, the different types of vegetation contribute differently to different ES. Secondly, the majority are case studies which suffer from a lack of standards and are therefore rarely comparable (different approaches, urban definitions and types of data). The UFES typology presented in Chapter 2 is the first to address the above drawbacks. The land use database used allows to assess the diversity and spatial organisation of the urban forest in urban areas at a high spatial resolution. The method used allowed to consider a very large number of urban areas and to gain knowledge from existing cases. Furthermore, it is easily replicable (different location or time period).

UCB model

The High Resolution Urban Carbon Balance (UCB) model allowed to create the first European high resolution CO₂ emissions database for urban areas. The method to do so

considers sectoral emissions, applies spatial downscaling based on land use data, and temporal downscaling based on sectors, year and country. It has also allowed to create the first high resolution database on sequestration capacity for European urban areas. Additionally, the model proposes to simulate the spatial dispersion of the anthropogenic emissions and their sequestration, for the time being, in a simplistic way. The UCB model can be replicated for other locations or time periods. Moreover, the emission part is not limited to CO₂ emissions, and could be used to downscale other gases and air pollutants from a LU dataset and the some emission or concentration data only.

6.2 Urban form, urban forest and ecosystem services

In Chapter 2, 10 different types of urban patterns were identified in the European urban areas studied. They can be gathered into 4 groups: Forest, Herbaceous, Anthropogenic and Standard European Cities. Each cluster is characterised by a set of landscape metrics describing the urban pattern, the spatial organisation and the potential of ES flows. The spatial organisation aspect emphasises on the integration of different vegetation types within the urban core and on the spatial configuration of these natural and semi-natural land. UFES scores were then computed, in Chapter 3, to provide an overview of the UFES potential of each urban area. They identify which urban patterns types are more or less sensitive to the 5 urban stressors studied. These scores show that, as anticipated, Forest Cities tend to support a positive UFES score, while Anthropogenic Cities are more associated with a negative score. A negative score means that they are more likely to have a demand for ES from the urban forest which exceeds what the existing urban forest can provide.

Looking at the clusters within each group allows to nuance the previous conclusions. We found that urban compactness is not supporting the provision of ecosystem services. Instead, a certain degree of fragmentation of anthropogenic land by the urban forest leads to a better global capacity of delivering UFES. Therefore, the spatial integration of the urban forest into the urban core can improve the human wellbeing (micro climate, air quality, rainwater runoff and human health regulation), as well as reduce the contribution of the urban areas to climate change (macro climate regulation). This finding is verified for the group Forest Cities, as well as for the group Anthropogenic Cities (see Chapter 3). The direct consequence is that urban patterns with low level of urban forest integration near the human activity hotspots are more likely to experience higher levels of urban stress.

In Chapter 5, we looked at the relationship between urban carbon profiles and the types of urban patterns. The use of metrics describing the carbon profile of urban areas, instead of the macro index score as an indicator of macro climate regulation flows (see Chapter 3), has provided a set of new knowledge. Two specific clusters of urban areas provided interesting new insights: A3 (Built-up Green Cities) and F3 (Sparse Forest Cities). In the case of the urban carbon balance, the level of spatial integration of the urban forest seems to play a more important role than observed previously. The large and dense urban forest cover of cluster F3 translates into a high theoretical sequestration capacity. Yet, the low level of spatial integration of the urban forest is limiting its capacity to sequester its own anthropogenic emissions. On the other hand, the anthropogenic cities from cluster A3, despite a low sequestration capacity, they tend to have rather high relative sequestration capacity.

In addition, we identified an important limitation on this approach. It is trivial to first identify the main emitting sectors, but more particularly, the magnitude of their emissions in comparison to the sequestration capacity. The least emitting cities are more

driven by residential, transport and agricultural sectors. The energy production and industrial combustion and processes are the main sectors of emissions for the highly emitting European urban areas. In a number of cases, these emissions cumulate to tens of thousands t CO₂ per year. This can hardly be compensated by an optimised urban planning approach. For these urban areas, heading towards a more neutral carbon balance starts with questioning their industrial sector as a whole.

6.3 Limitations

Data availability and quality

This thesis intended to analyse a large number of European urban areas in a systematic way, in order to be able to compare and learn from aggregated results. Unfortunately, to date there is no homogeneous and detailed database at the European scale of the urban vegetation. The decision to carry out a systematic analysis therefore had an impact on the quality of the input data (spatial resolution, accuracy and type of data), and thus on the uncertainty of the results of this research. This has resulted in the use of data for which information on the vegetation are not as detailed as they could have been if the study area was limited to one or a few case studies.

Simplifications in modelling

Simplifications are inherent in modelling. The different chapters of this dissertation are all subject to some level of simplification. They are two main reasons for this. Firstly, the objective was not to simulate ecological processes as complex as the reality. Rather, the objective was to gain knowledge from known processes, and the results should be used as such. Secondly, the data available or selected sometimes induced a simplification. For instance, considering the UFES typology, two forest stands could have very different types of vegetation, tree cover or soil quality. However, the data used did not allow for any further characterisation and all forest patches were considered as equivalent.

Computing limitations

Another important aspect is the computational part. The pre-processing and processing such a large amount of spatial datasets required important resources. At each step, the data are produced for hundreds of urban areas at a high spatial resolution and sometimes at multiple time resolutions or for multiple categories (sector, LU, etc.). Fortunately, I had access to the HPC facilities of the University of Luxembourg (Varrette et al., 2014), which allowed me to process part of my scripts more efficiently, and remotely.

6.4 Continuing this work

The databases created from Chapters Chapter 2, Chapter 3 and 4 allow to consider a large set of perspectives and further works. The types of urban patterns, and more particularly the level of integration of the urban forest, has been identified as an important component in the supply of urban ecosystem services.

Regarding the UCB model, two further steps in its development have been identified. The first one is to conduct a sensitivity analysis to assess the level of uncertainty of each parameters. The second is about proposing a simulation of the dispersion which accounts for the main wind fields. It would allow to use the UCB model beyond a single average day per month, but for a cumulated period instead.

The empirical analysis of the UCB database could also be extended to evaluate the impact of specific landscape metrics on different aspects of the carbon profiles. In

addition, the UCB database will be available for the year 2018 in the future.

An extension of both the UFES typology and the UCB model to different continents could also bring interesting new insights. More particularly for comparisons with North America, where more examples are already available.

Another important possible further work concerns the delimitation of the urban boundaries. In this thesis, functional urban boundaries were used as they are more meaningful in the context of urban ES. Yet, there is no "right" definition of the urban boundaries and one could consider questioning the implications of different definitions of urban with regard to different urban ES.

A. Chapter 3

A.1 Clustering

Figure A.1: Dendrogram of the HCA - 10 clusters in 4 groups

Figure A.2: Spatial distribution of standardised spatial metrics

Figure A.3: Distribution of standardised metrics per cluster

Notes: red dots indicate cluster' mean; dashed lines are located at ± 2 the standard deviation.

Variables	Groups					Clusters					ANOVA			
	E	F	H	A	F1	F2	F3	F4	H1	H2		A1	A2	A3
ForestsPct	0.508 (0.623)	1.233 (0.874)	-0.701 (0.526)	-0.604 (0.480)	2.358 (0.760)	1.035 (0.800)	1.670 (0.472)	0.755 (0.687)	-0.745 (0.480)	-0.413 (0.723)	-0.567 (0.472)	-0.749 (0.415)	-0.273 (0.516)	169.5846 (3.63E-167)
Forests_50_area_cv	0.532 (0.840)	0.988 (1.132)	-0.486 (0.432)	-0.560 (0.462)	1.097 (1.287)	0.986 (0.498)	2.005 (1.115)	0.440 (0.711)	-0.461 (0.439)	-0.651 (0.348)	-0.511 (0.503)	-0.643 (0.414)	-0.454 (0.440)	85.8412 (6.66E-106)
Forests_50_area_mn	0.125 (0.562)	0.719 (1.907)	-0.196 (0.359)	-0.341 (0.303)	3.600 (3.985)	0.880 (1.138)	0.650 (0.679)	0.036 (0.432)	-0.216 (0.357)	-0.061 (0.355)	-0.367 (0.241)	-0.398 (0.298)	-0.084 (0.362)	55.7631 (8.23E-76)
Forests_50_cohesion	0.538 (0.162)	0.616 (0.157)	-0.039 (0.715)	-0.424 (1.133)	0.737 (0.016)	0.676 (0.068)	0.710 (0.030)	0.532 (0.171)	-0.059 (0.738)	0.095 (0.552)	-0.329 (0.978)	-0.738 (1.324)	0.246 (0.319)	37.6096 (3.18E-54)
Forests_50_config_mn	-0.203 (0.740)	0.018 (0.976)	0.677 (1.271)	-0.099 (0.906)	-0.417 (0.918)	1.019 (0.772)	-0.563 (0.934)	0.324 (0.818)	0.601 (1.319)	1.178 (0.736)	-0.299 (0.706)	-0.076 (1.011)	0.435 (0.901)	14.5291 (1.22E-21)
Forests_50_division	0.044 (0.438)	-1.002 (1.851)	0.356 (0.065)	0.330 (0.200)	-4.646 (2.228)	-1.015 (1.605)	-1.044 (0.945)	-0.091 (0.657)	0.359 (0.063)	0.335 (0.077)	0.296 (0.256)	0.370 (0.127)	0.313 (0.168)	173.3473 (2.10E-169)
Forests_50_ed	0.277 (0.647)	1.157 (0.872)	-0.773 (0.616)	-0.410 (0.749)	1.006 (1.006)	0.752 (0.827)	1.241 (0.619)	1.191 (0.949)	-0.796 (0.614)	-0.627 (0.637)	-0.127 (0.817)	-0.685 (0.572)	-0.205 (0.708)	72.2587 (4.64E-93)
WetlandsPct	-0.159 (0.418)	-0.132 (0.564)	0.612 (2.274)	-0.056 (0.473)	0.035 (1.093)	-0.311 (0.041)	-0.084 (0.557)	-0.180 (0.376)	-0.216 (0.282)	6.090 (2.062)	-0.117 (0.410)	-0.009 (0.505)	-0.015 (0.538)	194.2791 (2.90E-181)
HerbaceousPct	-0.331 (0.599)	-0.002 (0.768)	1.561 (0.445)	-0.346 (0.445)	-0.024 (0.430)	1.408 (0.847)	-0.161 (0.665)	-0.053 (0.747)	1.745 (1.164)	0.342 (0.886)	-0.399 (0.332)	-0.243 (0.569)	-0.505 (0.150)	81.2654 (1.07E-101)
ArtificialPct	-0.212 (0.413)	-0.492 (0.285)	-0.561 (0.280)	0.410 (1.049)	-0.577 (0.186)	-0.596 (0.354)	-0.385 (0.335)	-0.516 (0.258)	-0.578 (0.254)	-0.448 (0.406)	1.152 (1.111)	-0.034 (0.561)	-0.477 (0.230)	77.0027 (1.13E-97)
Artificial_50_cohesion	0.210 (0.680)	-0.433 (1.034)	-0.476 (0.956)	0.341 (0.808)	-0.754 (0.811)	-0.187 (1.193)	0.079 (1.028)	-0.641 (0.984)	-0.471 (0.980)	-0.510 (0.808)	0.432 (0.711)	0.350 (0.864)	0.038 (0.856)	17.2731 (7.43E-26)
Artificial_50_config_mn	0.110 (0.792)	-0.513 (0.846)	-0.712 (0.793)	0.449 (0.895)	-0.860 (0.693)	-0.592 (0.800)	-0.182 (0.586)	-0.590 (0.948)	-0.788 (0.712)	-0.205 (1.110)	0.235 (0.770)	0.619 (0.935)	0.575 (1.009)	26.3895 (3.45E-39)
Forests_UrbanFabric1500	-0.060 (0.205)	0.757 (2.075)	-0.193 (0.209)	-0.254 (0.090)	0.586 (0.651)	7.955 (5.014)	0.406 (0.346)	0.277 (0.520)	-0.192 (0.210)	-0.195 (0.212)	-0.260 (0.077)	-0.269 (0.079)	-0.188 (0.126)	183.6076 (2.46E-175)
Artificial_UrbanFabric1000	-0.158 (0.289)	0.048 (2.011)	-0.191 (0.326)	0.094 (0.537)	-0.111 (0.853)	4.587 (7.692)	-0.125 (0.305)	-0.267 (0.231)	-0.194 (0.310)	-0.175 (0.432)	0.359 (0.594)	-0.036 (0.420)	-0.312 (0.124)	29.1257 (5.45E-43)
Vegetation_Roads1500	0.216 (0.561)	1.117 (0.926)	0.389 (0.917)	-0.789 (0.461)	2.083 (0.729)	1.959 (0.437)	1.603 (0.553)	0.550 (0.744)	0.454 (0.934)	-0.043 (0.674)	-0.704 (0.462)	-0.896 (0.450)	-0.721 (0.435)	127.3706 (1.96E-139)
Roads_50_cohesion	0.202 (0.740)	-0.144 (1.033)	-0.087 (0.935)	-0.007 (1.133)	-0.190 (0.853)	-0.327 (0.843)	0.322 (0.476)	-0.354 (1.216)	0.047 (0.778)	-0.970 (1.371)	0.442 (0.815)	0.162 (0.748)	-1.881 (1.092)	28.5391 (3.50E-42)
Roads_50_config_mn	0.176 (0.840)	0.075 (1.123)	-0.127 (0.924)	-0.101 (1.028)	-0.214 (0.839)	0.087 (0.823)	0.402 (0.812)	-0.023 (1.307)	-0.076 (0.875)	-0.465 (1.188)	0.044 (0.847)	0.246 (0.767)	-1.603 (0.931)	15.4894 (3.99E-23)
Roads_50_ed	-0.278 (0.456)	-0.294 (0.822)	-0.158 (0.803)	0.430 (1.264)	-0.424 (0.383)	-0.286 (0.573)	-0.503 (0.363)	-0.155 (1.041)	-0.146 (0.808)	-0.238 (0.794)	1.429 (1.240)	-0.147 (0.567)	-0.836 (0.207)	53.3065 (4.60E-73)
Indus_50_cohesion	0.408 (0.698)	-0.639 (1.068)	-0.047 (0.966)	0.169 (0.880)	-0.157 (0.819)	-1.177 (1.722)	-0.126 (0.670)	-0.967 (1.074)	-0.060 (0.985)	0.039 (0.864)	0.455 (0.780)	-0.160 (0.872)	0.308 (0.873)	22.3256 (2.25E-33)
Indus_50_config_mn	0.250 (0.805)	-0.781 (0.753)	-0.437 (0.925)	0.519 (0.889)	-0.711 (0.744)	-1.021 (0.798)	-0.358 (0.850)	-0.991 (0.601)	-0.548 (0.775)	0.300 (1.434)	0.436 (0.793)	0.488 (0.991)	0.866 (0.772)	35.2389 (3.64E-51)
UrbanFabric_50_cohesion	0.084 (0.729)	-0.890 (1.030)	-0.004 (0.882)	0.468 (0.840)	-0.611 (1.145)	-0.639 (1.011)	-0.516 (0.901)	-1.175 (0.995)	-0.035 (0.888)	0.201 (0.852)	0.884 (0.532)	0.191 (0.868)	0.057 (0.972)	36.8281 (3.19E-53)
UrbanFabric_50_config_mn	0.531 (0.914)	-0.494 (0.833)	-0.419 (0.992)	0.073 (0.943)	-0.695 (0.719)	0.064 (0.912)	0.064 (0.800)	-0.741 (0.736)	-0.528 (0.865)	0.301 (1.444)	-0.026 (0.826)	0.043 (0.940)	0.464 (1.182)	19.4731 (3.61E-29)
ImperviousPct	-0.199 (0.551)	-0.494 (0.534)	-0.692 (0.570)	0.524 (1.033)	-0.626 (0.468)	-0.915 (0.466)	-0.602 (0.418)	-0.366 (0.574)	-0.723 (0.551)	-0.489 (0.676)	1.356 (0.831)	-0.013 (0.694)	-0.356 (0.503)	85.8440 (6.62E-106)

Table A.1: Mean value (standard deviation) of each group and cluster with ANOVA results: F statistics (p-value) - (standardised values)

AL = Albania	EE = Estonia	LT = Lithuania	RO = Romania
AT = Austria	EL = Greece	LU = Luxembourg	RS = Serbia
BA = Bosnia and Herzegovina	ES = Spain	LV = Latvia	SE = Sweden
BE = Belgium	FI = Finland	ME = Montenegro	SI = Slovenia
BG = Bulgaria	FR = France	MK = Macedonia	SK = Slovakia
CH = Switzerland	HR = Croatia	MT = Malta	TR = Turkey
CY = Cyprus	HU = Hungary	NL = Netherlands	UK = United Kingdom
CZ = Czech Republic	IE = Ireland	NO = Norway	XK = Kosovo
DE = Germany	IS = Iceland	PL = Poland	
DK = Denmark	IT = Italy	PT = Portugal	

Table A.2: Country codes

A.2 Ranking

Table A.3: List of FUAs and their allocated clusters

Rank	FUA	City	Group	Cluster	Index
1	TR077L1	Manavgat	Forest Cities	F2	5.7013
2	SE005L1	Umea	Forest Cities	F1	3.4834
3	TR015L1	Kastamonu	Forest Cities	F2	3.2908
4	TR062L1	Bolu	Forest Cities	F2	3.2263
5	CY001L1	Lefkosia	Forest Cities	F1	2.7809
6	FI009L1	Jyvaskyla	Forest Cities	F3	2.7523
7	TR057L1	Fethiye	Forest Cities	F2	2.6924
8	RS009L1	Kraljevo	Forest Cities	F1	2.6371
9	AL004L1	Shkoder	Forest Cities	F4	2.5872
10	SE007L1	Linkoping	Forest Cities	F3	2.3599
11	SE505L1	Boras	Forest Cities	F1	2.2981
12	NO005L2	Kristiansand	Forest Cities	F1	2.2720
13	EL007L1	Ioannina	Forest Cities	F2	2.2159
14	BA003L1	Mostar	Forest Cities	F4	2.2039
15	PT014L1	Viseu	Forest Cities	F2	2.1921
16	NO006L2	Tromso	Forest Cities	F4	2.1911
17	TR061L1	Odemis	Forest Cities	F4	2.1768
18	EE002L1	Tartu	Herbaceous Cities	H1	2.1650
19	AL003L1	Elbasan	Forest Cities	F4	2.1378
20	ME001L1	Podgorica	Forest Cities	F4	2.1284
21	LV002L1	Liepaja	Forest Cities	F4	2.1241
22	SE006L1	Uppsala	Forest Cities	F3	2.1120
23	RS006L1	Novi	Forest Cities	F4	2.1048
24	IT051L1	Sanremo	Forest Cities	F1	2.0448
25	IT034L1	Bolzano	Forest Cities	F1	2.0287
26	TR059L1	Tokat	Forest Cities	F2	2.0242
27	PL040L1	Przemysl	Forest Cities	F4	1.9969
28	BA005L1	Zenica	Forest Cities	F4	1.9912
29	IT052L1	Savona	Forest Cities	F1	1.9836
30	FI004L2	Oulu	Forest Cities	F3	1.9189
31	TR051L1	Canakkale	Forest Cities	F4	1.8915
32	TR050L1	Karabuk	Forest Cities	F1	1.8869
33	RS014L1	Valjevo	Forest Cities	F4	1.8475
34	BA002L1	Banja	Forest Cities	F4	1.8458
35	BA001L1	Sarajevo	Forest Cities	F1	1.8232
36	ES011L2	Santiago De Compostela	Forest Cities	F4	1.8160
37	TR026L1	Zonguldak	Forest Cities	F4	1.7847
38	ES529L1	Ourense	Forest Cities	F4	1.7687
39	IT048L1	Cosenza	Forest Cities	F1	1.7658
40	FI008L1	Kuopio	Forest Cities	F3	1.7649
41	BG016L1	Blagoevgrad	Forest Cities	F1	1.7284
42	RS015L1	Vranje	Forest Cities	F3	1.7004
43	SE008L1	Orebro	Forest Cities	F3	1.6877
44	FR205L2	Nice	Forest Cities	F3	1.6587
45	SE502L1	Norrkoping	Forest Cities	F3	1.6562
46	PL045L1	Stalowa Wola	Forest Cities	F4	1.6350
47	XK003L1	Mitrovice	Forest Cities	F4	1.6210
48	FR048L2	Annecy	Forest Cities	F4	1.6019
49	PT005L2	Coimbra	Forest Cities	F4	1.5843
50	XK002L1	Prizren	Forest Cities	F4	1.5804
51	HR006L1	Pula Pola	Forest Cities	F3	1.5695
52	IT014L2	Trento	Forest Cities	F1	1.5578
53	IT024L2	Catanzaro	Forest Cities	F4	1.5280
54	AL005L0	Vlore	Herbaceous Cities	H1	1.5027
55	IT515L2	Terni	Forest Cities	F4	1.4858
56	SI001L1	Ljubljana	Forest Cities	F3	1.4798
57	RS011L0	Cacak	Forest Cities	F4	1.4721
58	IT006L2	Genova	Forest Cities	F1	1.4084
59	RS004L1	Kragujevac	Forest Cities	F3	1.3825

Table A.3: *Continued*

Rank	FUA	City	Group	Cluster	Index
60	IT036L1	La Spezia	Forest Cities	F1	1.3639
61	PL020L2	Nowy Sacz	Forest Cities	F4	1.3528
62	FR007L2	Bordeaux	Forest Cities	F3	1.3435
63	PL033L1	Lubin	Forest Cities	F4	1.3434
64	FI002L2	Tampere	Forest Cities	F3	1.3424
65	AT006L1	Klagenfurt	Forest Cities	F3	1.3361
66	SE501L1	Vasteras	Standard European Cities	E1	1.3183
67	IT023L2	Potenza	Forest Cities	F4	1.2994
68	FR093L2	Brive La Gaillarde	Forest Cities	F4	1.2938
69	AT002L2	Graz	Forest Cities	F4	1.2717
70	XK001L1	Pristina	Forest Cities	F4	1.2716
71	ES533L1	Marbella	Forest Cities	F2	1.2684
72	RS013L1	Leskovac	Forest Cities	F3	1.2538
73	NO002L2	Bergen	Herbaceous Cities	H2	1.2500
74	PL511L2	Walbrzych	Forest Cities	F4	1.2438
75	RO017L1	Tulcea	Herbaceous Cities	H1	1.2336
76	SK003L1	Banska Bystrica	Forest Cities	F1	1.2294
77	CZ007L1	Liberec	Forest Cities	F3	1.2231
78	BA004L1	Tuzla	Standard European Cities	E1	1.2168
79	SI002L1	Maribor	Forest Cities	F4	1.2087
80	TR074L1	Bingol	Herbaceous Cities	H2	1.2042
81	AL001L1	Tirana	Herbaceous Cities	H2	1.1764
82	CZ013L1	Karlovy Vary	Forest Cities	F3	1.1445
83	DE540L2	Siegen	Forest Cities	F3	1.1362
84	HR002L2	Rijeka	Forest Cities	F1	1.1348
85	EL009L1	Kalamata	Herbaceous Cities	H2	1.1315
86	IT045L1	Asti	Forest Cities	F4	1.1291
87	AT003L2	Linz	Forest Cities	F4	1.1158
88	ES510L1	Donostia San Sebastian	Forest Cities	F4	1.1139
89	ES019L2	Bilbao	Forest Cities	F4	1.0966
90	FR045L2	Pau	Forest Cities	F4	1.0892
91	AT005L2	Innsbruck	Forest Cities	F3	1.0888
92	FR505L1	Charleville Mezieres	Forest Cities	F4	1.0821
93	IT060L1	Lecco	Forest Cities	F1	1.0813
94	TR035L1	Osmaniye	Forest Cities	F1	1.0774
95	IT020L2	Campobasso	Forest Cities	F4	1.0689
96	FR025L2	Besancon	Forest Cities	F4	1.0576
97	FI003L2	Turku	Forest Cities	F3	1.0527
98	NO003L2	Trondheim	Forest Cities	F3	1.0471
99	FR026L2	Grenoble	Forest Cities	F3	1.0422
100	PL028L2	Koszalin	Standard European Cities	E1	1.0323
101	LV003L1	Jelgava	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	1.0277
102	FR027L2	Ajaccio	Herbaceous Cities	H2	1.0171
103	SE002L1	Goteborg	Forest Cities	F3	1.0105
104	IT502L2	Prato	Forest Cities	F1	1.0066
105	RO507L1	Baia Mare	Standard European Cities	E1	0.9850
106	TR011L1	Antakya	Forest Cities	F3	0.9625
107	ES022L2	Vigo	Forest Cities	F4	0.9616
108	IT043L1	Varese	Standard European Cities	E1	0.9458
109	PL029L1	Slupsk	Standard European Cities	E1	0.9441
110	ES031L0	Lugo	Forest Cities	F4	0.9150
111	CY501L1	Lemosos	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.9114
112	FR049L2	Lorient	Forest Cities	F4	0.9070
113	PT016L1	Viana Do Castelo	Forest Cities	F4	0.9068
114	SE001L1	Stockholm	Forest Cities	F3	0.8976
115	PT003L1	Braga	Forest Cities	F4	0.8917
116	FR050L2	Montbelliard	Forest Cities	F3	0.8901
117	RS003L1	Nis	Forest Cities	F3	0.8864
118	RS012L1	Krusevac	Forest Cities	F4	0.8759

Table A.3: *Continued*

Rank	FUA	City	Group	Cluster	Index
119	FI007L1	Lahti	Forest Cities	F3	0.8730
120	PL036L1	Ostrowiec Swietokrzyski	Forest Cities	F4	0.8670
121	ES008L2	Las Palmas	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.8655
122	HU016L1	Eger	Standard European Cities	E1	0.8588
123	PT009L1	Faro	Herbaceous Cities	H1	0.8536
124	HU019L1	Sopron	Herbaceous Cities	H1	0.8536
125	IT007L2	Firenze	Standard European Cities	E1	0.8518
126	FI001L2	Helsinki	Forest Cities	F3	0.8376
127	MK003L1	Bitola	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.8230
128	DE059L1	Bayreuth	Forest Cities	F4	0.8221
129	PL014L2	Olsztyn	Forest Cities	F3	0.8204
130	PT008L2	Aveiro	Herbaceous Cities	H1	0.7998
131	AT004L2	Salzburg	Forest Cities	F4	0.7929
132	PL513L2	Wloclawek	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.7917
133	TR048L1	Kutahya	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.7909
134	IT059L1	Biella	Forest Cities	F3	0.7888
135	LT001L1	Vilnius	Forest Cities	F3	0.7870
136	DE066L1	Kempton Allgau	Standard European Cities	E1	0.7869
137	DE077L1	Schweinfurt	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.7857
138	PL031L1	Siedlce	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.7786
139	CZ011L1	Zlin	Standard European Cities	E1	0.7777
140	TR029L1	Kahramanmaras	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.7726
141	SK006L1	Zilina	Forest Cities	F3	0.7726
142	FR043L2	Perpignan	Standard European Cities	E1	0.7644
143	DE027L1	Freiburg Im Breisgau	Forest Cities	F3	0.7611
144	DE069L1	Rosenheim	Forest Cities	F4	0.7603
145	PL011L2	Bialystok	Standard European Cities	E1	0.7582
146	PL019L2	Jelenia Gora	Standard European Cities	E1	0.7564
147	HR001L2	Grad Zagreb	Standard European Cities	E1	0.7544
148	TR079L1	Alasehir	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.7520
149	RO011L1	Piatra Neamt	Standard European Cities	E1	0.7516
150	TR046L1	Rize	Forest Cities	F4	0.7512
151	FR024L2	Limoges	Standard European Cities	E1	0.7498
152	DE044L1	Kaiserslautern	Standard European Cities	E1	0.7393
153	DE060L1	Celle	Forest Cities	F3	0.7366
154	DE045L1	Iserlohn	Forest Cities	F3	0.7324
155	BG008L2	Stara Zagora	Standard European Cities	E1	0.7285
156	PL048L1	Leszno	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.7030
157	PL037L1	Gniezno	Forest Cities	F4	0.7023
158	FR096L2	Albi	Forest Cities	F4	0.6980
159	FR046L2	Bayonne	Forest Cities	F4	0.6978
160	FR065L2	Bourges	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.6881
161	FR077L2	Roanne	Forest Cities	F4	0.6818
162	LU001L1	Luxembourg	Forest Cities	F4	0.6815
163	IE004L1	Galway	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.6746
164	TR024L1	Trabzon	Forest Cities	F4	0.6696
165	ES523L1	Leon	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.6685
166	RO504L1	Brasov	Standard European Cities	E1	0.6679
167	DE051L1	Villingen Schwenningen	Standard European Cities	E1	0.6655
168	ES057L0	Ponferrada	Standard European Cities	E1	0.6640
169	FR073L2	Tarbes	Forest Cities	F4	0.6553
170	IT512L2	Forli	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.6540
171	ES522L1	Cadiz	Herbaceous Cities	H1	0.6536
172	PL051L1	Tczew	Forest Cities	F4	0.6427
173	FR058L2	Chambery	Standard European Cities	E1	0.6258
174	BG001L2	Sofia	Standard European Cities	E1	0.6095
175	DE081L1	Passau	Forest Cities	F4	0.6004
176	FR056L2	Angouleme	Forest Cities	F4	0.5990
177	TR003L1	Antalya	Standard European Cities	E1	0.5932

Table A.3: *Continued*

Rank	FUA	City	Group	Cluster	Index
178	PL017L2	Gorzow Wielkopolski	Standard European Cities	E1	0.5899
179	PL016L2	Opole	Standard European Cities	E1	0.5896
180	HU004L2	Pecs	Standard European Cities	E1	0.5838
181	EL008L1	Kavala	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.5787
182	CZ018L1	Chomutov	Standard European Cities	E1	0.5731
183	IT501L2	Messina	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.5686
184	RO511L1	Ramnicu Valcea	Standard European Cities	E1	0.5684
185	PL026L2	Plock	Standard European Cities	E1	0.5673
186	FR068L2	Vannes	Forest Cities	F4	0.5644
187	ES013L2	Oviedo	Forest Cities	F4	0.5623
188	MK005L1	Prilep	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.5610
189	PL027L2	Kalisz	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	0.5596
190	NO004L2	Stavanger	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.5579
191	HR007L1	Zadar	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.5560
192	BG017L1	Veliko Tarnovo	Forest Cities	F4	0.5497
193	HU018L1	Zalaegerszeg	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.5497
194	UK016L1	Aberdeen	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.5471
195	IT016L2	Perugia	Forest Cities	F4	0.5462
196	PT505L2	Guimaraes	Forest Cities	F4	0.5429
197	BG003L2	Varna	Standard European Cities	E1	0.5379
198	DE537L1	Reutlingen	Standard European Cities	E1	0.5376
199	ES026L2	Coruna A	Forest Cities	F4	0.5371
200	ES034L0	Caceres	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.5345
201	HR005L2	Split	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.5336
202	FR076L2	Belfort	Forest Cities	F3	0.5314
203	DE064L1	Neubrandenburg	Standard European Cities	E1	0.5233
204	FR035L2	Tours	Forest Cities	F4	0.5223
205	ES014L2	Pamplona Iruna	Forest Cities	F4	0.5161
206	PL049L1	Swidnica	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.5161
207	DE053L1	Marburg	Standard European Cities	E1	0.5114
208	MK004L1	Tetovo	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.5114
209	IT025L2	Reggio Di Calabria	Forest Cities	F4	0.5100
210	ES521L1	Huelva	Herbaceous Cities	H1	0.5050
211	UK056L1	Hastings	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.5020
212	DE061L1	Aschaffenburg	Forest Cities	F3	0.4974
213	DE026L1	Trier	Forest Cities	F3	0.4897
214	IT027L1	Cagliari	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.4889
215	LV501L1	Daugavpils	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4875
216	FR067L2	Quimper	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.4706
217	PL008L2	Bydgoszcz	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4674
218	RO009L1	Sibiu	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4661
219	TR036L1	Aksaray	Herbaceous Cities	H1	0.4618
220	CH010L1	Biel Bienne	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4574
221	IT049L1	Carrara	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4473
222	RO513L1	Drobeta Turnu Severin	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4452
223	DE063L1	Plauen	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4450
224	FR020L2	Dijon	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4437
225	FR019L2	Orleans	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4407
226	CZ004L1	Plzen	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4357
227	FR010L2	Montpellier	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4283
228	PL047L1	Lomza	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.4220
229	UK013L2	Newcastle Upon Tyne	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4212
230	CZ008L1	Ceske Budejovice	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4209
231	LT003L1	Panevezys	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4165
232	DE078L1	Greifswald	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4125
233	TR068L1	Salihli	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.4112
234	DE547L2	Jena	Standard European Cities	E1	0.4099
235	DE071L1	Stralsund	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.3963
236	PL024L2	Czestochowa	Standard European Cities	E1	0.3883

Table A.3: *Continued*

Rank	FUA	City	Group	Cluster	Index
237	HR003L2	Slavonski Brod	Forest Cities	F4	0.3834
238	ES044L0	Pontevedra	Forest Cities	F4	0.3694
239	BG018L1	Vratsa	Standard European Cities	E1	0.3650
240	BG004L2	Burgas	Standard European Cities	E1	0.3648
241	ES025L2	Santa Cruz De Tenerife	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.3572
242	ES532L1	Algeciras	Forest Cities	F3	0.3544
243	FR099L2	Frejus	Standard European Cities	E1	0.3538
244	TR027L1	Eskisehir	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.3465
245	ES015L2	Santander	Forest Cities	F4	0.3381
246	BG009L1	Sliven	Standard European Cities	E1	0.3372
247	HR004L2	Osijek	Herbaceous Cities	H1	0.3351
248	FR074L2	Compiegne	Standard European Cities	E1	0.3327
249	TR044L1	Karaman	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.3311
250	CZ003L1	Ostrava	Standard European Cities	E1	0.3288
251	TR073L1	Cankiri	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.3275
252	ES023L2	Gijon	Forest Cities	F4	0.3265
253	RO007L1	Bacau	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.3261
254	PT006L2	Setubal	Herbaceous Cities	H1	0.3227
255	RO016L1	Targu Jiu	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.3171
256	DE020L1	Wiesbaden	Forest Cities	F3	0.3137
257	IT047L1	Massa	Standard European Cities	E1	0.3093
258	EL003L1	Patra	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.3067
259	DE067L1	Landshut	Standard European Cities	E1	0.3015
260	PL514L2	Tarnow	Standard European Cities	E1	0.3013
261	BG002L2	Plovdiv	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2966
262	TR033L1	Isparta	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.2965
263	CZ002L1	Brno	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2946
264	DE001L1	Berlin	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2928
265	PL022L2	Konin	Forest Cities	F4	0.2922
266	RO510L1	Botosani	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.2880
267	DE539L1	Cottbus	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2840
268	TR042L1	Usak	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.2776
269	PL032L1	Piotrkow Trybunalski	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2757
270	FR086L2	Evreux	Forest Cities	F4	0.2710
271	FR506L1	Colmar	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2701
272	CZ014L1	Jihlava	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2667
273	TR022L1	Samsun	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2624
274	DE009L2	Dresden	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2621
275	ES012L2	Vitoria Gasteiz	Forest Cities	F4	0.2582
276	SK008L1	Trencin	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2502
277	FR032L2	Toulon	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	0.2438
278	SK005L1	Presov	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2376
279	FR011L2	Saint Etienne	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2365
280	DE062L1	Bamberg	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2327
281	HU006L2	Szeged	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2259
282	PL034L1	Pila	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	0.2253
283	ES010L2	Palma De Mallorca	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.2156
284	FR203L2	Marseille	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2151
285	HU005L2	Debrecen	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2122
286	PL001L2	Warszawa	Standard European Cities	E1	0.2038
287	EL006L1	Volos	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.2011
288	FR021L2	Poitiers	Standard European Cities	E1	0.1995
289	FR084L2	Creil	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.1972
290	DE072L1	Friedrichshafen	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.1960
291	NL014L2	Apeldoorn	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	0.1912
292	MK001L1	Skopje	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.1909
293	FR090L2	Chateauroux	Standard European Cities	E1	0.1865
294	FR059L2	Chalon Sur Saone	Standard European Cities	E1	0.1811
295	PL007L2	Szczecin	Standard European Cities	E1	0.1755

Table A.3: *Continued*

Rank	FUA	City	Group	Cluster	Index
296	PL044L1	Glogow	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.1658
297	PL013L2	Torun	Standard European Cities	E1	0.1657
298	IT055L1	Viareggio	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	0.1587
299	IT040L1	Como	Standard European Cities	E1	0.1517
300	FR022L2	Clermont Ferrand	Standard European Cities	E1	0.1514
301	TR064L1	Mus	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.1502
302	IE005L1	Waterford	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.1379
303	TR028L1	Sanliurfa	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.1350
304	CZ016L1	Most	Standard European Cities	E1	0.1251
305	ES043L0	Ferrol	Forest Cities	F4	0.1202
306	IE002L1	Cork	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	0.1127
307	DE524L2	Wurzburg	Standard European Cities	E1	0.1015
308	UK517L1	Swansea	Standard European Cities	E1	0.0971
309	RO014L1	Alba Iulia	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.0959
310	RO018L1	Targoviste	Standard European Cities	E1	0.0862
311	FR051L2	Troyes	Standard European Cities	E1	0.0782
312	IT503L2	Parma	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.0781
313	EL002L1	Thessaloniki	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.0763
314	RS008L1	Zrenjanin	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.0726
315	HU008L2	Kecskemet	Standard European Cities	E1	0.0638
316	DE534L1	Ingolstadt	Standard European Cities	E1	0.0609
317	CZ005L1	Usti Nad Labem	Standard European Cities	E1	0.0602
318	DE533L1	Pforzheim	Standard European Cities	E1	0.0592
319	UK575L0	Carlisle	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	0.0559
320	FR036L2	Angers	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	0.0553
321	IT506L2	Ravenna	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	0.0548
322	IT050L1	Benevento	Forest Cities	F4	0.0542
323	IS001L1	Reykjavik	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.0538
324	IE003L1	Limerick	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	0.0508
325	TR041L1	Nigde	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.0445
326	RO512L1	Suceava	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.0417
327	IT001L2	Roma	Standard European Cities	E1	0.0392
328	DE031L1	Schwerin	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	0.0388
329	AT001L2	Wien	Standard European Cities	E1	0.0336
330	IT005L2	Palermo	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.0316
331	IT032L2	Salerno	Standard European Cities	E1	0.0269
332	PT002L2	Porto	Forest Cities	F4	0.0239
333	FR016L2	Nancy	Standard European Cities	E1	0.0188
334	DE043L2	Rostock	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	0.0183
335	PT001L2	Lisboa	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	0.0174
336	IT009L1	Bologna	Standard European Cities	E1	0.0170
337	RO002L1	Cluj Napoca	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.0152
338	DE028L1	Regensburg	Standard European Cities	E1	0.0143
339	RO022L1	Bistrita	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	0.0116
340	TR031L1	Sivas	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.0113
341	FR069L2	Cherbourg	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	0.0059
342	IT026L2	Sassari	Herbaceous Cities	H2	0.0022
343	CZ006L1	Olomouc	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.0017
344	TR006L1	Denizli	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.0083
345	ES501L1	Granada	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.0151
346	PL030L1	Jastrzebie Zdroj	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.0268
347	PL517L2	Grudziadz	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.0285
348	CH003L1	Basel	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.0290
349	PL508L1	Rybnik	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.0302
350	RO509L1	Satu Mare	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.0318
351	ES041L0	Palencia	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.0323
352	CH009L1	Lugano	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.0345
353	DE014L1	Nurnberg	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.0372
354	DE050L1	Tubingen	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.0438

Table A.3: *Continued*

Rank	FUA	City	Group	Cluster	Index
355	TR076L1	Polatli	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.0571
356	UK015L0	Derry	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.0579
357	DE021L1	Gottingen	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.0725
358	DE054L1	Konstanz	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.0734
359	ES059L0	Zamora	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.0747
360	LT002L1	Kaunas	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.0783
361	ES006L2	Malaga	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.0784
362	ES508L1	Jerez De La Frontera	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.0805
363	BE007L2	Namur	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.0852
364	EL001L1	Athina	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.0858
365	IT053L1	Vigevano	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.0860
366	RS016L1	Smederevo	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.0878
367	CH004L1	Bern	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.0925
368	FR215L2	Rouen	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.0934
369	PL512L2	Elblag	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.0950
370	DK004L1	Aalborg	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.0968
371	HU013L1	Veszprem	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.0987
372	IT505L2	Reggio Nell Emilia	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.1000
373	TR002L1	Adana	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1006
374	FR063L2	Beziers	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1035
375	ES073L0	Elda	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.1054
376	TR063L1	Bandirma	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.1056
377	TR039L1	Afyonkarahisar	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.1099
378	CZ001L1	Praha	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1119
379	FR006L2	Strasbourg	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1236
380	DK003L1	Odense	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.1239
381	FR013L2	Rennes	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1244
382	PL003L2	Krakow	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1245
383	PL010L2	Katowice	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1323
384	PL005L2	Poznan	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.1327
385	CH002L1	Geneve	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.1359
386	UK539L1	Bournemouth	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.1433
387	IE001L1	Dublin	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.1471
388	PL009L2	Lublin	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1471
389	RO020L1	Barlad	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.1500
390	NL018L1	Hilversum	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.1533
391	FR214L1	Valence	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1535
392	HU012L1	Tatabanya	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1620
393	PL506L2	Bielsko Biala	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1686
394	TR037L1	Aydin	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1698
395	DE057L1	Giessen	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1713
396	UK041L0	Ashford	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.1755
397	ES514L1	Almeria	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.1780
398	RO005L1	Braila	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.1817
399	HU002L2	Miskolc	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1838
400	CZ010L1	Pardubice	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1857
401	NL005L2	Eindhoven	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.1926
402	IT041L1	Pisa	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.1927
403	TR032L1	Elazig	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.1942
404	DE007L1	Stuttgart	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1948
405	DE527L1	Bremerhaven	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.1955
406	HU007L2	Gyor	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.1967
407	DE005L1	Frankfurt Am Main	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.2072
408	DE058L1	Luneburg	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.2086
409	UK027L1	Stoke On Trent	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.2090
410	IT513L2	Latina	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.2124
411	IT035L1	Udine	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.2180
412	CH006L1	Winterthur	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.2232
413	DE033L2	Augsburg	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.2276

Table A.3: *Continued*

Rank	FUA	City	Group	Cluster	Index
414	BG011L1	Shumen	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.2289
415	ES515L1	Burgos	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.2361
416	ES070L0	Irun	Forest Cities	F4	-0.2380
417	UK009L1	Cardiff	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.2435
418	DE012L1	Bremen	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.2452
419	RS005L1	Subotica	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.2458
420	HU015L1	Kaposvar	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.2495
421	FR018L2	Reims	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.2621
422	EL005L1	Larisa	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.2662
423	DE040L1	Saarbrücken	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.2671
424	DK002L1	Århus	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.2684
425	NL512L3	Ede	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.2686
426	DE522L1	Heidelberg	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.2721
427	DE034L1	Bonn	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.2735
428	DE003L2	München	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.2915
429	UK557L2	Blackburn With Darwen	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.2952
430	TR055L1	Adiyaman	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.2971
431	FR040L2	Mulhouse	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.2997
432	LT004L0	Alytus	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.3037
433	IT054L1	Matera	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3082
434	HU010L1	Szombathely	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.3090
435	FR044L2	Nîmes	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3133
436	DE535L1	Gera	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3168
437	DE008L2	Leipzig	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3246
438	BG007L2	Vidin	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.3312
439	CH001L1	Zürich	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.3400
440	FR017L2	Metz	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3408
441	DE529L1	Heilbronn	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3415
442	FR304L1	Melun	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3426
443	ES007L2	Murcia	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3440
444	BG006L2	Ruse	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3459
445	UK569L1	Ipswich	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.3476
446	DE523L1	Paderborn	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3503
447	FR082L2	Beauvais	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3519
448	FR023L2	Caen	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.3520
449	FR061L2	Niort	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3572
450	DE032L1	Erfurt	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3574
451	SK001L1	Bratislava	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3711
452	DE035L1	Karlsruhe	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3737
453	UK033L0	Guildford	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.3759
454	FR066L2	Saint Brieuc	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.3809
455	EL004L1	Irakleio	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.3819
456	CH008L1	Luzern	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.3837
457	ES017L2	Badajoz	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.3842
458	CH007L1	St Gallen	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.3869
459	PL004L2	Wrocław	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.3965
460	ES009L2	Valladolid	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.3972
461	NL008L2	Enschede	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.3992
462	TR001L1	Ankara	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.4001
463	BG013L1	Yambol	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.4021
464	FR037L2	Brest	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.4096
465	RO012L1	Calarasi	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.4141
466	UK551L0	Falkirk	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.4173
467	RO013L1	Giurgiu	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.4193
468	FR053L2	La Rochelle	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.4195
469	DE513L1	Kassel	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.4222
470	UK018L2	Exeter	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.4300
471	FR034L2	Valenciennes	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.4327
472	DE013L1	Hannover	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.4358

Table A.3: *Continued*

Rank	FUA	City	Group	Cluster	Index
473	SK004L1	Nitra	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.4409
474	HU009L2	Szekesfehervar	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.4454
475	TR018L1	Konya	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.4459
476	UK566L1	Norwich	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.4482
477	TR004L1	Balikesir	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.4545
478	RO506L1	Pitesti	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.4574
479	FR003L2	Lyon	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.4638
480	ES005L2	Zaragoza	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.4646
481	RS002L1	Novi	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.4685
482	DE039L1	Kiel	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.4694
483	IT004L2	Torino	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.4720
484	HU003L2	Nyiregyhaza	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.4722
485	UK554L0	Maidstone	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.4764
486	IT021L2	Caserta	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.4779
487	IT507L2	Ferrara	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.4823
488	DE084L1	Mannheim Ludwigshafen	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.4827
489	UK548L0	Basingstoke And Deane	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.4840
490	NL513L2	Deventer	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.4922
491	UK004L1	Glasgow	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.4951
492	ES002L2	Barcelona	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.4956
493	DE042L1	Koblenz	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.5012
494	UK007L1	Edinburgh	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.5021
495	FR057L2	Boulogne Sur Mer	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.5085
496	IT037L1	Lecce	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.5126
497	IT039L1	Pesaro	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.5190
498	RO019L1	Slatina	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.5219
499	ES048L0	Guadalajara	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.5327
500	ES033L0	Girona	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.5339
501	UK038L0	Waveney	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.5347
502	NL009L2	Arnhem	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.5372
503	UK051L0	Great Yarmouth	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.5435
504	IT504L2	Livorno	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.5439
505	BE004L2	Charleroi	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.5454
506	ES050L0	Manresa	Forest Cities	F4	-0.5474
507	ES519L1	Albacete	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.5488
508	NL013L2	Nijmegen	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.5542
509	FR004L2	Toulouse	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.5553
510	DE520L1	Oldenburg Oldenburg	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.5600
511	BE008L1	Leuven	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.5611
512	SK007L1	Trnava	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.5640
513	BE005L2	Liege	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.5658
514	UK054L0	Cannock Chase	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.5716
515	DE002L1	Hamburg	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.5742
516	EE003L0	Narva	Herbaceous Cities	H1	-0.5749
517	DE504L1	Munster	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.5838
518	UK043L0	East Staffordshire	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.5851
519	DE030L1	Weimar	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.5941
520	IT058L1	Pordenone	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.5973
521	DE029L0	Frankfurt Oder	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.5997
522	DE507L1	Aachen	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.5999
523	ES046L0	Gandia	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.6111
524	DE083L1	Braunschweig Salzgitter Wolfsburg	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.6176
525	ES016L2	Toledo	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.6178
526	ES506L1	Cartagena	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.6273
527	BG005L1	Pleven	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.6283
528	FR324L1	Martigues	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.6315
529	RO508L1	Buzau	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.6332
530	DE025L1	Darmstadt	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.6350
531	FR001L1	Paris	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.6365

Table A.3: *Continued*

Rank	FUA	City	Group	Cluster	Index
532	BG010L1	Dobrich	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.6438
533	PL516L2	Legnica	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.6556
534	TR019L1	Malatya	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.6560
535	IT012L2	Verona	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.6569
536	TR010L1	Gaziantep	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.6596
537	RO008L1	Arad	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.6640
538	HU001L2	Budapest	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.6645
539	ES520L1	Castellon De La Plana	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.6668
540	TR016L1	Kayseri	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.6674
541	DE542L1	Hildesheim	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.6719
542	BG014L1	Haskovo	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.6731
543	LT502L0	Siauliai	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.6748
544	ES040L0	Talavera De La Reina	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.6773
545	HU011L1	Szolnok	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.6776
546	BG015L1	Pazardzhik	Anthropogenic Cities	A3	-0.6830
547	ES018L2	Logrono	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.6859
548	IT031L2	Foggia	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.7011
549	CZ009L1	Hradec Kralove	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.7087
550	IT046L1	Pavia	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.7163
551	ES037L0	Puerto De Santa Maria El	Herbaceous Cities	H1	-0.7177
552	DE544L1	Zwickau	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.7188
553	NL020L1	Roosendaal	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.7228
554	NL514L2	Alkmaar	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.7269
555	IT017L2	Ancona	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.7326
556	RO006L1	Oradea	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.7345
557	SE003L1	Malmo	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.7365
558	UK568L2	Cheshire West And Chester	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.7390
559	DE530L0	Remscheid	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.7398
560	NL006L2	Tilburg	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.7484
561	BE009L1	Mons	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.7524
562	DE048L1	Wilhelmshaven	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.7582
563	FR039L1	Avignon	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.7666
564	BE006L2	Brugge	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.7697
565	FR062L2	Calais	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.7704
566	NL032L1	Middelburg	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.7809
567	UK549L0	Bedford	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.7816
568	UK005L0	Bradford	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.7939
569	DE516L0	Solingen	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.8039
570	UK546L0	Colchester	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8040
571	HU014L1	Bekescsaba	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8106
572	DK001L2	Kobenhavn	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.8141
573	NL503L2	S Hertogenbosch	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.8158
574	NL015L2	Leeuwarden	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8159
575	PL038L1	Stargard Szczecinski	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8208
576	IT056L1	Acireale	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8258
577	FR104L2	Chalons En Champagne	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8266
578	UK506L0	Doncaster	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8273
579	UK519L0	Barnsley	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8326
580	NL012L2	Breda	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.8333
581	IT029L2	Brescia	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.8334
582	IT508L2	Rimini	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8377
583	UK019L2	Lincoln	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8403
584	DE037L1	Mainz	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.8404
585	ES053L0	Ciudad Real	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.8413
586	IT509L2	Siracusa	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8510
587	BE001L2	Bruxelles Brussel	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.8523
588	RO001L1	Bucuresti	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8572
589	NL007L2	Groningen	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8618
590	UK553L2	Blackpool	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8646

Table A.3: *Continued*

Rank	FUA	City	Group	Cluster	Index
591	ES527L1	Jaen	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8659
592	ES528L1	Lleida	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8670
593	ES505L1	Elche Elx	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8830
594	DE038L1	Ruhrgebiet	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.8837
595	RO004L1	Craiova	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8839
596	IT011L2	Venezia	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8867
597	IT514L2	Vicenza	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.8957
598	UK558L1	Newport	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.8999
599	CH005L1	Lausanne	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.9158
600	ES055L0	Melilla	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.9196
601	IT033L1	Piacenza	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.9218
602	ES001L2	Madrid	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.9321
603	DE004L1	Koln	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.9328
604	ES020L2	Cordoba	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-0.9396
605	FR012L2	Le Havre	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.9399
606	DE510L1	Lubeck	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-0.9451
607	UK001L2	London	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.9598
608	ES028L1	Reus	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.9693
609	DE018L1	Halle An Der Saale	Standard European Cities	E1	-0.9893
610	IT003L2	Napoli	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.9925
611	NL002L2	Amsterdam	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.9927
612	ES054L0	Benidorm	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-0.9940
613	IT022L2	Taranto	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.0005
614	BE002L2	Antwerpen	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.0043
615	UK501L0	Kirklees	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.0052
616	UK010L2	Sheffield	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.0067
617	ES003L2	Valencia	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-1.0274
618	ES004L2	Sevilla	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.0381
619	LV001L0	Riga	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.0452
620	UK026L1	Kingston Upon Hull	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.0723
621	RO505L1	Ploiesti	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.0907
622	UK046L0	Mansfield	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.1005
623	TR008L1	Edirne	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.1018
624	UK029L1	Nottingham	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.1034
625	UK008L2	Manchester	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.1110
626	NL004L2	Utrecht	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.1116
627	NL010L2	Heerlen	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.1148
628	TR007L1	Diyarbakir	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.1231
629	FR042L2	Dunkerque	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.1277
630	IT511L2	Bergamo	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.1390
631	TR025L1	Van	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.1416
632	IT010L2	Catania	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.1707
633	TR066L1	Nizip	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.1750
634	ES516L1	Salamanca	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.1794
635	RO503L1	Galati	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.1795
636	TR070L1	Kiziltepe	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.1799
637	NL003L2	Rotterdam	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.1803
638	UK011L2	Bristol	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.2157
639	UK014L1	Leicester	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.2164
640	ES021L2	Alicante Alacant	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-1.2362
641	DE546L0	Wuppertal	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.2501
642	UK012L1	Belfast	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.2542
643	DE011L1	Dusseldorf	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.2582
644	BE003L2	Gent	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.2801
645	IT008L2	Bari	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.2818
646	FR009L2	Lille	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.2827
647	FR209L2	Douai	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.2883
648	IT013L2	Cremona	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.3046
649	UK520L1	Southampton	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.3166

Table A.3: *Continued*

Rank	FUA	City	Group	Cluster	Index
650	ES525L1	Tarragona	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.3333
651	IT030L2	Modena	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.3568
652	TR009L1	Erzurum	Herbaceous Cities	H2	-1.3627
653	IT516L2	Novara	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.3754
654	UK525L0	Milton Keynes	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.4061
655	NL505L1	Maastricht	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.4139
656	NL001L2	S Gravenhage	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.4360
657	UK515L1	Brighton And Hove	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.4532
658	UK003L1	Leeds	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.4921
659	IT002L2	Milano	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.4933
660	NL504L2	Amersfoort	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.5077
661	HU017L1	Dunaujvaros	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.5086
662	RO501L1	Constanta	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.5118
663	FR207L2	Lens Lievin	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.5194
664	UK045L0	Worthing	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.5243
665	UK559L1	Middlesbrough	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.5353
666	UK545L0	Peterborough	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.5711
667	TR030L1	Batman	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.5744
668	UK006L2	Liverpool	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.5843
669	TR014L1	Kars	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.5856
670	UK025L2	Coventry	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.6192
671	NL029L1	Katwijk	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.6307
672	UK562L2	Preston	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.6377
673	DE055L0	Neumunster	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.6461
674	DE036L0	Monchengladbach	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.6743
675	IT019L2	Pescara	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.6834
676	NL016L1	Sittard Geleen	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.6884
677	UK023L1	Portsmouth	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.7187
678	IT042L1	Treviso	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.7479
679	ES035L0	Torreveja	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.7562
680	LT501L0	Klaipeda	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.7702
681	UK053L0	Hartlepool	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.9081
682	UK531L0	Warrington	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.9167
683	UK535L0	Swindon	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-1.9358
684	BE010L1	Kortrijk	Anthropogenic Cities	A2	-1.9393
685	IT044L1	Busto Arsizio	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-2.0519
686	FR208L1	Henin Carvin	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-2.0695
687	NL026L1	Alphen Aan Den Rijn	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-2.2190
688	UK532L0	Luton	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-2.5715
689	NL507L2	Leiden	Anthropogenic Cities	A1	-2.7338

B. Chapter 4

B.1 General

Figure B.1: Study area - location of the FUAs studied and ecological zones

	Sarajevo	Newcastle	Faro	Tilburg
SNAP1	16,366.072	4,288.384	0.000	0.000
SNAP2	3,047.324	64,958.056	191.347	9,043.385
SNAP34	267.434	323,443.781	277,247.477	575,129.000
SNAP5	0.000	12.360	0.072	0.015
SNAP6	0.000	120.427	0.436	58.942
SNAP71	18.526	1,522.540	10.539	403.956
SNAP72	34.458	2,379.727	35.349	663.217
SNAP73	0.000	21.161	0.529	31.617
SNAP8	0.000	35,857.782	87,497.010	0.037
SNAP10	252.636	8,047.786	918.165	120.376
Total	19,986.450	440,652.004	365,900.924	585,450.588

Table B.1: Annual emissions in t CO₂

Figure B.2: 2D Gaussian isotropic dispersion matrices

B.2 Dispersion

B.2.1 Simulating the spatial dispersion

CO₂ molecules transportation - like that of any other gas or particule - is driven by meteorologic and physical processes. When considering large-scale systems (global to regional), the main drivers are winds, temperatures, vertical profiles, clouds and relative humidity (Jacobson, 2012). On the other side, at local scales, such as urban areas, molecules transportation is mainly impacted by fluctuations within the boundary layer (up to 500-3,000 m from the ground level) with ground temperatures, local winds and soil moisture (Jacobson, 2012). For simplicity, we mimic steady-state wind conditions using a 2D Gaussian isotropic dispersion matrix (circular and symmetric). According to Stull (2020), "theoretical steady-state winds can be found based on only the remaining larger-magnitude forces". In other words, a steady-state corresponds to the very low residual wind speed after accounting for: the pressure gradient force, the apparent Coriolis force (due to the Earth rotation), the turbulent drag and the apparent centrifugal force (for more details, see Jacobson, 2012, Stull, 2020).

We use three different parametric values $\sigma = \{1; 2; 3\}$ for the weight matrices (see Figure B.2). These matrices are used to simulate the spatial dispersion of the CO₂ molecules emitted from each cell. After 10 iterations, the dispersion maps are then used respectively for the calculation of the balances called balance 1 (B1), balance 2 (B2) and balance 3 (B3), as opposed to balance 0 (B0), for which no spatial dispersion is simulated. Spatial dispersion is applied using moving averages and we consider the absence of any dominant strong wind (Gaussian isotropic dispersion). The weight matrices have a dimension of 9×9 cells of 1 ha. For $\sigma = 3$, the CO₂ molecules spread and mix faster but not further than for $\sigma = 1$. Hence, the CO₂ concentration becomes homogeneous faster with a higher σ . This spatial modelling of the dispersion of CO₂ molecules, similar to that of a steady state, is applied to the daily emission data.

The spatio-temporal approach

This approach accounts for (i) the temporal distribution of annual emissions towards monthly and daily emissions, (ii) the temporal distribution of annual sequestration towards monthly and daily sequestration and (iii) the spatial dispersion of emissions. The seasonality in CO₂ emissions and sequestration is taken into consideration by applying a spatial dispersion to one typical day of each month of the year for each urban area. For a weekday, we simulate the spatial dispersion of the emitted CO₂ molecules, from the cells where they are emitted to the surrounding locations. Then, the molecules reaching a cell with a sequestration capacity will be removed according to the capacity of the

corresponding cell. In this approach, we consider the study area as a closed system: only CO₂ molecules emitted within the system can be sequestered. The balance here corresponds to the difference between the CO₂ emissions after spatial dispersion and removal by vegetation. It is important to note that the balance cannot be negative. The relative sequestration corresponds to the amount of anthropogenic emissions the urban forest can actually sequester after spatial dispersion, over a given time period. When expressed in absolute terms, values are in t CO₂ per day. When expressed in relative terms, they correspond to the percentage of emissions which has been sequestered. Carbon balance metrics are now more realistic and meaningful for urban scale studies in a steady-state context.

B.3 Daily sequestration per ha**BA001L1 – Mean sequestration per day (month specific)
in t CO₂ per ha**

Figure B.3: Daily sequestration capacity per ha in Sarajevo (average day of each month)

Figure B.4: Daily sequestration capacity per ha in Newcastle (average day of each month)

Figure B.5: Daily sequestration capacity per ha in Faro (average day of each month)

**NL006L2 – Mean sequestration per day (month specific)
in t CO2 per ha**

Figure B.6: Daily sequestration capacity per ha in Tilburg (average day of each month)

B.4 Daily emissions per ha

Figure B.7: Daily emissions per ha in Sarajevo (average Monday of each month)

Figure B.8: Daily emissions per ha in Newcastle (average Monday of each month)

Figure B.9: Daily emissions potential per ha in Faro (average Monday of each month)

Figure B.10: Daily emissions potential per ha in Tilburg (average Monday of each month)

B.5 Vegetation characteristicsFigure B.11: Dominant leaf type (DLT) per cell of $20 \times 20 \text{ m}^2$

Figure B.12: Tree cover density (TCD) in percentage per cell of 20 × 20 m²

C. Chapter 5

C.1 Figures

Figure C.1: Lecco. **a.** Land use distribution. **b.** Daily CO₂ removal in percentage. Black curve for B0, red curve for B1, green curve for B2 and Blue curve for B3.

Figure C.2: Distributions for each dispersion parameter (σ or sd). **a.** Absolute daily emissions sequestered per FUA (t CO₂ per day). **b.** Relative daily CO₂ emissions sequestered per FUA (%).

Figure C.3: Scatterplot of annual emissions from SNAP1 VS carbon balance after dispersion ($\sigma = 3$) for each month

Figure C.4: Example of CO₂ molecules dispersion for $\sigma = 1$ (Lecco)

Figure C.5: Example of CO₂ molecules dispersion for $\sigma = 3$ (Lecco).

C.2 Tables

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>		
	log(annualE) (1)	log(annualE) ≤10 (2)	log(annualE) >10 (3)
log(pop)	1.639*** (0.139)	1.357*** (0.210)	0.884*** (0.095)
Constant	-7.661*** (1.748)	-8.131*** (2.512)	2.812** (1.212)
Observations	368	68	300
R ²	0.276	0.387	0.224
Adjusted R ²	0.274	0.378	0.222
Residual Std. Error	2.400 (df = 366)	0.813 (df = 66)	1.515 (df = 298)
F Statistic	139.669*** (df = 1; 366)	41.754*** (df = 1; 66)	86.181*** (df = 1; 298)
<i>Note:</i>	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01		

Table C.1: Linear regressions - Log emissions VS Log population size

D. Bibliography

Bibliography

- H. Akbari, H. Damon Matthews, and D. Seto. The long-term effect of increasing the albedo of urban areas. *Environmental Research Letters*, 7(2), 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/7/2/024004>.
- M. Alberti. The Effects of Urban Patterns on Ecosystem Function. *International Regional Science Review*, 28(2):168–192, 2005. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0160017605275160>.
- M. Alberti. The Urban Ecosystem. In M. Alberti, editor, *Advances in Urban Ecology. Integrating Humans and Ecological Processes in Urban Ecosystems*, pages 1–26. Springer, New York, 2008.
- D. Arribas-Bel, P. Nijkamp, and H. Scholten. Multidimensional urban sprawl in Europe: A self-organizing map approach. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 35(4): 263–275, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2010.10.002>.
- V. Avitabile and A. Camia. An assessment of forest biomass maps in Europe using harmonized national statistics and inventory plots. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 409:489–498, 2018. ISSN 03781127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2017.11.047>.
- D. D. Baldocchi, E. Falge, L. Gu, R. Olson, D. Hollinger, S. Running, P. Anthoni, C. Bernhofer, K. Davis, R. Evans, J. Fuentes, A. Goldstein, G. Katul, B. Law, X. Lee, Y. Malhi, T. Meyers, W. Munger, W. Oechel, K. T. U. Paw, K. Pilegaard, H. P. Schmid, R. Valentini, S. Verma, T. Vesala, K. B. Wilson, and S. Wofsy. FLUXNET : A New Tool to Study the Temporal and Spatial Variability of Ecosystem-Scale Carbon Dioxide , Water Vapor , and Energy Flux Densities. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 82(11):2415–2434, 2001. ISSN 0003-0007. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477\(2001\)082<2415:FANTTS>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477(2001)082<2415:FANTTS>2.3.CO;2).
- T. Ballinger, J. Overland, M. Wang, U. Bhatt, E. Hanna, I. Hanssen-Bauer, S. J. Kim, R. Thoman, and J. Walsh. Surface Air Temperature. *NOAA Arctic Report Card 2020*, pages 1–7, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.25923/gcw8-2z06>.

- J. Barredo, J. San Miguel, G. Caudullo, and L. Busetto. A European map of living biomass and carbon stock. Executive report. page 12, 2012. ISSN 1831-9424. <https://doi.org/10.2788/780>.
- S. Bell, D. Blom, M. Rautamäki, A. Simson, and A. I. Olsen. Urban Forests and Trees. In C. Konijnendijk, K. Nilsson, T. Randrup, and J. Schipperijn, editors, *Urban Forests and Trees: A Reference Book*. Springer, Berlin, 2005. https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-27684-X_7.
- P. Bolund and S. Hunhammar. Ecosystem services in urban areas. *Ecological Economics*, 29(2):293–301, 1999. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-8009\(99\)00013-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-8009(99)00013-0).
- M. Boura and G. Caruso. Land cover, landscape metrics and typology of European cities for Urban Forest Ecosystem Services (UFES) evaluation. *Zenodo*, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4301952>.
- M. Boura and G. Caruso. High Resolution Urban Carbon Balance (UCB) Model (data set). *Zenodo*, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5499979>.
- M. Boura and G. Caruso. Urban Forests as Regulating Ecosystems: Types and Ranking of European Cities. *Ecosystem Services*, under review.
- D. Bowler, L. Buyung-Ali, T. Knight, and A. Pullin. A systematic review of evidence for the added benefits to health of exposure to natural environments. *BMC Public Health*, 10(1):456, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-10-456>.
- M. Breheny. The compact city and transport energy consumption. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 20(1):81–101, 1995.
- S. Brown, E. Miltner, and C. Cogger. Carbon Sequestration Potential in Urban Soils. In R. Lal and B. Augustin, editors, *Carbon Sequestration in Urban Ecosystems*, pages 173–196. Springer, Dordrecht, 2012. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-2366-5_9.
- R. Bruegmann. Sprawl across the centuries. In *Sprawl: A Compact History*. University of Chicago Press, 2005. URL <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/unilu-ebooks/detail.action?docID=408469>.
- R. Brunet. *Les villes européennes. Rapport pour la DATAR, Délégation à l'Aménagement du Territoire et à l'Action Régionale*. La Documentation Française, Paris, 1989.
- B. Burkhard, F. Kroll, S. Nedkov, and F. Müller. Mapping ecosystem service supply, demand and budgets. *Ecological Indicators*, 21:17–29, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2011.06.019>.
- B. Burkhard, M. Kandziora, Y. Hou, and F. Müller. Ecosystem service potentials, flows and demands-concepts for spatial localisation, indication and quantification. *Landscape Online*, 34(1):1–32, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.3097/L0.201434>.
- G. Caruso, J. Cavailhès, D. Peeters, I. Thomas, P. Frankhauser, and G. Vuidel. Greener and larger neighbourhoods make cities more sustainable! A 2D urban economics perspective. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 54:82–94, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2015.06.002>.
- J. Chang, P. Ciais, N. Viovy, N. Vuichard, B. Sultan, and J.-F. Soussana. The greenhouse gas balance of European grasslands. *Global Change Biology*, 21(10):3748–3761, oct 2015. ISSN 13541013. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12998>. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/gcb.12998>.

- G. Churkina. Modeling the carbon cycle of urban systems. *Ecological Modelling*, 216(2): 107–113, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2008.03.006>.
- G. Churkina. Carbon Cycle of Urban Ecosystems. In R. Lal and B. Augustin, editors, *Carbon Sequestration in Urban Ecosystems*, chapter 16, pages 315–330. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, 2012. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-2366-5_16.
- City of Helsinki. *From City to City-Region City of Helsinki. City of Helsinki, Strategic Spatial Plan*. Helsinki City Planning Department publications, prima oy edition, 2009.
- R. Costanza. Ecosystem services: Multiple classification systems are needed. *Biological Conservation*, 141(2):350–352, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2007.12.020>.
- M. Crippa, E. Solazzo, G. Huang, D. Guizzardi, E. Koffi, M. Muntean, C. Schieberle, R. Friedrich, and G. Janssens-Maenhout. High resolution temporal profiles in the Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR), figshare (data set), 2019.
- M. Crippa, E. Solazzo, G. Huang, D. Guizzardi, E. Koffi, M. Muntean, C. Schieberle, R. Friedrich, and G. Janssens-Maenhout. High resolution temporal profiles in the Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research. *Scientific Data*, 7(1):1–17, 2020. ISSN 20524463. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0462-2>.
- G. Daily. Introduction: What are Ecosystem Services. In G. Daily, editor, *Nature's services: Societal dependence on natural ecosystems*. Island Press, Washington DC, 1997.
- B. Danley and C. Widmark. Evaluating conceptual definitions of ecosystem services and their implications. *Ecological Economics*, 126:132–138, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2016.04.003>.
- Z. Davies, J. Edmondson, A. Heinemeyer, J. Leake, and K. Gaston. Mapping an urban ecosystem service: quantifying above-ground carbon storage at a city-wide scale. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 48(5):1125–1134, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2011.02021.x>.
- R. de Groot. Function-analysis and valuation as a tool to assess land use conflicts in planning for sustainable, multi-functional landscapes. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 75(3-4):175–186, 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2005.02.016>.
- N. Debbage and M. Shepherd. The urban heat island effect and city contiguity. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 54:181–194, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2015.08.002>.
- N. Dempsey, C. Brown, S. Raman, S. Porta, M. Jenks, C. Jones, and G. Bramley. Elements of Urban Form. In M. Jenks and C. Jones, editors, *Dimensions of the Sustainable City*, chapter 2, pages 21–51. Springer, Dordrecht, Heidelberg, London, New York, future city, vo.l 2 edition, 2010. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-8647-2_2.
- H. A. C. Denier van der Gon, J. J. P. Kuenen, G. Janssens-Maenhout, U. Döring, S. Jonkers, and A. Visschedijk. TNO_CAMS high resolution European emission inventory 2000-2014 for anthropogenic CO₂ and future years following two different pathways. *Earth System Science Data Discussions*, (November):1–30, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2017-124>.

- F. Des Rosiers, M. Thériault, G. Biba, and M.-H. Vandersmissen. Greenhouse gas emissions and urban form: Linking households' socio-economic status with housing and transportation choices. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 44(5):964–985, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265813516656862>.
- D. C. Dickinson and R. J. Hobbs. Cultural ecosystem services: Characteristics, challenges and lessons for urban green space research. *Ecosystem Services*, 25:179–194, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2017.04.014>.
- L. Dijkstra and H. Poelman. Cities in Europe. The new OECD-EC Definition. 2012. URL https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/publications/regional-focus/2012/cities-in-europe-the-new-oecd-ec-definition.
- L. Dijkstra, H. Poelman, and P. Veneri. *The EU-OECD definition of a functional urban area*. OECD Regional Development Working Papers, No 2019/11, Paris, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1787/d58cb34d-en>.
- C. Dobbs, F. Escobedo, and W. Zipperer. A framework for developing urban forest ecosystem services and goods indicators. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 99(3-4):196–206, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2010.11.004>.
- C. Dobbs, D. Kendal, and C. Nitschke. Multiple ecosystem services and disservices of the urban forest establishing their connections with landscape structure and sociodemographics. *Ecological Indicators*, 43:44–55, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2014.02.007>.
- G. Donovan. Including public-health benefits of trees in urban-forestry decision making. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 22:120–123, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2017.02.010>.
- J. Dunn. A Fuzzy Relative of the ISODATA Process and Its Use in Detecting Compact Well-Separated Clusters. *Journal of Cybernetics*, 3(3):32–57, 1974. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01969727308546046>.
- EEA. *Urban Sprawl in Europe. The ignored challenge*. Publications Office of the European Union. EEA Report No 10/2006, Copenhagen, 2006. URL https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/eea_report_2006_10.
- EEA. *Floods*. Copenhagen, 2007. URL <https://www.eea.europa.eu/archived/archived-content-water-topic/water-resources/floods>.
- EEA. *Mapping the impacts of natural hazards and technological accidents in Europe. An overview of the last decade*. Publications Office of the European Union. EEA Report No 13/2010, Copenhagen, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.2800/62638>.
- EEA. Urban Atlas LCLU 2012, 2016. URL <https://land.copernicus.eu/local/urban-atlas/urban-atlas-2012>.
- EEA. Green Infrastructure typology of cities, 2017. URL <https://www.eea.europa.eu/themes/sustainability-transitions/urban-environment/sub-sections/urban-green-infrastructure/typology-for-urban-green-infrastructure>.
- EEA. High Resolution Layer: Dominant Leaf Type (DLT) 2012, Copernicus (data set), 2018a. URL <https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-resolution-layers/forests/dominant-leaf-type/status-maps/2012>.

- EEA. High Resolution Layer: Tree Cover Density (TCD) 2012, Copernicus (data set), 2018b. URL <https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-resolution-layers/forests/tree-cover-density/status-maps/2012>.
- EEA. *Emissions of air pollutants from transport*. European Environment Agency, Copenhagen, 2019a. URL <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/transport-emissions-of-air-pollutants-8/transport-emissions-of-air-pollutants-8>.
- EEA. *Greenhouse gas emissions from transport in Europe*. European Environment Agency, Copenhagen, 2019b. URL <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/transport-emissions-of-greenhouse-gases/transport-emissions-of-greenhouse-gases-12>.
- EEA. *Meteorological and hydrological droughts in Europe*. European Environment Agency, Copenhagen, 2020. URL <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/river-flow-drought-3/assessment>.
- EEA. Greenhouse gas emissions by source sector, EEA (data set), 2021. [link](#).
- EEA and FOEN. *Landscape Fragmentation in Europe. Joint EEA-FOEN report*. Publications Office of the European Union. EEA Report No 2/2011, Copenhagen, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.2800/78322>.
- EEA and FOEN. *Urban sprawl in Europe. Joint EEA-FOEN report*. Number 11. Publications Office of the European Union. EEA Report No 11/2016, Copenhagen, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.2800/143470>.
- EMEP and CORINAIR. Part B Background. In S. Richardson, editor, *EMEP/CORINAIR Atmospheric emission inventory guidebook, second edition*. 1999.
- EMEP and EEA. *EMEP/EEA air pollutant emission inventory guidebook 2019. Technical guidance to prepare national emission inventories*, EEA Report No 13/2019, 2019.
- EPA. *EPA Water Quality Standards Handbook, second edition*. United States Environmental Protection Agency, Office of Water, Office of Science and Technology, Washington DC, 1994.
- F. Escobedo, D. Nowak, J. Wagner, C. L. De la Maza, M. Rodríguez, D. Crane, and J. Hernández. The socioeconomics and management of Santiago de Chile's public urban forests. *Urban Forestry and Urban Greening*, 4(3-4):105–114, 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2005.12.002>.
- ESPON. *Territorial potentials for green infrastructure*. ESPON, Luxembourg, 2018. URL <https://www.espon.eu/working-paper-territorial-potentials-green-infrastructure>.
- Eurostat. *Urban Europe - Statistics on cities, towns and suburbs*. Publications office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2016 edition, 2016. URL <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-statistical-books/-/KS-01-16-691>.
- R. Ewing and S. Hamidi. Compactness versus Sprawl: A Review of Recent Evidence from the United States. *Journal of Planning Literature*, 30(4):413–432, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0885412215595439>.

- L. Fahrig. Ecological Responses to Habitat Fragmentation Per Se. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*, 48(1):1–23, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ecolsys-110316-022612>.
- FAO. Global Forest Resources Assessment 2010. Main report. *FAO Forestry Paper*, 163: 340, 2010. URL <http://www.fao.org/3/i1757e/i1757e.pdf>.
- FAO. Global ecological zones for FAO forest reporting: 2010 Update. *Forest resources Assessment Working Paper*, 179:42, 2012. URL <http://www.fao.org/docrep/017/ap861e/ap861e00.pdf>.
- FAO. Global Forest Resources Assessment 2020. Main report. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.4060/ca9825en>.
- J. A. Foley, R. Defries, G. P. Asner, C. Barford, G. Bonan, S. R. Carpenter, F. S. Chapin, M. T. Coe, G. C. Daily, H. K. Gibbs, J. H. Helkowski, T. Holloway, E. A. Howard, C. J. Kucharik, C. Monfreda, J. A. Patz, I. C. Prentice, N. Ramankutty, and P. K. Snyder. Global Consequences of Land Use. *Science*, 309(5734):570–575, 2005. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1111772>.
- S. Frank, C. Fürst, L. Koschke, and F. Makeschin. A contribution towards a transfer of the ecosystem service concept to landscape planning using landscape metrics. *Ecological Indicators*, 21:30–38, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2011.04.027>.
- P. Friedlingstein, M. O’Sullivan, M. W. Jones, R. M. Andrew, J. Hauck, A. Olsen, G. P. Peters, W. Peters, J. Pongratz, S. Sitch, C. Le Quéré, J. G. Canadell, P. Ciais, R. B. Jackson, S. Alin, L. E. O. C. Aragão, A. Arneeth, V. Arora, N. R. Bates, M. Becker, A. Benoit-Cattin, H. C. Bittig, L. Bopp, S. Bultan, N. Chandra, F. Chevallier, L. P. Chini, W. Evans, L. Florentie, P. M. Forster, T. Gasser, M. Gehlen, D. Gilfillan, T. Gkritzalis, L. Gregor, N. Gruber, I. Harris, K. Hartung, V. Haverd, R. A. Houghton, T. Ilyina, A. K. Jain, E. Joetzjer, K. Kadono, E. Kato, V. Kitidis, J. I. Korsbakken, P. Landschützer, N. Lefèvre, A. Lenton, S. Lienert, Z. Liu, D. Lombardozi, G. Marland, N. Metzler, D. R. Munro, J. E. M. S. Nabel, S.-I. Nakaoka, Y. Niwa, K. O’Brien, T. Ono, P. I. Palmer, D. Pierrot, B. Poulter, L. Resplandy, E. Robertson, C. Rödenbeck, J. Schwinger, R. Séférian, I. Skjelvan, A. J. P. Smith, A. J. Sutton, T. Tanhua, P. P. Tans, H. Tian, B. Tilbrook, G. van der Werf, N. Vuichard, A. P. Walker, R. Wanninkhof, A. J. Watson, D. Willis, A. J. Wiltshire, W. Yuan, X. Yue, and S. Zaehle. Global Carbon Budget 2020. *Earth System Science Data*, 12:3269–3340, 2020.
- B.-J. Fu, C.-H. Su, Y.-P. Wei, I. R. Willett, Y.-H. Lü, and G.-H. Liu. Double counting in ecosystem services valuation: causes and countermeasures. *Ecological research*, 26(1):1–14, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11284-010-0766-3>.
- M. Graça, P. Alves, J. Gonçalves, D. Nowak, R. Hoehn, P. Farinha-Marques, and M. Cunha. Assessing how green space types affect ecosystem services delivery in Porto, Portugal. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 170:195–208, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2017.10.007>.
- I. Grass, J. Loos, S. Baensch, P. Batáry, F. Librán-Embíd, A. Ficiciyan, F. Klaus, M. Riechers, J. Rosa, J. Tiede, K. Udy, C. Westphal, A. Wurz, and T. Tschardtke. Land-sharing/-sparing connectivity landscapes for ecosystem services and biodiversity conservation. *People and Nature*, 1(2):262–272, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.21>.

- C. Greene and A. Millward. Getting closure: The role of urban forest canopy density in moderating summer surface temperatures in a large city. *Urban Ecosystems*, 20(1): 141–156, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11252-016-0586-5>.
- S. Grimmond. Urbanization and global environmental change: local effects of urban warming. *The Geographical Journal*, 173(1):83–88, 2007. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4959.2007.232_3.x.
- C. Gromke and B. Ruck. On the Impact of Trees on Dispersion Processes of Traffic Emissions in Street Canyons. *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, 131(1):19–34, 2009. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10546-008-9301-2>.
- S. Guerreiro, R. Dawson, C. Kilsby, E. Lewis, and A. Ford. Future heat-waves, droughts and floods in 571 European cities. *Environmental Research Letters*, 13(3):034009, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aaaad3>.
- K. Gunawardena, M. Wells, and T. Kershaw. Utilising green and bluespace to mitigate urban heat island intensity. *Science of the Total Environment*, 584-585:1040–1055, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.01.158>.
- C. Haaland and C. C. Konijnendijk. Challenges and strategies for urban green-space planning in cities undergoing densification: A review. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 14(4):760–771, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2015.07.009>.
- D. Haase. Effects of urbanisation on the water balance - A long-term trajectory. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 29(4):211–219, 2009. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2009.01.002>.
- D. Haase and H. Nussli. Does urban sprawl drive changes in the water balance and policy? The case of Leipzig (Germany) 1870–2003. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 80(1-2):1–13, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2006.03.011>.
- D. Haase, N. Frantzeskaki, and T. Elmqvist. Ecosystem Services in Urban Landscapes: Practical Applications and Governance Implications. *AMBIO*, 43(4):407–412, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-014-0503-1>.
- Y. N. Harari. *Sapiens. A Brief History of Humankind*. Penguin Random House, London, 2011.
- L. Hein, K. van Koppen, R. de Groot, and E. van Ierland. Spatial scales, stakeholders and the valuation of ecosystem services. *Ecological Economics*, 57(2):209–228, 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2005.04.005>.
- J. Helms. *The dictionary of forestry*. Society of American Foresters, Bethesda, 1998.
- B. Heusinkveld, G.-J. Steeneveld, B. van Hove, C. Jacobs, and B. Holtslag. Spatial variability of the rotterdam urban heat island as influenced by urban land use. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 119(2):677–692, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2012JD019399>.
- L. R. Hutyrá, R. Duren, K. R. Gurney, N. Grimm, E. A. Kort, E. Larson, and G. Shrestha. Urbanization and the carbon cycle: Current capabilities and research outlook from the natural sciences perspective. *Earth's Future*, 2(10):473–495, 2014. ISSN 23284277. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014EF000255>.

- IEA. *World Energy Outlook 2008*. IEA Publications, Paris, 2008. URL <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2008>.
- IEA. *Global Energy Review 2021. Assessing the effects of economic recoveries on global energy demand and CO2 emissions in 2021*. IEA Publications, Paris, 2021. URL <https://www.iea.org/reports/global-energy-review-2021>.
- IPCC. Generic Methodologies Applicable to Multiple Land-Use Categories. In *Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories*, volume 4 AFOLU, pages 4.1–4.83. 2006a. URL https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2006gl/pdf/4_Volume4/V4_02_Ch2_Generic.pdf.
- IPCC. Forest lands. In *Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories*, volume 4 AFOLU, pages 2.1–2.59. 2006b. URL http://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2006gl/pdf/4_Volume4/V4_04_Ch4_Forest_Land.pdf.
- IPCC. Grassland. In *Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories*, volume 4 AFOLU, pages 6.1–6.49. 2006c. URL https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2006gl/pdf/4_Volume4/V4_06_Ch6_Grassland.pdf.
- IPCC. Wetlands. In *Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories*, volume 4 AFOLU, pages 7.1–7.24. 2006d. URL https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2006gl/pdf/4_Volume4/V4_07_Ch7_Wetlands.pdf.
- IPCC. Summary for Policymakers and Technical Summary. In O. Edenhofer, R. Pichs-Madruga, Y. Sokona, E. Farahani, S. Kadner, K. Seyboth, A. Adler, I. Baum, S. Brunner, P. Eickemeier, B. Kriemann, J. Savolainen, S. Schlömer, C. von Stechow, T. Zwickel, and J. Minx, editors, *Climate Change 2014: Mitigation of Climate Change. Part of the Working Group III Contribution to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.*, pages 1–30. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 2014. ISBN 9781107415416. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CB09781107415416.005>.
- IPCC. *Climate Change 2014: Mitigation of Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CB09781107415416>.
- IPCC. Summary for Policymakers. In V. Masson-Delmotte, P. Zhai, H.-O. Pörtner, D. Roberts, J. Skea, P. Shukla, A. Pirani, W. Moufouma-Okia, C. Péan, R. Pidcock, J. S. Connors, B. Matthews, Y. Chen, X. Zhou, M. Gomis, E. Lonnoy, T. Maycock, M. Tignor, and T. Waterfield, editors, *Global warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change.*, pages 1–24. Cambridge, 2019. URL https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/sites/2/2019/05/SR15_{_}SPM_{_}version_{_}report_{_}LR.pdf.
- IPCC. Summary for Policymakers. In V. Masson-Delmotte, P. Zhai, A. Pirani, S. Connors, C. Péan, S. Berger, N. Caud, Y. Chen, L. Goldfarb, M. Gomis, M. Huang, K. Leitzell, E. Lonnoy, J. Matthews, T. Maycock, T. Waterfield, O. Yelekçi, R. Yu, and B. Zhou, editors, *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, pages SPM1–SPM41. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 2021.
- Y. R. Jabareen. Sustainable Urban Forms. *Journal of Planning Education and Research*, 26(1):38–52, sep 2006. ISSN 0739-456X. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739456X05285119>.

- M. Z. Jacobson. *Atmospheric pollution: history, science, and regulation*. Cambridge University Press, 2nd edition, 2012.
- J. A. Jaeger, R. Bertiller, C. Schwick, and F. Kienast. Suitability criteria for measures of urban sprawl. *Ecological Indicators*, 10(2):397–406, 2010. ISSN 1470160X. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2009.07.007>.
- S. Janhäll. Review on urban vegetation and particle air pollution – Deposition and dispersion. *Atmospheric Environment*, 105:130–137, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2015.01.052>.
- J. Kaplan, K. Krumhardt, and N. Zimmermann. The prehistoric and preindustrial deforestation of Europe. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 28(27-28):3016–3034, 2009. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2009.09.028>.
- N. Karvosenoja, V.-V. Paunu, M. Savolahti, K. Kupiainen, A. Karppinen, J. Kukkonen, and O. Hänninen. A high-resolution national emission inventory and dispersion modelling—is population density a sufficient proxy variable? In *International Technical Meeting on Air Pollution Modelling and its Application*, pages 199–204. Springer, 2018.
- R. Kellett, A. Christen, N. C. Coops, M. van der Laan, B. Crawford, T. R. Tooke, and I. Olchovski. A systems approach to carbon cycling and emissions modeling at an urban neighborhood scale. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 110(1):48–58, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2012.10.002>.
- F. Kong, C. Sun, F. Liu, H. Yin, F. Jiang, Y. Pu, G. Cavan, C. Skelhorn, A. Middel, and I. Dronova. Energy saving potential of fragmented green spaces due to their temperature regulating ecosystem services in the summer. *Applied Energy*, 183:1428–1440, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.09.070>.
- C. Konijnendijk. A decade of urban forestry in Europe. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 5(2):173–186, 2003. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1389-9341\(03\)00023-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1389-9341(03)00023-6).
- C. C. Konijnendijk, R. M. Ricard, A. Kenney, and T. B. Randrup. Defining urban forestry – A comparative perspective of North America and Europe. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 4(3-4):93–103, 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2005.11.003>.
- S. Kotthaus and C. S. B. Grimmond. Identification of Micro-scale Anthropogenic CO₂, heat and moisture sources - Processing eddy covariance fluxes for a dense urban environment. *Atmospheric Environment*, 57:301–316, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2012.04.024>.
- J. J. P. Kuenen, A. J. H. Visschedijk, H. A. C. Denier van der Gon, S. Jonkers, and G. Janssens-Maenhout. TNO-CAMS European CO₂ emissions 2000-2014 v1, Zenodo (data set). 2017. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.112889>.
- M. Kuittinen, C. Moinel, and K. Adalgeirsdottir. Carbon sequestration through urban ecosystem services. *Science of The Total Environment*, 563-564:623–632, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.03.168>.
- K. Lachowycz and A. Jones. Towards a better understanding of the relationship between greenspace and health: Development of a theoretical framework. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 118:62–69, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2012.10.012>.

- N. Larondelle and D. Haase. Urban ecosystem services assessment along a rural–urban gradient: A cross-analysis of European cities. *Ecological Indicators*, 29:179–190, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2012.12.022>.
- R. Lemoy and G. Caruso. Evidence for the homothetic scaling of urban forms. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 47(5):870–888, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2399808318810532>.
- C. W. Y. Li, G. P. Brasseur, H. Schmidt, and J. P. Mellado. Error induced by neglecting subgrid chemical segregation due to inefficient turbulent mixing in regional chemical-transport models in urban environments. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics Discussions*, 21: 483–503, 2020. ISSN 1680-7316. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-21-483-2021>.
- R. Lindsay. Climate Change: Atmospheric Carbon Dioxide. NOAA, 2020. URL <https://www.climate.gov/news-features/understanding-climate/climate-change-atmospheric-carbon-dioxide>.
- Z. Liu, C. He, Y. Zhou, and J. Wu. How much of the world’s land has been urbanized, really? A hierarchical framework for avoiding confusion. *Landscape Ecology*, 29(5): 763–771, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-014-0034-y>.
- S. Livesley, G. McPherson, and C. Calfapietra. The Urban Forest and Ecosystem Services: Impacts on Urban Water, Heat, and Pollution Cycles at the Tree, Street, and City Scale. *Journal of Environment Quality*, 45(1):119, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2015.11.0567>.
- G. M. Mace, B. Reyers, R. Alkemade, R. Biggs, F. S. Chapin, S. E. Cornell, S. Díaz, S. Jennings, P. Leadley, P. J. Mumby, A. Purvis, R. J. Scholes, A. W. Seddon, M. Solan, W. Steffen, and G. Woodward. Approaches to defining a planetary boundary for biodiversity. *Global Environmental Change*, 28:289–297, 2014. ISSN 0959-3780. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2014.07.009>.
- Y. Makido, S. Dhakal, and Y. Yamagata. Relationship between urban form and CO2 emissions: Evidence from fifty Japanese cities. *Urban Climate*, 2:55–67, dec 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2012.10.006>.
- E. Maltby and M. Acreman. Ecosystem services of wetlands: pathfinder for a new paradigm. *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, 56(8):1341–1359, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02626667.2011.631014>.
- M. Marchi, V. Niccolucci, R. Pulselli, and N. Marchettini. Urban sustainability: CO2 uptake by green areas in the historic centre of Siena. *International Journal of Design & Nature and Ecodynamics*, 12(4):407–417, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.2495/DNE-V12-N4-407-417>.
- I. Markevych, E. Thiering, E. Fuertes, D. Sugiri, D. Berdel, S. Koletzko, A. von Berg, C.-P. Bauer, and J. Heinrich. A cross-sectional analysis of the effects of residential greenness on blood pressure in 10-year old children: results from the GINIplus and LISAplus studies. *BMC Public Health*, 14(1):477, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-14-477>.
- A. Martilli. An idealized study of city structure, urban climate, energy consumption, and air quality. *Urban Climate*, 10(Part 2):430–446, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2014.03.003>.

- N. McIntyre. Urban ecology. In I. Douglas, D. Goode, M. Houck, and D. Maddox, editors, *The Routledge Handbook of Urban Ecology*, chapter 1, page 10. Routledge, London, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203839263.ch1>.
- T. Mexia, J. Vieira, A. Príncipe, A. Anjos, P. Silva, N. Lopes, C. Freitas, M. Santos-Reis, O. Correia, C. Branquinho, and P. Pinho. Ecosystem services: Urban parks under a magnifying glass. *Environmental Research*, 160:469–478, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2017.10.023>.
- Millennium Ecosystem Assessment. Living Beyond Our Means: Natural Assets and Human Well-being, 2005. URL <https://www.millenniumassessment.org/documents/document.429.aspx.pdf>.
- M. Mitchell, A. Suarez-Castro, M. Martinez-Harms, M. Maron, C. McAlpine, K. Gaston, K. Johansen, and J. Rhodes. Reframing landscape fragmentation’s effects on ecosystem services. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 30(4):190–198, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2015.01.011>.
- NASA’s Goddard Space Flight Center. A Year In The Life Of Earth’s CO₂. *Goddard Media Studios*, 2014. URL <https://svs.gsfc.nasa.gov/11719>.
- M. Neuman. The compact city fallacy. *Journal of Planning Education and Research*, 25(1):11–26, 2005. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739456X04270466>.
- J. Niemelä. Ecology and urban planning. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 8(1):119–131, 1999. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1008817325994>.
- NOAA. Trends in Atmospheric Carbon Dioxide. Global Monthly Mean CO₂. *Global Monitoring Laboratory (last access: 6th of May 2021)*, 2021. URL <https://gml.noaa.gov/ccgg/trends/global.html>.
- D. Nowak. Atmospheric Carbon Reduction by Urban Trees. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 37(3):207–217, 1993. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jema.1993.1017>.
- D. Nowak and D. Crane. Carbon storage and sequestration by urban trees in the USA. *Environmental Pollution*, 116(3):381–389, 2002. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0269-7491\(01\)00214-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0269-7491(01)00214-7).
- D. Nowak, D. Crane, and J. Stevens. Air pollution removal by urban trees and shrubs in the United States. *Urban Forestry and Urban Greening*, 4(3-4):115–123, 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2006.01.007>.
- D. Nowak, S. Hirabayashi, A. Bodine, and R. Hoehn. Modeled PM_{2.5} removal by trees in ten U.S. cities and associated health effects. *Environmental Pollution*, 178:395–402, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2013.03.050>.
- OECD. *Definition of Functional Urban Areas (FUA) for the OECD metropolitan database*. OECD Publishing, Paris, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264174108-en>.
- OECD. *Rethinking Urban Sprawl: Moving towards sustainable cities*. OECD Publishing, Paris, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264189881-en>.
- Office of the Deputy Prime Minister. Planning Policy Guidance 2 : Green belts. Technical report, 1995. URL <http://www.dcp-online.co.uk/dcpcontent/odpm/Planning%20Policy%20Guidance/P.P.G.02/index.htm>.

- T. Oke. The energetic basis of the urban heat island. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 108(455):1–24, 1982. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.49710845502>.
- T. Oke. Urban heat islands. In I. Douglas, D. Goode, M. Houck, and D. Maddox, editors, *The Routledge Handbook of Urban Ecology*, page 12. Routledge, London, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203839263.ch11>.
- D. W. O’Neill, A. L. Fanning, W. F. Lamb, and J. K. Steinberger. A good life for all within planetary boundaries. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(2):88–95, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0021-4>.
- A. O’Sullivan. The First Cities. In R. J. Arnott and D. P. McMillen, editors, *A Companion to Urban Economics*, chapter 3, pages 40–54. John Wiley & Sons, 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470996225.ch3>.
- T. Panagopoulos, J. A. González Duque, and M. Bostenaru Dan. Urban planning with respect to environmental quality and human well-being. *Environmental Pollution*, 208 (Part A):137–144, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2015.07.038>.
- B.-J. Park, Y. Tsunetsugu, T. Kasetani, H. Hirano, T. Kagawa, M. Sato, and Y. Miyazaki. Physiological Effects of Shinrin-yoku (Taking in the Atmosphere of the Forest)—Using Salivary Cortisol and Cerebral Activity as Indicators—. *Journal of PHYSIOLOGICAL ANTHROPOLOGY*, 26(2):123–128, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.2114/jpa2.26.123>.
- J. Parr. Spatial Definitions of the City: Four Perspectives. *Urban Studies*, 44(2):381–392, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00420980601075059>.
- G. Pastorello, C. Trotta, E. Canfora, H. Chu, D. Christianson, Y. W. Cheah, C. Poindexter, J. Chen, A. Elbashandy, M. Humphrey, P. Isaac, and et al. The FLUXNET2015 dataset and the ONEFlux processing pipeline for eddy covariance data. *Scientific data*, 7 (225):1–27, 2020. ISSN 20524463. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0534-3>.
- M. Peel, B. Finlayson, and T. McMahon. Updated world map of the Köppen-Geiger climate classification. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 11(5):1633–1644, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-11-1633-2007>.
- S. Pickett, W. Burch Jr., S. Dalton, T. Foresman, M. Grove, and R. Rowntree. A conceptual framework for the study of human ecosystems in urban areas. *Urban Ecosystems*, 1(4): 185–199, 1997. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1018531712889>.
- S. Pickett, M. Cadenasso, M. Grove, C. Nilon, R. Pouyat, W. Zipperer, and R. Costanza. Urban Ecological Systems: Linking Terrestrial Ecological, Physical, and Socioeconomic Components of Metropolitan Areas. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, 32 (1):127–157, 2001. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ecolsys.32.081501.114012>.
- L. Poelmans, A. Van Rompaey, and O. Batelaan. Coupling urban expansion models and hydrological models: How important are spatial patterns? *Land Use Policy*, 27(3): 965–975, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2009.12.010>.
- R. Pouyat, P. Groffman, I. Yesilonis, and L. Hernandez. Soil carbon pools and fluxes in urban ecosystems. *Environmental Pollution*, 116:S107–S118, 2002. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0269-7491\(01\)00263-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0269-7491(01)00263-9).

- R. Privitera, V. Palermo, F. Martinico, A. Fichera, and D. La Rosa. Towards lower carbon cities: urban morphology contribution in climate change adaptation strategies. *European Planning Studies*, 26(4):812–837, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2018.1426735>.
- R Core Team. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria, 2019. URL <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- S. Raciti, L. Hutyrá, P. Rao, and A. Finzi. Inconsistent definitions of “urban” result in different conclusions about the size of urban carbon and nitrogen stocks. *Ecological Applications*, 22(3):1015–1035, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1890/11-1250.1>.
- E. Rall, C. Bieling, S. Zytynska, and D. Haase. Exploring city-wide patterns of cultural ecosystem service perceptions and use. *Ecological Indicators*, 77:80–95, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2017.02.001>.
- C. Raudsepp-Hearne, G. Peterson, and E. Bennett. Ecosystem service bundles for analyzing tradeoffs in diverse landscapes. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 107(11):5242–5247, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0907284107>.
- K. Raworth. *Doughnut Economics : Seven Ways to Think Like a 21st-century Economist*. Random House, London, 2017.
- J. Rockström, W. Steffen, K. Noone, Åsa Persson, F. S. Chapin, E. Lambin, T. M. Lenton, M. Scheffer, C. Folke, H. J. Schellnhuber, B. Nykvist, C. A. de Wit, T. Hughes, S. van der Leeuw, H. Rodhe, S. Sörlin, P. K. Snyder, R. Costanza, U. Svedin, M. Falkenmark, L. Karlberg, R. W. Corell, V. J. Fabry, J. Hansen, B. Walker, D. Liverman, K. Richardson, P. Crutzen, and J. Foley. Planetary boundaries: Exploring the safe operating space for humanity. *Ecology and Society*, 14(2), 2009. URL <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26268316>.
- B. Scharenbroch. Urban Trees for Carbon Sequestration. In R. Lal and B. Augustin, editors, *Carbon Sequestration in Urban Ecosystems*, pages 121–138. Springer, Dordrecht, 2012. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-2366-5_6.
- M. Schindler and G. Caruso. Urban compactness and the trade-off between air pollution emission and exposure: Lessons from a spatially explicit theoretical model. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 45:13–23, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2014.01.004>.
- N. Schwarz. Urban form revisited-Selecting indicators for characterising European cities. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 96(1):29–47, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2010.01.007>.
- W. Selmi, C. Weber, E. Rivière, N. Blond, L. Mehdi, and D. Nowak. Air pollution removal by trees in public green spaces in Strasbourg city, France. *Urban Forestry and Urban Greening*, 17(2):192–201, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2016.04.010>.
- A. Semadeni-Davies, C. Hernebring, G. Svensson, and L.-G. Gustafsson. The impacts of climate change and urbanisation on drainage in Helsingborg, Sweden: Suburban stormwater. *Journal of Hydrology*, 350(1-2):114–125, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2007.11.006>.
- K. C. Seto, B. Güneralp, and L. R. Hutyrá. Global forecasts of urban expansion to 2030 and direct impacts on biodiversity and carbon pools. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 109(40):16083–16088, 2012. ISSN 00278424. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1211658109>.

- W. Steffen, K. Richardson, J. Rockström, S. E. Cornell, I. Fetzer, E. M. Bennett, R. Biggs, S. R. Carpenter, W. de Vries, C. A. de Wit, C. Folke, D. Gerten, J. Heinke, G. M. Mace, L. M. Persson, V. Ramanathan, B. Reyers, and S. Sörlin. Planetary boundaries: Guiding human development on a changing planet. *Science*, 347(6223), 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1259855>.
- U. Steinhardt, F. Herzog, A. Lausch, E. Müller, and S. Lehmann. Hemeroby index for landscape monitoring and evaluation. In Y. Pykh, E. Hyatt, and R. Lenz, editors, *Environmental Indices - System Analysis Approach*, pages 237–254. EOLSS Publications, Oxford, 1999.
- M. Strohbach and D. Haase. Above-ground carbon storage by urban trees in Leipzig, Germany: Analysis of patterns in a European city. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 104(1):95–104, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2011.10.001>.
- R. Stull. Horizontal Winds, 2020. URL <https://geo.libretexts.org/@go/page/9593>. (Online; accessed 2021-08-09).
- I. Super. *Quantification and attribution of urban fossil fuel emissions through atmospheric measurements*. PhD thesis, Wageningen University, 2018.
- H. Taha. Urban climates and heat islands: albedo, evapotranspiration, and anthropogenic heat. *Energy and Buildings*, 25(2):99–103, 1997. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7788\(96\)00999-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7788(96)00999-1).
- I. Thomas, J. Jones, G. Caruso, and P. Gerber. City delineation in European applications of LUTI models: review and tests. *Transport Reviews*, 38(1):6–32, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2017.1295112>.
- A. Townsend-Small and C. I. Czimczik. Carbon sequestration and greenhouse gas emissions in urban turf. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 37(2):1–5, jan 2010. ISSN 00948276. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009GL041675>.
- L. Trepl. *Towards a theory of urban biocoenoses*. Balogh Scientific Books, The Hague, 1995.
- K. Turner, S. Georgiou, and B. Fisher. The ecosystem services approach: Valuation of multi-functional wetlands. In K. Turner, S. Georgiou, and B. Fisher, editors, *Valuing ecosystem services - The case of multi-functional Wetlands*, pages 25–58. Earthscan, London, 2008.
- C. Twohig-Bennett and A. Jones. The health benefits of the great outdoors: A systematic review and meta-analysis of greenspace exposure and health outcomes. *Environmental Research*, 166:628–637, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2018.06.030>.
- K. Tzoulas, K. Korpela, S. Venn, V. Yli-Pelkonen, A. Kaźmierczak, J. Niemela, and P. James. Promoting ecosystem and human health in urban areas using Green Infrastructure: A literature review. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 81(3):167–178, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2007.02.001>.
- United Nations. Kyoto Protocol to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. Technical report, 1998.
- United Nations. World Urbanization Prospects: The 2014 Revision, Highlights. Technical report, New York, 2014. URL <https://population.un.org/wup/Publications/Files/WUP2014-Highlights.pdf>.

- United Nations. World Urbanization Prospects 2018 Highlights. Technical report, New York, 2019. URL <https://population.un.org/wup/Publications/Files/WUP2018-Highlights.pdf>.
- A. Urgeghe, D. Breshears, S. Martens, and P. Beeson. Redistribution of Runoff Among Vegetation Patch Types: On Ecohydrological Optimality of Herbaceous Capture of Run-On. *Rangeland Ecology & Management*, 63(5):497–504, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.2111/REM-D-09-00185.1>.
- M. van den Berg, W. Wendel-Vos, M. van Poppel, H. Kemper, W. van Mechelen, and J. Maas. Health benefits of green spaces in the living environment: A systematic review of epidemiological studies. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 14(4):806–816, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2015.07.008>.
- M. van den Bosch and Å. Ode Sang. Urban natural environments as nature-based solutions for improved public health – A systematic review of reviews. *Environmental Research*, 158:373–384, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2017.05.040>.
- S. Varrette, P. Bouvry, H. Cartiaux, and F. Georgatos. Management of an academic hpc cluster: The ul experience. In *Proc. of the 2014 Intl. Conf. on High Performance Computing & Simulation (HPCS 2014)*, pages 959–967, Bologna, July 2014. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/HPCSim.2014.6903792>.
- H. Vejre, J. Primdahl, and J. Brandt. The Copenhagen Finger Plan: Keeping a green space structure by a simple planning metaphor. In *Europe’s Living Landscapes. Essays on exploring our identity in the countryside*, pages 310–331. KNNV Publishing, Boston, 2007. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004278073_020.
- J. Vieira, P. Matos, T. Mexia, P. Silva, N. Lopes, C. Freitas, O. Correia, M. Santos-Reis, C. Branquinho, and P. Pinho. Green spaces are not all the same for the provision of air purification and climate regulation services: The case of urban parks. *Environmental Research*, 160:306–313, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2017.10.006>.
- K. Wallace. Classification of ecosystem services: Problems and solutions. *Biological Conservation*, 139(3-4):235–246, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2007.07.015>.
- U. Walz and C. Stein. Indicators of hemeroby for the monitoring of landscapes in Germany. *Journal for Nature Conservation*, 22(3):279–289, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2014.01.007>.
- A. Wania, M. Bruse, N. Blond, and C. Weber. Analysing the influence of different street vegetation on traffic-induced particle dispersion using microscale simulations. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 94(1):91–101, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2011.06.036>.
- J. Ward. Hierarchical Grouping to Optimize an Objective Function. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 58(301):236–244, 1963. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2282967>.
- K. Ward, S. Lauf, B. Kleinschmit, and W. Endlicher. Heat waves and urban heat islands in Europe: A review of relevant drivers. *Science of The Total Environment*, 569-570: 527–539, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.06.119>.

- E. A. Wentz, A. M. York, M. Alberti, L. Conrow, H. Fischer, L. Inostroza, C. Jantz, S. T. Pickett, K. C. Seto, and H. Taubenböck. Six fundamental aspects for conceptualizing multidimensional urban form: A spatial mapping perspective. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 179:55–62, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2018.07.007>.
- E. White and J. Brown. The template: patterns and processes of spatial variation. In G. Lovett, C. Jones, M. Turner, and K. Weathers, editors, *Ecosystem function in heterogeneous landscapes*, pages 31–47. Springer, New York, 2007. https://doi.org/10.1007/0-387-24091-8_3.
- V. Whitford, R. Ennos, and J. Handley. City form and natural process: indicators for the ecological performance of urban areas and their application to merseyside, uk. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, (2):91–103. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-2046\(01\)00192-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-2046(01)00192-X).
- J. Wolch, J. Byrne, and J. Newell. Urban green space, public health, and environmental justice: The challenge of making cities ‘just green enough’. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 125:234–244, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2014.01.017>.
- K. Wolf, S. Lam, J. McKeen, G. Richardson, M. van den Bosch, and A. Bardekjian. Urban Trees and Human Health: A Scoping Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(12):4371, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17124371>.
- M. Yamaguchi, M. Deguchi, and Y. Miyazaki. The Effects of Exercise in Forest and Urban Environments on Sympathetic Nervous Activity of Normal Young Adults. *Journal of International Medical Research*, 34(2):152–159, 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1177/147323000603400204>.
- M. Zhao, F. A. Heinsch, R. R. Nemani, and S. W. Running. Improvements of the modis terrestrial gross and net primary production global data set. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 95(2):164–176, 2005. ISSN 0034-4257. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2004.12.011>.

E. List of symbols and acronyms

Symbols	Meaning
B	Budget
c	Cell
d	Day or Weekday
E	Emissions
ha	Hectare (100×100 m)
Gt	Metric gigaton (1×10^9 t = 1 billion t)
iso	Country (using ISO code)
m	Month
S	Sequestration
t	Metric ton (1000 kg = 1 Mg)
y	Year

Table E.1: List of symbols

Abbreviations	Meaning
C	Carbon
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CH ₄	Methane
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Environment Agency
EDGAR	Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research
ES	Ecosystem Services
EU	European Union
EZ	Ecological Zone
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FUA	Functional Urban Area
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
GHG	Greenhouse gases
LU	Land use
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
SNAP	Selected Nomenclature for Air Pollution
TNO	Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek ^a
UES	Urban Ecosystem Services
UFES	Urban Forest Ecosystem Services

Table E.2: List of acronyms

^aEnglish: Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research

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